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Report on citizens' involvement in emergency communication

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In Task 4.1, entitled “Citizens’ Involvement in Emergency Communications”, COSMIC seeks to examine the various roles that citizens may have in communications during emergencies. Also, through this task, the partners aimed to map the relationship between the use of different types of media and communication technologies—including mass media, as well as new media technologies—and citizens’ involvement in emergency communications as

- 1) potential or actual volunteers (first responders) who may aid emergency response and rescue;
- 2) as social activists who may utilize online networks to organize, coordinate, collaborate or mobilize during political crises; and
- 3) as citizens who report on emergencies and political crises.

With respect to the role that citizens may play as first responders, Task 4.1 focused on how various communication media are utilized by response organizations and government agencies to identify, recruit, network with and train citizens. In addition, we also aimed to investigate the nature of the communication strategies/approaches that are utilized by organizations reaching out to volunteers. In order to accomplish this goal, the partners engaged in an in-depth analysis of citizen awareness programs and volunteer recruitment and training processes in four different countries: Turkey, Italy, United Kingdom, and Greece. This analysis indicates:

- Citizens’ involvement in emergency response via social media can not only enhance the availability of data about the impact of an emergency but also help (at least potentially) organizations make sense of existing data through crowdsourced filtering.
- Agencies tend to utilize social media extensively to reach out to the citizens. However, in some of the countries analyzed, we also observed inconsistencies in the extent and types of utilization of social media.
- While social media is extensively utilized, we do not see sufficient evidence to conclude that the use of social media has also changed the communicative approaches of agencies trying to reach citizens as volunteers. Namely, in terms of the mode of communication, the dominant approach is still “communicating to citizens” rather than “communicating with citizens”. In many respects, for example, we see very scant evidence suggesting that agencies utilize citizens who may have expertise (as a result of their own experience) to help improve emergency preparedness.
- In addition to conventional training methods (such as lectures, workshops, online videos), many organizations across countries are now utilizing innovative technologies (like G-Force simulators and virtual reality) and techniques (like earthquake drill camps) to raise awareness and reach out to the public.

With respect to social activism as a citizen involvement in crises (predominantly political crises), the partners aimed to provide a detailed description of how various media technologies are utilized by social activists. Specifically, the task focused on how social activist formations use media to recruit members and/or form networks, communicate ideas, and coordinate action. We observe that:

- With the help of online network technologies (including social media and mobile networks), social activist formations can create organizations with horizontal structures that allow for direct participation in decision making processes.
- Relatedly, partly with the help of online networking capabilities, contemporary social activist formations are highly flexible, forming and dissolving in short periods of time and enabling the formation of affinity groups.
- Social activism is increasingly becoming glocal in the sense that while issues may be specific to different localities, the approaches, networks, and communicative actions are often global.
- While information and communication technologies facilitate more efficient coordination, organization and communication for social activist networks, mass media still play an important role with respect to the extent to which ideas can diffuse to the larger public.

Regarding the role that citizens may play as reporters (i.e., citizen journalists) during emergencies and crises, the partners aimed to discuss in detail issues related to news selection processes, types of coverage (commentary vs. news), types of sources utilized by citizen journalists and citizen journalists' perceptions regarding issues like reliability of information.

In order to do so, the partners have engaged in a two-pronged analysis of citizen journalism that combines results from a content analysis of the articles published by citizens who reported about four emergencies/crises with results from online interviews conducted with a sample of citizens whose reports were content analyzed.

To our knowledge, the content analysis procedures developed for this task constitutes one of the first attempts to systematically quantify the content of citizen journalism coverage of emergencies.

Overall, this section of the Task 4.1 provides some important findings:

- We find evidence supporting the notion that in addition to the ease with which citizens now can create and share content online, one of the key factors that drive the increase in citizen journalistic coverage of emergencies is the dissatisfaction that citizens have

about the ways in which mainstream media perform their agenda setting, watchdog, and sense-making duties.

- Our analysis of the content of citizen journalists' coverage of recent emergencies/crisis suggest that citizen journalists may have been, partly, successful in terms of challenging the monopoly that established media organizations have over whose voice gets to be heard by the public. That is, at least to some extent, the information sources that citizen journalists utilize underline an approach whereby citizen journalists report for citizens from citizens.
- While, in our interviews, citizen journalists frequently claimed that the editorial freedom they have enables them to do away with reporting conventions associated with mainstream journalism, our content analysis data suggests that citizen journalists frequently adopt episodic frames that are associated with the detached form of reporting in commercial media.
- An alarming finding pertains to the measures that citizen journalist (fail to) utilize to verify information while reporting news. Namely, by adopting what has been called as the "publish and then filter" approach; some citizen journalists expect that the readers will filter out false information after it is published by them. This may have important implications for the extent to which citizen journalism can progress as a reliable source of information by the public.

Chapter 1: Introduction

1 INTRODUCTION

The widespread adoption of new media technologies and “social media” applications that have emerged within the last two decades have the potential to transform the nature of communication during emergencies and crises. New research indicates that a key dimension of this transformation pertains to the role that citizens may play in emergency communications and crisis management.

First, use of social media applications by the public can potentially enhance information gathering and problem solving capacities of response organizations and government agencies.¹ Commenting on this potential benefit of social media, Justin Herman, the social media lead for the U.S. Office of Citizen Services and Innovative Technologies at the General Services Administration, recently opined that “social media offers that unique ability in order to engage and listen in real time to the needs of the citizens” during an emergency situation like Hurricane Sandy.² The faster flow of information in social media, and the ensuing intelligence derived from social media play a key role in the development of first response stations, directing volunteers to places of need, and coordinating first response actions of response organizations and volunteers.³

Second, particularly in political crises, the increased availability of new media technologies that allow networking of individuals also offers new possibilities for citizens to organize, engage and coordinate action as social activists. With the help of online networks, activists can locally and globally push grassroots ideas, organize and coordinate action (such as during the Occupy movements), get their voices heard by the wider public. Also significantly, the use of network technologies have the potential to transform the organizational structures of activist networks in ways that may have long term implications for the future of political organizations and participatory politics.⁴

Third, social media bring about new means through which citizens can produce/share/get access to information. The types of information that are now much more readily available for individuals include, but are not limited to, information produced and shared by fellow citizens and information shared by various response organizations using social media platforms.⁵ In this respect, the growth of social media platforms means that individuals are no longer merely consumers of information but also, in many occasions their producers, distributors, curators, and verifiers. Indeed, literature on citizen journalism suggests that the increased role that

¹ Starbird, Katei and Leysia Palen, “Pass It On: Retweeting in Mass Emergency”, *International ISCRAM Conference*, No. May 2010, 2012. <https://www.cs.colorado.edu/~palen/starbirdpaleniscramretweet.pdf>.

Wegscheider, Stephanie, Tobias Schneiderhan, Alexander Mager, Hendrik Zwenzner, Joachim Post, and Günter Strunz, “Rapid Mapping in Support of Emergency Response after Earthquake Events,” *Natural Hazards*, Vol. 68, No. 1, pp. 181–195.

² Justin Herman, quoted in O’Connell, Michael, “Agencies turn to social media to engage public in an emergency,” *Federal News Radio*, 12 November 2012, <http://www.federalnewsradio.com/445/3152420/Agencies-turn-to-social-media-to-engage-public-in-an-emergency>

³ Corbin, Kenneth. "Tapping Social Media In Disasters." *Cio* 25.12 (2012): 28. *Business Source Complete*. Harmanci Seren, Arzu Kader, “Gezi Park and Nurses.,” *Public Health Nursing* (Boston, Mass.), Vol. 30, No. 5, 2013, pp. 387–389.

⁴ Castells, Manuel, *Networks of Outrage and Hope*, Polity Press, Cambridge, 2012. Juris, Jeffrey Scott, “The New Digital Media and Activist Networking Within Anti-Corporate Globalization Movements,” *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, Vol. 597, No. 1, 2005a, pp. 189-208.

⁵ Thomas, Steff, “Social Media Changing the Way FEMA Responds to Disasters,” *National Defense*, 2013, <http://www.nationaldefensemagazine.org/archive/2013/September/Pages/SocialMediaChangingtheWayFEMARespondstoDisasters.aspx>

citizens play in production and dissemination of information create new opportunities, such as disintermediation of information,⁶ as well as new challenges, such as potential for misinformation to be disseminated quickly through online networks.⁷

In the light of these discussions, the aim of this report is to describe the various roles that citizens assume in emergency communications and how media and communication technologies are utilized to engage citizens as 1) first responders, 2) social activists, 3) citizen reporters/journalists.

Chapter 2 of this report will focus on “citizens as volunteers” and how media technologies, including conventional forms of mass media and new technologies and applications, can be leveraged to involve citizens as first responders during emergencies. The chapter will start with a description of current literature as it pertains to use of communication technologies during emergencies, the impact of such technologies on first response behaviour of citizens, and how media technologies can be used to recruit, train and organize citizens.

Following this brief overview, the chapter will have four different sections focusing on how volunteer organizations and government agencies communicate to the public to increase awareness of emergencies, recruit and train volunteers in Turkey, Greece, Italy, and UK. More specifically, each of these sections will describe in detail actions taken by volunteer organizations and government agencies to 1) train citizens in emergency preparedness; 2) provide training materials to the public; 3) recruit and network with potential volunteers. Also, each of these sections will provide an analysis of the media mix (mass media, social media, mobile applications, face-to-face communications) that the organizations in question utilize to reach out to the public.

In Chapter 3, the report will outline the changes in contemporary social activism and trace the potential impact of network technologies on the transformation of social activist formations. Specifically, the chapter will start with a summary of the main characteristics of contemporary social activist networks. This section will focus on three salient characteristics of contemporary social activist formations: 1) “glocalization”, 2) “participatory politics and horizontal organization structures” and 3) “autonomous flexibility.”

In the sections that follow this summary of the main characteristics of contemporary social activist networks, the chapter will create a typology of activist formations according to their organization logic along three axes that can be named as “looseness”, “ecology of presence”, and “objective of presence”. Then the chapter will outline types of online and offline actions that are often seen in social activism and will discuss the role communication technologies play in organization and decision making processes of social activist organizations.

In Chapter 4, the report will focus on the role that citizens may play as reporters or journalists during emergencies. The chapter will start with a theoretical discussion of questions related to the definition of the concept of citizen journalism and the role that communication technologies may have played in the emergence of citizen journalism as a mode of reporting. Next the chapter will discuss opportunities and challenges that are brought about by citizen journalism in the context of citizen involvement in emergency communications.

⁶ Anden-Papadopoulos, K., “Media Witnessing and the ‘Crowd-Sourced Video Revolution’,” *Visual Communication*, Vol. 12, No. 3, July 8, 2013, pp. 341–357. Waldman, Steven, “The Media Food Chain and the Functions of Journalism,” *The Information Needs of Communities: The Changing Media Landscape in a Broadband Age*, Carolina Academic Press, Durham, NC, 2011, pp. 242–247.

⁷ Kuhn, Martin, “Interactivity and prioritizing the human: A code of blogging ethics”, *Journal of Mass Media Ethics*, 2007, Vol. 22, No. 1, pp.18-36.

After this theoretical overview, the chapter will summarize primary data collected about citizen journalism activities during four recent emergencies or crises: Xynthia Storm, Boston Bombings, Gezi Protests, and Haiti Earthquake. These four emergencies or crises were chosen for data collection in order to follow up on the data from the case studies conducted for Deliverable 2.2. of the COSMIC project.⁸

The primary data collected for this chapter was obtained through a content analysis of the articles published by a sample of citizen journalists who reported on the emergencies in question and in-depth interviews conducted with a subsample of the citizen journalists whose articles were content analyzed.

Specifically, the content analysis of citizen journalists' articles focus on questions related to the balance between information and commentary; types of news sources that are utilized by the citizen journalists; targets and sources of criticism; expression of negative emotions (and sources that emotions are attributed to) and use of episodic frames (focusing on telling what transpired in an event) vs. thematic frames (providing contextual information regarding the causes and solutions, thereby contributing to sense-making capabilities of the readers).

In conjunction with the content analysis results, the data collected from the interviews will focus on what motivates individuals to engage in citizen reporting, citizen journalists' perceptions regarding the definition of citizen journalism and how their activities differ from professional journalists.

Overall, by providing a synthesis of literature and supplementing this literature with analyses of primary and secondary data regarding citizens' involvement in emergencies/crises as volunteers, activists and journalists, these three chapters will help map the relationship between the rise of information and communication technologies and the types of roles that are assumed by citizens in emergency/crisis communications and emergency response.

⁸ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., "Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations", *COSMIC*, 2013

Chapter 2: Citizens as First Responders

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2 CITIZENS AS FIRST RESPONDERS

2.1 INTRODUCTION

In his article “Agility and Discipline: Critical Success Factors for Disaster Response”, John R. Harrald argues that “designers of organizational systems for emergency response, like designers of software systems, must ensure both discipline (structure, doctrine, and process) and agility (creativity, improvisation, and adaptability)”.⁹ Accordingly, both capability and will play a strong role on how such actions are prepared and implemented. While, as Harrald points out, first response is not a complete solution to a crisis, as further structuring and organization is needed for levels of problems that need more resources than the resources available to early responders, first responders constitute an important component of emergency response because of their ability to deliver first aid, provide initial organization and on-site expertise until more organized and resourced help comes to the scene.

Citizen involvement in emergency response includes both preparation and response. A more organized, capable and resourceful response will be more likely to ensure that first response will be provided in a timely manner, and resources and experts will be mobilized efficiently. Enhancing citizens' preparedness involves not only improving their ability to provide first response before “organized” help arrives but also making sure that citizens are able to collaborate with each other as well as response authorities.

More than 50 years ago, Cuba had just been hit by cyclone Flora. The establishment of a national Civil Defence System followed the natural disaster. This system included phases like preparation, first response, and recovery, and was updated with a law about 13 years later. To some extent, cyclones, as the events are seasonal storms, are predictable. With the laws and regulations including the Civil Defence System, every year in Cuba, two days are designated for nationwide disaster preparation and education. Everyone in the country is included, and everyone is trained to know what to do first during such a crisis, what to expect from the government, and how to get involved in the recovery. The government authorities have information about the risk level of each region, the sections of the population are under threat and in what way, and how to help those people and regions. The involvement of citizens in events like the annual nationwide preparations in Cuba illustrates the importance of citizen involvement in times of crises.¹⁰

Also important to note is that not only the participation of citizens in crises, but also the nature of their participation, or how they participate is important. For example, the Turkish Medical Association estimates that during the Gezi Parkı protests in Turkey (Summer 2013), about 8000 people were injured after violent clashes between the police force and protestors. Because the number of ambulances were limited, and because of road blocks making it difficult to reach hospitals in the surrounding areas, doctors and medical school students established first aid tents and help stations in different parts of cities to assist the injured citizens.¹¹ This decision by doctors and medical school students to provide assistance to citizens in (or near) protest zones not only underlines the importance of mobilization of private citizens for assistance and first response, but also points to the potential hurdles that

⁹ Harrald, John R., “Agility and Discipline: Critical Success Factors for Disaster Response,” *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, Vol. 604, No. 1, January 1, 2006, pp. 256–272, [p. 256].

¹⁰ Bermejo, Pedro Mas, “Preparation and Response in Case of Natural Disasters: Cuban Programs and Experience,” *Journal of Public Health Policy*, Vol. 27, No. 1 (2006), pp. 13-21, [p.16].

¹¹ Reynolds, James, and Zeynep Erdim “Turks Question Police Use of Force During Protests,” *BBC News*, 2 July 2013. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-europe-23142657>.

citizens may face in organizing for and providing emergency response. For example, reports indicate that the Turkish Ministry of Health opened an investigation into the voluntary health centres established during the protests,¹² prompting the Turkish Medical Association to publish a press release explaining that not helping citizens in need is a crime in Turkish laws and regulations, and such first response organizations are the keys to preventing further harm and are acts of professional commitment and humanitarian values.¹³

This chapter of the report will focus on the different roles citizens assume as first responders in emergencies and man-made crises. Particularly, we will focus on citizens’ role as first responders both in terms of citizens’ preparation and training before a crisis, and in terms of organization and implementation of action during or right after a crisis. In doing so, we will also discuss the role media and communication technologies, and particularly social media, may play in relation to citizens’ involvement in emergency response.

The next section (Section 2.2) of this report will give provide an overview of recent examples on how citizens utilize new media for emergency response. Sections that follow this brief overview will provide in-depth analyses of how communication technologies are utilized by first response organizations (NGOs and government authorities) to involve citizens in emergency preparation and response. This section will focus on emergency response organizations (and their utilization of communication technologies to train and involve citizens) in four countries: Italy, Turkey, United Kingdom and Greece. With the exception of Turkey, which is not a European Union Member State, all countries that were selected rank in the top 10 in the European Union in terms of number of disasters between 2003-2013 (data summarized in Deliverable 1.1. of the COSMIC project; see Figure 2.1. below).¹⁴

Figure 2.1: Number of disasters in European Member States 2003-2013

¹² “Turkish Health Ministry opens probe into voluntary health center in Gezi Park,” *Hurriyet Daily News*, 14 June 2013, <http://www.hurriyetaidailynews.com/turkish-health-ministry-opens-probe-into-voluntary-health-center-in-gezi-park-.aspx?pageID=238&nid=48838>

¹³ “Is Volunteer Health Services and Humanitarian Intervention to Gezi Park Protestors ‘legal’ or Not?,” *Turkish Medical Association*, 18 June 2013, <http://www.tb.org.tr/en/index.php/tuem-haberler-blog/179-ttb/1216-is-volunteer-health-services-and-humanitarian-intervention-to-gezi-park-protestors-legal-or-not->

¹⁴ Watson, Hayley et al., “Deliverable 1.1: Report on security crises with high societal impact”, *COSMIC*, 1 April 2013.

2.2 COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND CITIZENS IN FIRST RESPONSE

This section of the chapter will give examples from recent emergencies and crises to provide an introductory overview of 1) how citizens may utilize information and communication technologies in first response after crises; 2) the potential impact of use of such technologies on citizens' involvement in emergency response; 3) issues related to training of citizens for emergency response. The content of this section should serve as a preliminary introduction to the next section whereby we discuss in great detail the involvement of citizens in emergency preparedness and response in four different countries (Italy, Turkey, Greece, and UK).

2.2.1 Use of communication technologies and media

As discussed in the introduction section, emergency response comprises both preparation for response before an emergency and responding to the emergency during and after it transpires. The preparation phase consists of training, planning and staying ready for a perceived potential crisis or a likely emergency situation. Wegscheider et al. take two case studies on Van (Turkey) and Haiti earthquakes to inquire into the characteristics of a vastly-studied emergency situation: an earthquake.¹⁵ According to Wegscheider et al., casualty and harm assessment not only after an earthquake, but also before it makes it easier for the stakeholders to deal with emergencies and respond more efficiently, especially for a risky region.¹⁶ Wegscheider et al., provide several different examples to usages of technological means in the region or internationally, such as satellite-based damage maps, casualty estimations based on previously collected population distribution data, optical input on damaged building and on-demand point-based visual interpretation approaches. These examples indicate that such methods, especially existing data on population distribution or satellite imagery, may be very useful in response action and preparation, especially for natural emergencies.

While preparations before crises are most likely to evolve around approaches and planning according to the estimations about the immediate needs that will come up after a crisis, response action right after a disaster show more diverse examples of the utilization of technology and media. Media, and particularly information and communication technologies are increasingly being used to communicate and organize after an emergency or a man-made crisis. For example, Ewert and Dekker provide instances of how mass media has been used by citizens in the aftermath of emergencies. They report that talkback radio—a radio format based on discussions about topical issues, generally featuring a single host and interviews with different guests related to the topic—is mostly used for getting information on a specific subject, and this aspect of talkback radio has been useful in Australia in community formation, distribution of public health information and response during crises. Accordingly, listeners of talkback radio have been found to be more mobile, and their main purpose in listening to talkback radio is to get information about a specific event or policy. Certainly, as Ewert and Dekker's example suggests, battery powered radios in some homes can still be a more viable option to communicate, learn and organize in crises and emergencies when there

¹⁵ Wegscheider, Stephanie, Tobias Schneiderhan, Alexander Mager, Hendrik Zwenzner, Joachim Post, and Günter Strunz, "Rapid Mapping in Support of Emergency Response after Earthquake Events," *Natural Hazards*, Vol. 68, No. 1, pp. 181–195.

¹⁶ *Ibid.* pp.181-182

is a power outage or communications breakdown in an area.¹⁷

Furthermore, advances in information and communication technologies, and, relatedly, increased penetration of the Internet and mobile networks offer new ways to respond to emergencies. Consider, for example, how social media was used for information purposes during the H1N1 outbreak in 2009. According to an analysis of utilization of three social media platforms—Blogs, Twitter, and Delicious—a major source of the information being bookmarked was from the CDC, an organization with a strong reputation and level of credibility in the crisis situation and a traditional source of information active in a non-traditional media environment. The CDC was also the most tagged key organization and social media site. Other traditional sources of information included newspapers and newspaper blogs, demonstrating a clear interaction among traditional and new media.¹⁸

Another example of technology usage in a crisis is the recent Boston bombing event. High quality CCTV footage was used by the biometrics company that processed the images via a face recognition software for the identification of the suspects. Also, FBI collected visual information from social media sources, too. The experts say face recognition technology might be affected from the changes in people's faces in time, however, passport photos, driver's licenses and similar data can be used to identify people just like the usage of fingerprints.¹⁹ Likewise, in the case of typhoon Pablo in Philippines in 2012, citizen participation in emergency response via social media was considerably high. A new system named MicroMappers, developed by Patrick Meier, was utilized to filter out the information on social media, narrow down the data to efficiently deal with and create a combination of "micro-tasking" and "disaster-mapping". The MicroMappers system, which has been tried out for some time now, was utilized in the aftermath of the crisis in Philippines not only by authorities involved in mapping of the crisis but also by citizen volunteers. In many respects, this example illustrates that with the help of new crowdsourcing technologies, citizens can engage in emergency response not only by providing information that can then be processed by authorities but also by helping process the information provided by other citizens.²⁰

2.2.2 Media technology and its impact on first response behaviour by citizens

Mainstream media tend to lack the ability to directly communicate with the citizens, or directly involve citizens, as they have to maintain a standard of procedures, methods, and content according to their area of focus, format or ownership.²¹ For example, as discussed in Deliverable 2.2. of the COSMIC project,²² after the first police raid on the Gezi Park protests

¹⁷ Ewart, Jacqui, and Sidney Dekker, "Radio, Someone Still Loves You! Talkback Radio and Community Emergence during Disasters," *Continuum*, Vol. 27, No. 3, June 2013, pp. 365–381, [p. 376].

¹⁸ Freberg, Karen, Michael J. Palenchar, and Shari R. Veil, "Managing and Sharing H1N1 Crisis Information Using Social Media Bookmarking Services," *Public Relations Review*, Vol. 39, No. 3, September 2013, pp. 178–184 [p. 183].

¹⁹ O'Mahony, Jennifer, "Boston Marathon Bombs: How Investigators Use Technology to Identify Suspects," *The Telegraph*, 19 April 2013, <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/technology/social-media/10005569/Boston-Marathon-bombs-how-investigators-use-technology-to-identify-suspects.html>.

²⁰ Gilber-Knight, Ariel, "Social Media, Crisis Mapping and the New Frontier in Disaster Response," *The Guardian*, 8 October 2013, <http://www.theguardian.com/global-development-professionals-network/2013/oct/08/social-media-microtasking-disaster-response>.

²¹ Kollmeyer, Christopher J., "Corporate Interests: How the News Media Portray the Economy," *Social Problems*, Vol. 51, No. 3 (August 2004), pp. 432-452, [p.435].

²² Papadimitriou, Alex et al., "Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations", *COSMIC*, 2013.

at the end of May 2013, many of the mainstream television channels were criticized for ignoring the events in the news making process, or broadcast unrelated programming such as (in the case of CNN Turk) documentary about penguins.²³

Communicating via mass media during a crisis might prove difficult for regular citizens, as they first need to reach the centre of distribution. If such information does not reach such centres of distribution via reporters, press releases or wire services, the information does not get coverage in mass media platforms such as newspapers or television channels. In addition to this problem, when the information of such an event reaches such channels to be shared with the public, it is usually too late. For example, a regular newspaper correspondent gets massive amounts of press releases in a day via e-mail, and has limited time to go through some of them, while being able to create news stories on only a few of them (also called the Filtering Function or the Gate Keeping Function of news media).

Conversely, the advantage new media technologies bring is that the content is usually produced and shared by communities of people, rather than commercial and/or government controlled entities.²⁴ Especially the Internet and social media platforms involve citizens directly and make media content creators out of regular people. New media technologies including social media tools and mobile devices make it easier and faster to connect with people, communicate an idea or a piece of information, and mobilize people and resources. Use of online networks helps individuals in different locations, having different occupations to gather and make use of their collective skills and information bases.²⁵

Reportedly, on a typical day, thousands of mentions are made by the users to the Twitter account of the American Red Cross and the amount of correspondence dramatically increases in a time of a crisis.²⁶ Social media usage by citizens and the integration of social media in everyday lives of the citizens create a constant flow of information, and as this flow can theoretically be accessed by anyone with an internet connection, for many media users, the reliance on mass media is becoming less of a necessity each day.²⁷ Especially in the last decade, for many individuals, the primary source of communication during crises is becoming the citizens themselves.²⁸ The potential availability of real-time information on the location of people (victims) and resources provides important benefits for first response, and dissemination of solutions to problems faced during a crisis. For example, right after the Haiti earthquake, citizens used new media technologies to map the region, organize a fundraiser, and find missing people.²⁹

New media technologies and online platforms not only help distribute information, but also help organize action and mobilize people, as well as resources. Citizens often use social media to organize strategies in a crisis. Typically, faster information flow in social media

²³Schmitt, Mirjam, "Türkische Medien Zeigen Lieber Pinguin-Dokus," *Zeit Online*, 4 June 2013, <http://www.zeit.de/politik/ausland/2013-06/medien-tuerkei-proteste-fernsehen>.

²⁴ Wilson, Samuel M. And Leighton C. Peterson, "The Anthropology of Online Communities," *Annual Review of Anthropology*, Vol 31 (2012), pp. 449-467, [449-450].

²⁵ Rice, Ronald E., "Task Analyzability, Use of New Media, and Effectiveness: A Multi-Site Exploration of Media Richness," *Organization Science*, Vol. 3, No. 4, 1992, pp. 475-500, [p.480].

²⁶ Corbin, Kenneth. "Tapping Social Media In Disasters." *Cio* 25.12 (2012): 28. *Business Source Complete*, p. 28.

²⁷ Rideout, Victoria J, Ulla G. Foehr and Donald F. Roberts, "Media in the Lives of 8-to 18-Year-Olds," Generation M2 Kaiser Family Foundation, January 2010.

²⁸ Beers, David, "The Public Sphere and Online, Independent Journalism," *Canadian Journal of Education*, Vol. 29, No. 1 (2006), pp. 109-130, [p.119].

²⁹ Ward, Amy Sample, "The Social Media Response to Disaster in Haiti," *NTEEN*, 17 February 2010, <http://www.nten.org/blog/2010/02/17/social-media-response-disaster-haiti>.

mostly helps immediate response solutions like organizing help stations, directing people to the places of need, and dispersing introductions to first responders in crises.³⁰

For example, during the clashes between the police force and the protesters in Gezi Park protests, volunteering doctors, nurses and medical students established tents and first-aid stations for the people injured, and they reached the people in need via social media, sometimes sharing their phone numbers on social media platforms, distributing the locations of help stations via social media, and following up on the locations and health statuses of people in need via social media.³¹

Likewise, after the earthquake in Van, Turkey, a significant amount of people and resource mobilization was achieved using new technologies and social media. Google's "Person Finder" system allowed citizens to post and receive information about missing people, while a Twitter campaign named "Evim Evindir Van"³² received responses from tens of thousands of people who wanted to accept the people who were left homeless after the first few hours of the earthquake into their homes.³³ Organizing via Twitter and Facebook and using donation services, citizens were able to provide equipment, medical aid, and other supplies (like food, clothing) urgently needed by the victims of the earthquake, while also helping the flow of information and giving some relief to the families and friends of the victims via their communication on the Internet.³⁴ According to the article on Time, citizens in this particular example also utilized social media to urge private organizations to provide disaster relief and help the victims by helping the shipment of aid packages and sending supplies.³⁵

Likewise, as Tsang summarizes, after the accident in the nuclear power plant in Fukushima, Japan, when there were doubts regarding the reliability of official sources (as the government purportedly withheld information from the public in the aim of avoiding panic), citizens used social media to gain information on the possible dangers of the situation they were in. The blog entries by experts among citizens helped the remaining citizens understand the situation and plan accordingly, as they included technical details in a language that regular citizens would be able to understand.³⁶

2.2.3 Emergency response training for citizens

As previously discussed in COSMIC deliverables D1.1 and D1.2, there is a wide range of potential emergency situations with various needs and stakeholders.³⁷ Consequently, one important question pertains to how communities can be prepared for situations that by nature

³⁰ Harmanaci Seren, Arzu Kader, "Gezi Park and Nurses.," *Public Health Nursing* (Boston, Mass.), Vol. 30, No. 5, 2013, pp. 387–389.

³¹ Ibid, pp. 387–388.

³² Can be translated as "My home is your home"

³³ "Turkey's Earthquake: Social Media to the Rescue," *Time World*, 24 October 2011, <http://world.time.com/2011/10/24/turkeys-earthquake-social-media-to-the-rescue/>

³⁴ Blair, Kelsey, "Social Media Helps Turkey After Earthquakes," *SocialTimes*, 25 October 2011, https://socialtimes.com/social-media-helps-turkey-after-earthquakes_b82083

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Tsang, Monique, "Lessons From Fukushima: Do not Ignore Citizen Media," *World Energy Council*, 11 March 2013, <http://www.worldenergy.org/news-and-media/news/lessons-from-fukushima-do-not-ignore-citizen-media/>.

³⁷ Watson, Hayley et al., "Deliverable 1.1: Report on security crises with high societal impact", *COSMIC*, 1 April 2013. Watson, Hayley et al., "Deliverable 1.2: Report on search and rescue actions", *COSMIC*, 1 April 2013.

violate regular patterns, which are thought of while preparing for them.³⁸ Some crises such as extreme temperatures and floods can, potentially, be predicted in advance (although, our discussions of Xynthia Storm in Deliverable D1.2 underlines how errors in predictions regarding the extent of a flood may create additional threats).³⁹ On the other hand, crises like earthquakes or political unrest might prove very hard to anticipate.

As some crises are by their nature “surprises”, preparation shall be made according to the cost and benefit assessment, considering which threat requires attention.⁴⁰ For example, a non-governmental search and rescue organization in Turkey, AKUT, prepares volunteers with seminars, field exercises, and search and rescue trainings by experts. According to the policy guidelines of AKUT, their aim in preparation and training includes raising awareness for political, cultural, social issues that might affect people's lives during a crisis.⁴¹ Similarly, governmental organizations like AFAD,⁴² also in Turkey, keep guidelines on their websites and bulletins on how a citizen can participate in response and preparation in the time of a natural disaster or an emergency. AFAD works on crisis preparation by organizing or distributing guidelines on field exercises in business environments, residences and schools; issuing training programs on first aid, nuclear disaster management, search and rescue operations and basic disaster management in emergencies.

Moreover, there are also newly developed methods for crisis management training. Crisis management training can be made easier and more accessible with the use of utilities like game simulations and 3D maps, interactive mobile technologies, and smart boards that help users visualize each situation.⁴³ Being connected via mobile devices, or communicating on smart boards might improve organizational skills of the participants of the training. According to Walker, Giddings and Armstrong, creating scenarios for pre- and post-incident situations is also important in visualizing a possible crisis environment, and when gaming is used for simulating such an environment, it could help account for other external factors like the political situation, weather:

It is the sequence of events to which the crisis management must respond. For a flood, it would specify the times and places where specific dikes were breached, services were disrupted, persons were swept away, etc. The context plus the crisis prior to the start of the game would provide the players with the necessary background information about the situation to enable them to specify the initial conditions for their response activities. Also, of course, the purpose of the game would provide several parameters that are vital to the scenario, such as the setting, potential list of actors, and many of the “rules of the game.”⁴⁴

³⁸ Boin, Arjen, and Allan McConnell, “Preparing for critical infrastructure breakdowns: the limits of crisis management and the need for resilience,” *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, Vol. 15, Issue 1, 2007, pp. 50-59, [53].

³⁹ Watson, Hayley et al., “Deliverable 1.1: Report on security crises with high societal impact”, *COSMIC*, 1 April 2013.

⁴⁰ Watson, Hayley et al., “Deliverable 1.2: Report on search and rescue actions”, *COSMIC*, 1 April 2013

⁴¹ “AKUT Arama Kurtarma Derneği Tüzüğü,” n.d. <http://www.akut.org.tr/tuzuk>.

⁴² Prime Ministry Disaster & Emergency Management Presidency.

⁴³ Ahmad, Alexandre, Olivier Balet, Jesse Himmelstein, Arjen Boin, Maaïke Schaap, Paolo Brivio, Fabio Ganovelli, Enrico Gobetti, Giovanni Pintore, Jean-Baptiste de la Riviere, “Interactive Simulation Technology for Crisis Management and Training: The INDIGO Project,” *International ISCRAM Conference*, No. April 2012, 2012, pp. 2–6. <http://www.iscramlive.org/ISCRAM2012/proceedings/144.pdf>, [pp.3-4].

⁴⁴ Walker, Warren E., Jordan Giddings, and Stuart Armstrong, “Training and Learning for Crisis Management Using a Virtual Simulation/gaming Environment,” *Cognition, Technology & Work*, Vol. 13, No. 3, 2011, pp. 163–173, [p.165].

Walker, Giddings and Armstrong additionally argue that usage of gaming for crisis management preparation creates a suitable environment for studying the effects of stressful, overloaded conditions on decision making.⁴⁵

Given this brief discussion regarding the potential benefits that new communication technologies may offer in enhancing citizen involvement in emergency response, the next section will provide an in-depth summary of the utilization of various communication and media technologies in recruitment of, training and coordination of citizens as “first responders”. The section will address the following questions:

- Level of involvement of citizens in emergency preparedness.
- How citizen experts are identified, recruited and networked.
- The respective role that conventional media, web, and social media play in citizen outreach programs.
- Allocation of resources (funding, time, content) for utilization of conventional and new media.
- Availability of training materials (e.g., simulation games, brochures, videos etc.) for general public.

Since the analyses were based on secondary data about the questions raised above, the level of detail for each institution analyzed and each country analyzed may vary as a function of the availability of such data.

⁴⁵ Ibid. p.168.

2.3 INVOLVEMENT OF CITIZENS AS VOLUNTEERS: REPORT ON TURKEY

2.3.1 Introduction

In its recent history, Turkey has experienced a considerable number of high impact natural disasters, majority of which were earthquakes that have killed over tens of thousands of people and decimated large parts of cities like Izmit, Sakarya, Erzincan and Van (Figure 2.2).⁴⁶ Particularly after the devastating earthquakes in Marmara and Black Sea region in 1999 and in eastern Turkey (Van) in 2011, and as a result of the fact that a large majority of the population in Turkey lives in the vicinity of highly active fault lines, the governmental and non-governmental organizations in Turkey have started to redefine their agenda of preparation against the earthquake. Some of the measures taken in the last decade include large-scale renewal of infrastructure (e.g., transportation, energy), urban redevelopment projects, within which old, damaged and/or poorly constructed buildings are demolished, and introduction of a national (required but still not highly adopted) earthquake insurance system. Authorities and non-governmental organizations have also been active in trying to raise public’s awareness regarding earthquake preparedness and response.

Figure 2.2: Disaster Occurrence in Turkey (1980-2010)⁴⁷

This report will summarize how six government and non-government organizations reach out to and involve (or fail to do so) citizens in emergency preparedness. Particularly, the report will focus on the use of various communication technologies, media (mass media and social media) and strategies to increase public awareness and involve citizens in emergency preparedness. The organizations are listed below. As can be seen, a majority of the organizations were established after the 1999 Marmara Earthquake:

⁴⁶ “İlk 72 Saat”, AFAD, 5. 01 October 2013. <https://www.afad.gov.tr/Dokuman/TR/14-2012092815355-ilk72saat1.pdf>

⁴⁷ Prevention Web, "Disaster Statistics - Turkey - Europe - Countries & Regions - PreventionWeb.net". <http://www.preventionweb.net/english/countries/statistics/?cid=177>

Prime Ministry Disaster & Emergency Management Presidency (AFAD)

AFAD is the largest governmental organization related to natural disasters. AFAD was established in 2009. It executes its duties under the deputy Prime Minister. AFAD works for the cooperation and coordination of organizations and companies in Turkey for activities preventing the natural disasters and minimizing the cost of the natural disasters.

Ministry of Internal Affairs Disaster and Crisis Management Centre (AADYM)

AADYM aims to help solve the problems at the time of a natural disaster or any kind of crisis. AADYM is also responsible for informing AFAD when problems go beyond the capabilities of AADYM during a crisis.⁴⁸

Health Emergency Coordination Centre (SAKOM) Medical Rescue Team (UMKE)

UMKE was established in 2004 as a part of the Health Project on Disasters, led by the Ministry of Health and other government authorities. The main goal of this organization is to create local medical teams to increase the efficiency of rescue and medical treatment services in case of natural disasters in order to develop the quality of rescue process and treatments in the case of natural disasters.

Turkish Red Crescent

Among other functions, The Turkish Red Crescent operates the Disaster Management Centre (AFOM). AFOM was established in 2001. It cooperates with the Red Crescent's other divisions in order to prepare and protect the civilians against the natural disasters.

Search and Rescue Association

AKUT is the most widely known non-governmental organization related to natural disasters in Turkey. It was founded in 1994 as a voluntary rescue association by a group of mountaineers. It is important, because it was the first voluntary first response organization for natural disasters in Turkey before the earthquake of 1999. After 1999, the importance of AKUT and its activities and rescue missions here in Turkey and elsewhere (e.g., in Greece) served as an example for the growth of similar organizations in Turkey.⁴⁹

Search Rescue Research Association (AKA)

AKA was founded after the 1999 Marmara Earthquake. Its main purpose is to conduct research on emergency response and provide emergency response and rescue services after disasters. In addition, the organization also aims to prepare the society for earthquakes and other kind of disasters.

2.3.2 Citizen training and participation in emergency preparedness

Among the organizations listed above, two organizations, AKUT and AFAD stand out in terms of the projects they have developed to raise public's awareness about emergency preparedness and to receive input from them for emergency preparedness. Since, as mentioned in the introduction section, Earthquakes have been and are expected to continue to be the most important threat for citizens' safety in Turkey, most of these projects have focused on Earthquake preparedness.

⁴⁸ "İçişleri Bakanlığı Afet ve Acil Durum Yönetim Merkezi Yönergesi", AADYM, 2. 15 September 2013.

http://www.icisleriafad.gov.tr/ortak_icerik/icisleriafad/%C4%B0%C3%A7i%C5%9Fleri%20Bakanl%C4%B1%C4%9F%C4%B1%20Afet%20ve%20Acil%20Durum%20Y%C3%B6netim%20Merkezi%20Y%C3%B6nergesi.pdf

⁴⁹ "Tarihçe", AKUT. 25 July 2013. <http://www.akut.org.tr/tarihce>

AKUT's projects typically address all steps of emergency preparedness and response through education programs that focus on what precautions to take before, how to act during and what to do in the aftermath of an earthquake. Our research indicates that most of the education programs that AKUT develops primarily aim to reach youth and students (although other segments of the population is reached to various media campaigns and education programs).

One of the more widely known projects that AKUT has is the “Continue to Live Turkey” project (Figure 2.3, on the left), which aims to prepare citizens against disasters by teaching them how to minimize the immediate sources of threat within a household during an earthquake (e.g., how to position themselves during the earthquake, what not to do during the earthquake). In this project, AKUT volunteers have visited several cities in Turkey with a van equipped with a G-force earthquake simulator in order to show citizens the difference between a safe room and an unsafe room at the time of an earthquake. The project also shows the importance of the earthquake insurance for recovery after an Earthquake.⁵⁰

Another project of AKUT was a musical for children (Figure 2.3, on the right). Through this project, the organization aims to inform children about the damage earthquakes can cause and how they can take precautions to survive in an earthquake.

AKUT's other projects include a training programme for high school students to prepare them for natural disasters and a mobile training project that travels around Turkey to educate (so far close to 4000) citizens and personnel working for public authorities. This project is called “The Anatolian van.” In this project, a movie about how to be prepared for the natural disasters is shown to the public in towns across Turkey. In addition to the movie, AKUT personnel also give seminars about earthquakes and distribute handbooks to the citizens.⁵¹

Figure 2.3: (Left) A scene from the G-force earthquake simulator of the “Continue to Life, Turkey” project videos on Youtube. The video shows several scenes from the places the project team went to (The video is in Turkish). For the video of the simulator click on the image. (Right) The poster of the musical project for children. It says: “One of us is all of us and all of us are AKUT.”

As a government organization, AFAD has also developed several key projects to reach out to both citizens and government employees. Indeed, AFAD has declared 2013 as the year for informing Turkish citizens for disaster preparedness. With a motto “Turkey, Prepared for Disasters,” AFAD created the “Disaster Awareness Seminars and Workshops.” With these workshops, AFAD tries to prepare citizens and staff of government entities to be ready for earthquakes. In another project called “First 72 Hours”⁵² AFAD targeted families, schools and

⁵⁰ “Projeler”, AKUT. 2013. <http://www.akut.org.tr/hayata-devam-turkiye>

⁵¹ “Anadolu Tiri Sonuç Raporu.” AKUT. 2004. <http://www.akut.org.tr/akut-anadolu-tiri-sonuc-raporu>

⁵² “İlk 72 Saat,” AFAD. 2013. <https://www.afad.gov.tr/TR/HbIcerikListele.aspx?ID=18>

workplaces to enhance the self-sufficiency of individuals and organizations by training them about survival skills and first response within the first 72 hours after a disaster.

In addition to the seminars and workshops, AFAD also is active in involving citizens, or more specifically citizen experts, in developing ideas for emergency response. For example, in a recent contest, AFAD invited amateur and professional designers for design prototypes for shelter tents to be used after a natural disaster. Unlike other projects we have observed, the fact that AFAD includes not only certified experts but also amateurs is worth noting because of its potential to get input from a wider public.

AFAD is currently involved in two other projects called National Earthquake Research Program (UDAP) and National Earthquake Strategy and Action Plan (UDSEP)⁵³. UDAP is akin to a support action project for UDSEP and both involve the preparation of strategy the state will follow to prepare Turkey for earthquakes until 2023. Accordingly, these projects aim to raise the awareness and preparation level of the citizens against earthquakes, to predict the damage and the risk earthquakes can cause, to decrease the level of this damage and to create a safe living environment. In order to create safe living environments, the project plans to repair old buildings and to construct more durable buildings throughout Turkey.

AFAD also strives to involve citizens (or more accurately citizen experts) in development of emergency preparedness plans. For example, individuals from research organizations, universities and other departments with at least a PhD degree can offer their projects/ideas to improve disaster preparation and implementation of disaster recovery/relief efforts.⁵⁴ Although potentially useful in terms of identifying beneficial projects, the exclusion of the remainder of the public (i.e., those without a PhD, and those without an Assistant Professorship title) may result in a less diverse input for developing disaster preparedness plans. Yet, this effort by AFAD can still be considered as exemplary in terms of creating incentives for the public to contribute to the enhancement of emergency preparedness.

AFAD's Centre in Istanbul, with the support of the Istanbul Governor's Office, has another important project called "The Reduction of Seismic Risk and Crisis Preparation in Istanbul (ISMEP)." The website of this project encourages citizens to take the one hour training of disaster preparation.⁵⁵

AADYM's actions about the participation of the citizens in preparation are relatively less clear when compared to AKUT and AFAD. Partners were unable to gather sufficient information about the details of projects or training programs that AADYM is involved. However, like AFAD, the website of AADYM provides detailed instructions on what actions to take at the time of natural disasters and how to prepare for them.⁵⁶

Like AFAD and AKUT, the Turkish Red Crescent has several projects intended for training citizens involving citizens:

1. "How to Live in a Safe Environment with Red Crescent:" This project seems to have been specifically tailored for reaching out to middle school students. The purpose of this project is to teach middle school students about natural disasters, their outcomes,

⁵³ "UDSEP," *AFAD*. 2013. <https://www.afad.gov.tr/TR/IcerikDetay.aspx?ID=77>

⁵⁴ "UDAP Proje Önerileri". *AFAD*. 2013. <https://www.afad.gov.tr/TR/IcerikDetay.aspx?ID=87&IcerikID=525>

⁵⁵ For more information about the Project, see <http://www.guvenliyasam.org/>

⁵⁶ AADYM http://www.icisleriafad.gov.tr/default_B0.aspx?content=1

what should be done for protection and finally what Red Crescent does in case of a natural disaster in Turkey.⁵⁷

2. Risk and Capacity Evaluation Project (VCA): A local project in Izmir, a western city in Turkey, the VCA aims to evaluate the risk people have against the natural disasters and how this risk can be decreased.⁵⁸ Unlike in other projects, citizen involvement seems to be low in this project; this may be due to the limited geographical reach of the project.
3. Basic Disaster Awareness Training (ABCD): ABCD is a three and a half hour training program that aims to increase the awareness level of the citizens and make the citizens realize that with small measures such as knowing how to organize the furniture for creating a safer place or knowing what to do before and after earthquakes, they can protect themselves against the natural disasters.⁵⁹
4. Training for Reduction of Non-Structural Risks (YOTA): Similar to the project described in the previous paragraph, YOTA aims to show how citizens can live in safer places against the natural disasters. Again, the project aims to teach citizens how precautions like proper arrangement of furniture and immobilizing large furniture may help reduce the “non-structural” threats posed by earthquakes and decrease injuries that stem from individuals being crushed by toppling furniture.

In addition to these training programs, the Turkish Red Crescent is also undertaking a project that seeks to involve representatives of what they name as the “civil leaders” citizens in emergency preparedness: Organizing the Leaders of the Society for Reduction of the Destruction of Natural Disasters.⁶⁰ This project aims to reach out to likely opinion leaders within the society and utilize their help in increasing public's emergency preparedness and awareness. Unfortunately, this project seems to have identified a very limited set of stakeholders as potential contributors: religious leaders, teachers, police representatives and district governors.

Unlike AFAD, AKUT and the Turkish Red Crescent, UMKE and AKA share considerably less information about their training activities. This may either be due to lack of information or lack of projects. Since the scope of the COSMIC project involves utilization of secondary data to analyse the activities of major public and private organizations, further studies may be needed to collect primary data in addressing this question.

Nevertheless, available data provides some examples to the types of activities that UMKE and AKA are involved in. For example, UMKE collaborates with AFAD to provide seminars and earthquakes exercises in several cities. There are also examples of seminars given to hospital personnel about what they should or should not do during earthquakes. Since UMKE is a medical emergency response organization, it mostly aims to supply citizens with relevant medical information about emergency response.

⁵⁷ “Eğitim Hizmetleri,” *Türk Kızılayı*. 2013.

http://www.kizilay.org.tr/egitimhizmetleri/konu4a.php?subaction=showfull&id=1189163918&archive=&start_from=&ucat=36&

⁵⁸ “VCA,” *Türk Kızılayı*. 2013.

http://www.kizilay.org.tr/egitimhizmetleri/konu4a.php?subaction=showfull&id=1189155408&archive=&start_from=&ucat=36.&

⁵⁹ “ABCD Temel Afet Bilinci Eğitimi,” *Türk Kızılayı*. 2013.

http://www.kizilay.org.tr/egitimhizmetleri/konu3a.php?subaction=showfull&id=1189440381&archive=&start_from=&ucat=35&

⁶⁰ “Toplum Liderlerini Teşkilatlandırma Projesi Afet Zararlarını Azaltma Programı,” *Türk Kızılayı*. 2013.

<http://www.toplumlideri.org.tr/index.php>

UMKE is also involved in getting feedback and information from stakeholders via polls they conduct on their website. Each poll contains only one question. The first poll asks the visitors to provide feedback about how UMKE can be improved as an organization (e.g., increase presence in media, lack of sufficient provisions for training camps). The second poll elicits feedback from public regarding UMKE's performance in emergency response and recovery in the aftermath of the Van Earthquake. Interestingly, the third poll asks the respondents about whether they believe they live in a building that would withstand an earthquake with a minimum magnitude of 6.5.⁶¹

Likewise, the limited information available from AKA website points to a training workshop entitled "Society's Disaster Awareness Workshop". In this three-hour workshop, AKA gives information about how people should prepare for an earthquake. The training includes first response education and development of a household plan for the crisis. AKA also provides basic search and rescue training (HAKE). According to AKA, for each neighbourhood, the training would help the formation of a neighbourhood emergency response team and subsequently this team would create a database that can be used in case of emergencies and disasters.⁶² The nature and purpose of this so-called database is not clarified on the website. In additional trainings, AKA aims to raise awareness of threats posed by disasters and inform citizens about research and rescue.

Based on the discussions provided in this section, the next section will summarize the types of training materials that are available/utilized by these organizations.

2.3.3 Training materials

Particularly in instances when workshops are not accessible to large groups of people and when workshops/trainings are organized in a limited number of cities, availability of training materials for interested citizens becomes a necessary but not a sufficient condition for citizen involvement in disaster preparation.

AFAD has twelve different brochures and handbooks that can be found on their website. These publications provide information about:

- Information about natural disasters
- The importance of raising awareness against natural disaster
- How to be prepared for the first 72 hours after an earthquake
- Psychological help for earthquake victims
- Structural risks against earthquakes
- Non-structural mitigation earthquakes

In addition to these brochures and handbooks, AFAD, under its ISMEP project also offers an online training portal for children. On the website of the ISMEP project a section devoted to children entitled "Safe Life for Children" (<http://cocuk.guvenliyasam.org/>) offers a wide range of materials including cartoons, animations, games, and quizzes. More information about the contents of these materials will be provided in the media usage section.

Like AFAD, AKUT also has nine different books and handbooks to inform people although we can only reach seven of them online. All of these publications inform citizens about what

⁶¹ "Anketler", *UMKE*. 2013. <http://www.umke.org/anketler.html>

⁶² "Eğitimler", *AKA*. 2013. <http://www.aka.org.tr/forum.asp>

to do at the time of earthquakes, how they should prepare their families and their homes. These books also focus on:

- The importance of being informed against natural disasters
- Training children against natural disasters
- Basic earthquake training
- Natural disasters and victims' psychology

AADYM, as mentioned above, has explanations about how to deal with the natural disasters. Different from others, AADYM also provides detailed information about preparedness for floods, droughts, avalanches, fires, terrorism as well as earthquakes. It explains what these disasters are and what to do before and after them.⁶³

In the case of the Turkish Red Crescent, training materials include brochures, previews of a few journal articles, information about the projects, activity reports and five online books that give information about protection against earthquakes both psychically and psychologically and first response treatment.⁶⁴ The brochures included on the website are mostly about the projects and do not provide detailed information for training citizens. In addition, there are some documents about the training of the personnel of the Turkish Red Crescent. These training documents provide information on topics such as setting up emergency tents and use of portable kitchens. Finally, Red Crescent releases periodicals that explain how citizens should prepare themselves against natural disasters once in four months. These periodicals provide information about the types of equipment and provisions that each household should have. They also explain how a volunteer in a rescue team should be prepared and the types of provisions that should be prepared before going to an earthquake region.⁶⁵

UMKE offers a large achieve of presentations and handbooks on its website.⁶⁶ Unfortunately, and unsurprisingly given the mission of UMKE, most of these documents were prepared for the medical professionals and is difficult for citizen to understand.

Similar to UMKE, AKA has only information about the training programs on its website. Unfortunately, full access to most of these materials, which include videos and other materials, requires membership. This decision seems particularly peculiar given that the mission of AKA clearly states that their goal includes raising the awareness level of “all members of the society.”⁶⁷

2.3.4 Recruitment and networking of new members

Recruitment process is different for each of the organization that this report focuses on. However, each organization requires a number of documents from potential volunteers and participants.

Since AFAD is a division of the government, its members consist of government personnel. This is also the case for AADYM, another government organization. However, there are a

⁶³ “Doğal Afetler”, AADYM. 2013. http://www.icisleriafad.gov.tr/default_B0.aspx?content=209

⁶⁴ <http://www.kizilay.org.tr/kurumsal/sayfa.php?t=7>

⁶⁵ “Türk Kızılayı Dergisi, “ Türk Kızılayı,8:47. 2012. <http://www.kizilay.org.tr/kurumsal/dergi/s14-Yaz-Guz-2012/index.html>

⁶⁶ “Eğitim Belgeleri,” UMKE. 2013. <http://www.umke.org/umke-sunumlari-egitim-s10.html>

⁶⁷ “Vizyon ve Misyon,” AKA. 2013. <http://www.aka.org.tr/dernek.asp>

few projects that involve recruitment of citizen volunteers. For example, the “First 72 Hours” project involves the formation of a group of “young” volunteers for earthquake. These volunteers seem to be involved in the preparation of other citizens against natural disasters. However, there is not an explanation about how these volunteers will be organized in these activities. Unfortunately, the partners also could not locate sufficient information about how this group of volunteers would be formed. Also, the ISMEP project of AFAD also recruits volunteers. In this project, when the citizens get the required one hour training they can be a volunteer of the Secure Life Volunteers. After taking a one-hour training about earthquakes, citizen can be volunteers and can participate in the future trainings as an instructor.⁶⁸

In the case of AKUT, for people living in Istanbul, to become a volunteer, citizens have to prepare documents such as photos, residential records, criminal records and blood type documents. After preparing these documents, citizens have to attend to the volunteer meetings held at different times. After completing this process, AKUT personnel evaluate the documents and decide whether a citizen should be a part of AKUT or not. After this, the personnel determine the departments of the new volunteers according to their skills.⁶⁹ Candidates from outside Istanbul can also contact personnel in their regions. For the volunteers, there are several exercises and seminars throughout the year. In addition to open recruitment meetings, AKUT also engages in active recruitment of high school and university students by providing seminars and trainings at campuses. AKUT also uses its own website as well as its own Facebook page in order to reach potential recruits and announce training/recruitment activities.

AKA's recruitment process here is not as clear as the other two volunteer groups summarized above. However, it is clear that to attend operations, volunteers need to complete three different training programs.⁷⁰ AKA's members and their activities can also be tracked via its open group on Facebook. In the group, the members keep contact with each other and give information about their experiences.

To be a part of UMKE, the candidates must be medical personnel. The candidates with medical background have to fill the application form and give it to their local health authorities. After this, the candidates attend to UMKE Basic Training Program. After this program, if the candidates are successful, they become UMKE volunteer and attend to UMKE operations.⁷¹ UMKE also makes several training camps and exercises for its member in every part of Turkey. How UMKE reaches potential recruits is unclear. Medical personnel interested in UMKE may learn about recruitment of volunteers only through UMKE's website.

Finally, The Turkish Red Crescent's application process for volunteers seems much easier than the others. Citizens can become volunteers simply by filling a detailed application form available online.⁷²

⁶⁸ “Güvenli Yaşam Facebook Sayfası”, *Güvenli Yaşam Gönüllüleri*. 2013.

<https://www.facebook.com/guvenliyasam.org/info>

⁶⁹ “Üyelik,” *AKUT*. 2013. <http://www.akut.org.tr/uyelik>

⁷⁰ “Eğitimler,” *AKA*. 2013. <http://www.aka.org.tr/forum.asp>

⁷¹ “Üyelik,” *UMKE*. 2013. <http://www.umke.org/umke-kayitbasvuru-formuyonerge-s24.html>

⁷² For more information about the application form see: http://www.kizilay.org.tr/kurumsal/gonullu_basvuru.php

2.3.5 Media coverage and use of media for citizen outreach programs

Newspapers, television channels, websites and social media are used frequently by the organizations that this report focuses on. The number of articles in national newspapers mentioning these organizations is not particularly high. For example AKUT has been mentioned in 61 different printed newspaper articles in the last year, while AFAD has been mentioned in 21 newspaper articles. However, evidence indicates that these organizations utilize a number of media outlets, including social media sites and advertisements on mass/outdoor media to reach the public.

2.3.5.1 News coverage

Most of the news about the organization our report focuses on concerns information regarding projects, seminars and workshops, training of personnel, training of citizens and recruitment of personnel and volunteers. Especially news about AKUT tends to cover all of these different topics. For example, articles often report updates about the lectures given by AKUT to students about how to protect themselves against emergencies.⁷³ Also, news reports cover volunteers who contribute to rescue staff in the aftermath of disasters.⁷⁴ These kinds of news reports can potentially not only inform citizens about how they can be involved in activities organized by AKUT but also gives visibility to AKUT's efforts.

Like AKUT, AFAD also benefits from news coverage of their activities. Articles about AFAD give information about AFAD's projects, plans and activities. These articles also provide coverage of training programs and workshops AFAD organized in cooperation with other organizations such as the Turkish Red Crescent and AKUT, to reach out to opinion leaders (again, religious leaders and teachers were emphasized) so that they can, in turn, educate the citizens.⁷⁵

News articles about the Turkish Red Crescent's activities were dominantly about blood donation. However, there were also a number of articles about disaster preparedness and citizen participation in training programs. For example, one article reported the cooperation between the Turkish Red Crescent and AKUT, which resulted in a training program that helped educate almost three thousand children for earthquake preparedness.⁷⁶

Unlike these three organizations, coverage of AKA is limited to local magazines and newspapers, with news stories about its training program and its collaboration with AFAD. News about AKA are not as detailed as news about the other organizations discussed hereinabove.

2.3.5.2 Use of media and communication technologies

In addition to the articles published in mass media, outreach efforts involve a considerably wide array of communication media, including mass media as well as social and mobile media.

As one of the leading emergency response volunteer groups in Turkey, AKUT both uses an active Youtube channel (with 43 videos) and engages in production of a TV program in CNN

⁷³ "AKUT'tan Deprem Eğitimi," *Hürriyet*. 01.07.2012

⁷⁴ "Bisiklete afet görevi " *Hürriyet*. 28.07.2013

⁷⁵ "Toplum Liderlerine Afet Eğitimi," *Milliyet Akdeniz*. 25.09.2012

⁷⁶ "3000 Öğrenciye Deprem Eğitimi," *Posta*. 28.09.2013.

[http://beta.interpress.com/\(S\(o2d4sutoryd0njydxscywvm2\)\)/BasinAyrintiGoster.aspx?IDS=ipf%2B%2BWcttPG6tY2bCZKFA%3D%3D&lm=0&medi=4367&kayitsayisi=1#.UjftKManfE8](http://beta.interpress.com/(S(o2d4sutoryd0njydxscywvm2))/BasinAyrintiGoster.aspx?IDS=ipf%2B%2BWcttPG6tY2bCZKFA%3D%3D&lm=0&medi=4367&kayitsayisi=1#.UjftKManfE8)

Türk (the Turkish affiliate of CNN) to raise citizen awareness about emergency preparedness and about their own projects. In each episode of the TV program, different kinds of pertinent information are given to the viewers. For example, in one episode, viewers can watch a research and rescue mission of AKUT while in another program, they can learn information about how to protect themselves against earthquakes, floods or fires. YouTube channel also includes the videos of AKUT projects such as Continue to Life Turkey. In addition to its YouTube channel and its TV program, AKUT also shares videos on its own website.

AKUT is also highly active in social media. On its Facebook page, AKUT gives detailed information about its operations, trainings and project activities. It has also two different Twitter accounts. One of them is in Turkish and the other one is in English. AKUT's Twitter accounts provide up to date information about AKUT volunteers' training and rescue operations that AKUT volunteers participated in.

Like AKUT, AFAD uses videos to inform people about their activities and training programs. AFAD website has a detailed video archive,⁷⁷ which showcases AFAD's human resource and technological capabilities. AFAD also uses its YouTube channel to share videos of their activities with the citizens although it's not as active as that of AKUT. Maybe one of its important videos is the presentation of AFAD's new mobile disaster information application.

As discussed above, AFAD is also involved in a separate project called Secure Life Training Program. On the website of this program, detailed information about the project, information about the training programs provided. Other publications of AFAD, which provide information about precautions that can help being safe during the time of a natural disaster, can be found on its website. The website also has a subsection dedicated to the training of the children. In this section, there are education videos, plays, cartoons and quizzes for children.⁷⁸ All of these contents aim to educate children against the natural disasters and to raise the volunteers of the future from small ages.

AFAD also has a Facebook page and a Twitter account. Currently, the Facebook page is not active. In fact, some of the members have already posted comments complaining about the lack of activity on the page. As of this report, the AFAD Twitter page mostly gives information about the activities of AFAD for refugees fleeing from Syria. Consequently, it can be argued AFAD's social media presence does not provide sufficient attention to disaster preparation.

At the same time, it should also be indicated that AFAD engages in new and potentially useful utilization of online and mobile environments for reaching out to citizens. One such outlet seems to be the AFAD mobile application that provides detailed up to date information about earthquakes happening in Turkey (Figure 2.4). Likewise, in 2013, AFAD also initiated a project that will use smartphones and tablets to collect data from citizens immediately after an earthquake. This data collection project aims to learn about the "magnitude" of earthquakes as "felt" by citizens. The survey will also allow citizens to upload photos illustrating the impact of earthquakes. Combined with data about the Richter scale of each earthquake, the survey and the photos will be used to increase the accuracy and sensitiveness of the mapping of earthquakes.⁷⁹

⁷⁷ "TV Arşivi," AFAD. 2013. <https://www.afad.gov.tr/TR/IcerikDetayl.aspx?ID=9&IcerikID=24>

⁷⁸ "Güvenli Yaşam Çocuk." İSMEP, 2013. <http://cocuk.guvenliyasam.org/tehlike-avi>

⁷⁹ "Deprem'in İnsanlar Üzerindeki Hissedilme Şiddeti Anketle Belirlenecek" 20.09.2013. <http://www.haberler.com/depremin-insanlar-uzerindeki-hissedilme-siddeti-4684781-haberi/>

Figure 2.4: Introduction Video for AFAD's new mobile disaster application. The video gives information about how to use this application"

Among the organizations that were studied, Red Crescent maybe the most active organization in the social media. Currently, they have an Instagram account, a Pinterest account as well as a Twitter and a Facebook account. On Instagram and Pinterest, Red Crescent shows several photo albums of their activities such as education albums, volunteer albums and natural disaster albums. On Twitter and on Facebook, Red Crescent mostly shares information about their daily activities. If the citizens follow these pages, they can have information about the activities; however, most of this information is related to blood donation or natural disasters in other places instead of giving specific information about the disaster preparation.

The Red Crescent also shares its video archive on its Website and its own YouTube channel (Figure 2.5). This archive mostly contains infomercials regarding its emergency preparedness and response activities in other countries. However, there are only a few videos in which Red Crescent actually discusses the emergency preparedness.

Figure 2.5: A scene from Red Crescent's video about earthquakes. The video asks "Are you ready for an earthquake that may happen tomorrow?"

UMKE has its own news database as well as its own video gallery.⁸⁰ UMKE's video collection contains a combination of information videos, training videos and videos targeting medical personnel in Turkey. Also, UMKE also shares its video collection via its social media platforms such as Google+ and Facebook. In addition, UMKE uses its Facebook and Twitter pages to regularly update citizens about their operations, but most of the content is related to the medical personnel arrangements in the country.

AKA's Facebook page is used for the coordination of the members and to inform AKA members about the regulations and operations. Hence, it is safe to conclude that Facebook presence of AKA is tailored towards reaching out to existing members rather than the public. Likewise, AKA's video collection is not as large as the other organizations analysed in this report. Indeed, AKA's video collection only includes two videos about what to do during fires and earthquakes.⁸¹

It should also be mentioned that outdoor and person-to-person communications are also used by these organizations, with AKUT and AFAD providing some recent examples to how these communication tools can be utilized.

For example, outdoor advertisement shown in Figure 2.6 was prepared for the memory of the Marmara earthquakes that happened in 1999 . Posted on billboards, these advertisements not only commemorated the earthquakes but also aimed to raise awareness by asking citizens to “prepare as if the next earthquake will happen tomorrow.”

Figure 2.6: AKUT's poster in memory of 1999 earthquakes. It asks “What if we told you there would be an earthquake tomorrow, what would you do?”

⁸⁰ “Video Galeri,” *UMKE*. 2013. <http://www.umke.org/video-galeri.html>

⁸¹ “Google + Hesabı,” *UMKE*. 2013. <https://plus.google.com/u/0/115215954790499803993/posts>

Figure 2.7 displays the aforementioned Earthquake simulator that was part of AKUT's "Continue to life Turkey" tour. As part of this tour, AKUT staff and the simulator went to different provinces in Turkey, providing training about natural disasters.

Figure 2.7: Earthquake simulators as well as interpersonal communication were a part of AKUT's outdoor projects

Likewise, AFAD also used billboards (Figure 2.8) and information booths (Figure 2.9) to reach out to citizens and get them enrolled in short training programs.

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Figure 2.8: The poster of Secure Life saying "One Hour against Earthquakes means One Life."

Figure 2.9: Information booths and interpersonal communication were also part of the media mix for the Secure Life project.

2.4 INVOLVEMENT OF CITIZENS AS VOLUNTEERS: REPORT ON ITALY

2.4.1 Introduction

As shown in Figure 2.1 at the beginning of this chapter, with more than 50 incidents between 2003 and 2013, Italy ranks the first among European Union member states in terms of number of disasters. The most frequently occurring types of disaster in Italy are floods, followed by earthquakes and storms (Figure 2.10).

2.10: Disaster Occurrence in Italy (1980-2010)⁸²

In Italy, the overall responsibility for the management of disasters and crises arising from natural events,⁸³ as well as the activities aimed at creating a culture of risk prevention at the national level, are coordinated by the Civil Protection Department (CPD) (*Dipartimento della Protezione Civile*).

The CPD heads what is referred to as the National Civil Protection Service (NCPS). The NCPS is a system that includes local and national stakeholders that intervene at different levels in case of calamities and disasters. In this context, civil society and volunteers/citizens are an important part of this system. The Italian portal on civil protection ISPRO reports that the number of citizens/volunteers keep steadily increasing and include 2,500 voluntary organizations, with approximately 1,300,000 volunteers, 60,000 of whom can be deployed

⁸² Prevention Web, "Disaster Statistics - Italy - Europe - Countries & Regions - PreventionWeb.net", 2013 <http://www.preventionweb.net/english/countries/statistics/?cid=85>

⁸³ In the context of the COSMIC project crises arising from natural events are considered flood, extreme temperature, storm, wildfire, earthquake, with others categorised as man-made (see D1.1: Report on security crises with high societal impact).

within a few minutes, and 300,000 in a few hours.⁸⁴

The tasks assigned to citizen/volunteer corps in case of emergencies and disasters include “providing information about the event and the number of volunteers and resources that are active in the affected areas as well as to plan for potential deployment of additional resources.” They can also be “called upon to participate, upon request by the competent authorities, in rescue operations of the population and all the necessary activities to reinstate ordinary living conditions.”⁸⁵

The NCPS, according to the Italian legislation (law n. 225/February 24, 1992) (Figure 2.11) comprises “components” and “operating arms”. The “components” that are called into action in case of an emergency are:

- National Government and State administrations
- Provincial Councils
- Municipalities
- Mountain Communities
- Institutes of Scientific Research with civil protection purposes
- Voluntary associations, professional associations and citizens who have competence in civil protection matters.⁸⁶

The “operating arms” of the NCPS include bodies such as:

- National Scientific Institutions as the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology (INGV), the National Research Council (CNR) and the Council for New Technologies, Energy and the Environment (ENEA)
- The National Council of Volunteers
- The National Fire Department
- the Armed Forces
- the Corps of Forest Rangers
- the Police Forces (Police, Carabinieri, Finance Police, Coast Guard, Prison Police, Local Police)
- the Italian Red Cross
- the National Health Service.

⁸⁴ ISPRO, *Cosa è il Volontariato di Protezione Civile*, 2013, <http://ispro.it/site/content/cosa-%C3%A8-il-volontariato-di-protezione-civile> [accessed 18 September 2013]

⁸⁵ Civil Protection Department, “The role of the voluntary organisations in the National Service”, 2013, http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/jcms/en/il_ruolo_del_volontariato.wp

⁸⁶ Civil Protection Department, “Components”, 2013, <http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/jcms/en/componenti.wp>

Figure 2.11: Civil Protection Structure Coordination⁸⁷

The hierarchical structure of Italian disaster management organization is shown in Figure 2.12.

As summarized in Figure 2.12, according to the Italian law and operative procedures, the protocol expects the Mayor of the municipality where a disaster has occurred to make sure that in the initial moments of a crisis, local relief teams and civil protection volunteers provide the necessary assistance to the population and coordinates the local forces.

If local efforts are not enough to cope with the scale of the crisis, then provincial, regional and, eventually, national authorities are asked to take over and coordinate the intervention. In the case of a disaster at the greatest scale, the Prime Minister will assume direct responsibility and coordinate CPD's activities.⁸⁸ In other words, the "components" are the decisional bodies, whereas the "operative structures" are the ones that will operate directly on the field in case of an emergency.

⁸⁷ Rapisardi, Elena "Building Civil Protection 2.0", 2010, <http://www.slideshare.net/elenis/building-civil-protection-20-updated>

⁸⁸ Civil Protection Department, "Components", 2013, <http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/jcms/en/componenti.wp>

Figure 2.12: Operational Organization of the Italian Disaster Management Structure

Figure 2.13 summarizes in more detail the departments that the CPD (and eventually the Prime Minister) coordinate in case of a major national emergency event.

Figure 2.13: Civil Protection Structure Coordination⁸⁹

2.4.2 Citizen training and participation in emergency preparedness

While citizens can be part of an emergency and disaster volunteer body registered in the NCPS, most of the volunteers will not have the opportunity to undergo detailed emergency training. However, it is imperative that citizen volunteers have awareness, and where possible, a basic training regarding what actions to take while waiting for professionally trained emergency services and/or to support them during emergency response.

With the advent of digital and social media technologies, as it will be explored further later in this report (see the case of heavy snowfall in Bologna), citizens can also be part of a network that actually helps local authorities to better direct emergency services based on geo-located information.

The general coordination of citizen training and participation in emergency preparedness ultimately relies on the CPD, which, as mentioned in the introduction section, is the overall coordination body of the NCPS.

The awareness and training projects coordinated by the CPD have been focusing primarily, but not solely, on earthquake risk reduction campaigns, which affect a large part of the country. According to the CPD “Italy is one of the countries in the Mediterranean with the highest seismic risk, due to its particular geographic position at the convergence of the African and Eurasian plates,”⁹⁰ The highest risks are concentrated in the central-southern part

⁸⁹ Rapisardi, Elena “Building Civil Protection 2.0”, 2010, <http://www.slideshare.net/elenis/building-civil-protection-20-updated>

⁹⁰ Civil Protection Department, “Seismic Risk”, 2013, http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/jcms/en/rischio_sismico.wp

of the peninsula and in some northern areas, as the regions of Friuli, Veneto and Liguria.

Projects such as the “Earthquake – I Don’t Risk” campaign (held since 2011) focus on seismic risk reduction and are promoted by the CPD and one of the largest voluntary rescue organizations (ANPAS), in collaboration with the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology and the Network of University Laboratories of Seismic Engineering. The campaign aims, among others, to help start “a process that will put citizens at the centre of seismic risk reduction procedures” and “to prevent and reduce the impact of earthquakes”.⁹¹

The campaign (Figure 2.14) has also a website: www.iononrischio.it, is disseminated (both in Italian and English) via Twitter, Facebook, Youtube and Instagram. Previous editions are also archived in the ‘Campaigns’ within the CPD’s Communications section pages.

Figure 2.14: The Banner of the 2013 “Earthquake. I Don’t Risk” Event.

Projects organized by the CPD also aim to target the younger population through campaigns like “I also am the Civil Protection,” a School Camp that provides information and awareness on fire prevention and aims to “stimulate a full and conscious civil protection culture among young people,” organized in collaboration with national and regional voluntary work organizations, and the 17 Italian Regions (Figure 2.15).⁹²

Figure 2.15: The cover of the 2011 Civil Protection School Camp brochures

⁹¹ Civil Protection Department, “Tivr 2012”, 2012, http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/jcms/en/terremoto_io_non_rischio.wp

⁹²Civil Protection Department, “I am the Civil Protection too. School Camps 2011. Woodfire Prevention”, 2011, http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/jcms/en/view_pub.wp?facetNode_1=f4_6_1&prevPage=pubblicazioni&contentId=PUB26038

ANPAS, one of the largest national voluntary networks in Italy part of the NCPS, which counts 350 offices, 300 emergency response vehicles and 11.000 'active' volunteers (those who are specifically trained for emergencies)⁹³ reports that in the last School Camps held in 2013 across the country, 630 students between 9 and 18 years of age have participated to the 24 camps during the summer months. ANPAS highlights how these camps can stimulate a sense of responsibility, active citizenship and sharing best practices of civil protection, and show participants the role that each individual member can be play in the wider context of the NCPS.⁹⁴

The CPD also coordinates regional simulations of disaster and emergency response. For example, a recent disaster simulation exercise was done in the North-East area of Italy in 2013. This simulation was put in place to test the functionality of the information flow among the various levels of the chain of command, and how each of them gets activated. It included the simulated intervention of emergency vehicles in area hypothetically struck by a 7th grade Richter earthquake, all the logistic operations connected to such an event, the evacuation of schools and public buildings, as well as communication and information to the local population.

The main reference tasks that were tested included:

- The activation of the coordination from the local to the National Civil Protection System (NCPS)
- Verify the telecommunications systems in a situation of emergency
- Verify the access to the areas that were 'hit' by the seismic event
- The activation of the emergency services, with particular attention to disaster relief and ambulance/life support services
- The levels of operability of the voluntary associations present in the area.⁹⁵

All of the projects described above, and coordinated by the CPD, are part of its "outreach activities to increase the public awareness about natural hazards and to encourage them to improve their own resilience."⁹⁶ The 'Dossiers' (basically an in-depth news item) section of the CPD website contains a list of the larger simulation exercises, including the objective, the scenario, the training activities and including a list of all the participants and partner organizations.⁹⁷

At the local level, municipalities prepare communication materials to address the particular risks of that territory for potential earthquakes, landslides or volcano eruptions and include tips on prevention and self-protection. For example, the Emilia-Romagna region, an area at high seismic risk, has produced a booklet (Figure 2.16) that has specific information targeted to the citizens living in this area of Italy with maps that highlight the risks in each of the

⁹³ ANPAS, "L'ANPAS e la Protezione Civile", 2013, <http://www.anpasnazionale.org/attivita/protezione-civile.html>

⁹⁴ ANPAS, "Anch'io sono la Protezione Civile", 2013, <http://www.anpasnazionale.org/categoria-news-pc/1142-campi-scuola-2013.html>

⁹⁵ Civil Protection Department, "Esercitazione Nord-Est 2013. Gli Obiettivi", 2013,

http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/jcms/en/view_dossier.wp?prevPage=dossier&contentId=DOS40876

⁹⁶ OECD, *OECD Reviews of Risk Management Policies: Italy 2010. Review of the Italian National Civil Protection System*, 2010, p.84 http://www.keepeek.com/Digital-Asset-Management/oecd/governance/oecd-reviews-of-risk-management-policies-italy-2010_9789264082205-en

⁹⁷ Civil Protection Department, "Esercitazione Nord-Est 2013. L'Esercitazione", 2013,

http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/jcms/en/view_dossier.wp?prevPage=dossier&contentId=DOS40874

provinces, and highlight what to do to prevent casualties, as activities to put in place once the seismic event has struck the area.

Figure 2.16: The cover of “What to do in case of earthquake”, published by the Region Emilia-Romagna

However, a recent review of the risk management policies in Italy published by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has noted how there is resistance in some parts of Italy to make “risk maps available to the public, which stems from the position that the public should not be made unnecessarily afraid or induced to panic. Instead, focus is placed on providing directions on what measures to take during an emergency.”⁹⁸ The OECD did eventually recommend the Italian authorities to provide such information to the public.

Indeed, elsewhere COSMIC (D.1.1, ‘Report on security crises with high societal impact’) had analysed societal dynamics in the context of crises and has also remarked how “Individual dynamics during crisis situations are dependent on (citizen) preparation, (early) warning, and interventions (or lack thereof) during the response and recovery phases of a crisis”.⁹⁹ Moreover, it had also underlined how ‘sudden’ crises that can occur without warning as earthquakes are difficult to prepare for and therefore ‘The degree to which individuals are able to cope with these unexpected crises depends largely on the skills and knowledge they have developed, as well as the resources they have possessed over their life time.’¹⁰⁰

Is then important that citizens who are living in areas at risk, especially if they are not specifically trained for disaster relief intervention, and are not part of any voluntary corps involved in such activities, are made aware of the possible activities that they can do as first responders to support their own families’ immediate needs, as well as become a proactive helper for other or act, within their limits, to perform the activities that can be useful to (or even support) the disaster relief teams.

⁹⁸ OECD, *OECD Reviews of Risk Management Policies: Italy 2010. Review of the Italian National Civil Protection System*, 2010, p.85 http://www.keepeek.com/Digital-Asset-Management/oecd/governance/oecd-reviews-of-risk-management-policies-italy-2010_9789264082205-en

⁹⁹ Watson, Hayley et al., “Deliverable D1.1: Report on security crises with high societal impact”, *COSMIC*, 2013., p.78

¹⁰⁰ Op.cit., Groenendaal et al., 2013, p.78

2.4.3 Training materials

Apart from the projects that aim to reach people in the areas particularly at risk for natural disasters, the CPD and the organizations part of its system publish materials that target also the general public and made available through their websites.

The CPD has organized Publications area within the Communications area of its website: these publications include brochures that inform on risks in different areas of Italy, educational material for families and schools that aim spread a culture of risk prevention among the general population, as well as training material for civil protection operators.

The brochures include topics such as ‘Civil protection for families’ (Figure 2.17), which outlines the risks present in Italy, makes citizens aware of those risks, and suggest its readers what approach to take in case of small and larger emergencies. The book is available for download as a PDF file free of charge, both in English and Italian.¹⁰¹

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Figure 2.17: The table of contents of the ‘Civil Protection in the family’.

As for the training that is necessary for volunteers to be part of the NCPS, where the CDP does not provide information about training at the national level, regional or local authorities have developed protocols, guidelines and training modules that address different levels of activity, from basic to complex disaster relief operations, as well as general or more specific functions in a team.

The Emilia-Romagna Regional Authority, for example, has the following modules included in its “Basics of Civil Protection” course, aimed at the volunteers that want to work in its regional system of associations:

¹⁰¹ Civil Protection Department, “The Civil Protection for Families”, 2005, http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/jcms/en/view_pub.wp?facetNode_1=f4_6_1&prevPage=pubblicazioni&contentId=PUB13445

1. The pathway of the Civil Protection Volunteer
2. First Aid basics
3. Radio communications
4. Introduction to Cartography
5. The Regional Civil Protection System and the role of volunteers
6. Volunteering and Civil Protection Legislation
7. Final practice module: a general emergency call¹⁰²

Further training courses include modules aimed at Team Leaders, groups that are specifically dealing with forest fires, the use of cranes in emergencies, the positioning of containing barriers, tools for hydraulic emergencies and driving off-road vehicles.¹⁰³

Other regional, provincial and local governmental authorities of Italy do organize courses based on the specific needs of their territories, and related risks, and compatibly with the budgets that have been destined to the training of volunteers for civil protection purposes in their areas.

For example, the Lombardy Regional Authority has established the High School of Civil Protection (Figure 2.18) in the context of its Training Division, Eupolis Lombardia, which aims to train public officers, utility workers (water, gas, electricity, telecommunications, etc.), corporate employees, professionals, teachers, students, volunteers and citizens in civil protection principles and practices.¹⁰⁴

Figure 2.18: Logo and website header of the High School of Civil Protection

Courses can vary from basic risk prevention training for beginners, to more advanced ones aimed at volunteers that live close to landslide, flooding, forest fire and seismic risk areas.¹⁰⁵

2.4.4 Recruitment and networking of new members

With reference to the recruitment of volunteers among the citizen population of Italy, the 2010 OECD Italy report had pointed out how

Volunteer organisations play a significant role in the civil protection system, providing a dedicated and well-organised corps of human resources that can intervene to support professional civil protection services in times of emergency. More than 100,000 volunteers across the country stand ready to supplement the Italian Red Cross staff of 4,000 official employees, whose salaries are paid by the Government.

¹⁰² Regione Emilia- Romagna, “DD 4811/2008. Linee guida per le amministrazioni provinciali per la realizzazione di corsi di protezione civile rivolti ai volontari che operano nel sistema regionale di protezione civile”, 2008, http://www.protezionecivile.emilia-romagna.it/aree-tematiche/formazione/livello-2/DD4811_2008.pdf

¹⁰³ Regione Emilia- Romagna, “Formazione del Volontariato e degli Operatori Pubblici”, 2013, <http://www.protezionecivile.emilia-romagna.it/aree-tematiche/formazione/livello-2>

¹⁰⁴ EUPOLIS-Scuola Superiore di Protezione Civile, “I Destinatari”, 2013, http://www.irefonline.it/websites/iref/staging/home_sspc.nsf/wAll/IDCW-77FDKE?opendocument

¹⁰⁵ EUPOLIS-Scuola Superiore di Protezione Civile, “Attività Anno 2012”, 2013, http://www.irefonline.it/websites/iref/staging/home_sspc.nsf/wAll/IDCW-8TB87Z?opendocument

The OECD review assessed that there seem to be 'enough' volunteers in the North of Italy, whereas in the Southern regions "there is a relative dearth of volunteers, and there too few professionals due to insufficient resources to pay them", this being "clearly a weak point in the preparedness and real time response to disasters that should be urgently addressed." Moreover, another issue "to consider in this context is why emergency response resources of this type are not part of the municipal structure as in other countries" .

What emerges is then how preparedness and real time responses, both by authorities and voluntary groups can vary greatly depending on the level of financial resources and number of volunteers in that particular area. Indeed, the OECD review highlighted how a "very large number of motivated volunteers provide the necessary resources needed for large scale civil protection operations and help to create local involvement in many, but not all, parts of Italy."

In fact, in the areas where the number of volunteers is large and the network of volunteer associations is more dense and solid, and where fiscal resources, environmental conditions and institutional peculiarities help to facilitate a well organised and strong capacity of response , the levels of community involvement are higher as the volunteers are able to input their responses via their own association that is part of the NCPS.

The recruitment of volunteers, at least in some parts of Italy, then, does not present a particular problem since the establishment of the Civil Protection volunteers as a result of the large spontaneous response that followed major disasters as the flooding of Florence in 1966, the earthquake in Friuli in 1976, and another earthquake in Irpinia in 1980. In these cases, what lacked was an organized public system to help out organizing such resources in the best way. The establishment of the NCPS in 1992 has made the voluntary organisations part of a national system that coordinates interventions during crises since then.

In order to become a volunteer in the Civil Protection system a citizen has to become a member of a local civil protection voluntary organization included in an official register at the national or local level. This is important as this a pre-condition to be involved in any 'official' disaster relief, rescue or support mission at any level in Italy. Governmental authorities want to be sure, in other words, that anyone involved in such activities is someone who has received training from the voluntary organisation approved and registered by the CPD.

Where the CPD provides general information on the importance of volunteers in the civil protection system, this structure delegates most of the recruitment drive for volunteers to the voluntary associations present at the local level or to campaigns promoted by Regions, Provinces and Municipalities.

2.4.5 Media coverage and use of media for citizen outreach programs

The media coverage on national and regional branches of the CPD activities tends to be usually higher during natural disasters that affect the country. Our analysis indicates that CPD does not consistently track media coverage of its own activities or document it on its own website, a function that is instead performed by an independent online publication. At the regional level, some civil protection branches provide extensive and up to date archives, as in the case of Friuli-Venezia Giulia, whereas others do not provide any documentation at all.

The use of social media by the CPD is also object of discussion among practitioners, who are very critical of the fact that it does not effectively utilize social media and crowdsourcing

tools, which have been very effective elsewhere (e.g., Haiti Earthquake, Hurricane Sandy in U.S.), with the consequence that citizens are not in the best possible position to be proactive actors in emergency situations. However, dissemination of awareness materials and training initiatives, although mostly in a web 1.0 fashion, is done regularly across the country.

2.4.5.1 News coverage

An analysis of the media coverage of the CPD at the national, regional and local conducted by retrieving archives from the newspapers with the largest circulation in Italy, underlines some interesting findings about the predominant topics that receive media attention. For example, analysing the tags related to the news covering the CPD, we observe that the topic most covered in *La Repubblica* between 2004-2014 is by far the 2009 L'Aquila earthquake and the two people who were managing respectively the CPD (Guido Bertolaso) and the Italian Government (Silvio Berlusconi).¹⁰⁶ Bertolaso and Berlusconi also top the list in the *Corriere della Sera*, *La Stampa* and the financial broadsheet *Il Sole 24 Ore*. This is no surprise given also the allegation of corruption at several levels that have surrounded the aftermath of the event and the reconstruction efforts, covered also by international media¹⁰⁷, and that this matter has been widely discussed across Italy's media and discussed in Italian literature,¹⁰⁸ arguably overshadowing its more 'natural' function of emergency response and relief in times of disaster and its role as a promoter of awareness on the risk of natural disasters in the country.

We also have observed that, given the recurrence of natural disasters, the news coverage of national and local CPD activities tends usually to privilege the reporting of disaster events and its consequences as repercussions on the environment, the lack of funds for reconstruction in areas affected by disasters, political and organizational responsibilities,¹⁰⁹ casualties, and the consequences on local transport infrastructures.¹¹⁰ In this context, news about training and awareness activities tend to appear rarely at the national level, with more space given at the regional or local levels,¹¹¹ as in the case of ANPAS Piedmont where the press review shows the richness of training and awareness activities that each of the local responders groups perform in their territories.¹¹²

Finally, the wide of range activities of the Italian Red Cross (Croce Rossa Italiana-CRI) at the local and the national, as well as the activities of the International Red Cross, are well documented in the comprehensive press review offered in a specific section the Italian Red

¹⁰⁶ "Protezione Civile – Archivio", *La Repubblica*, 2014.

<http://ricerca.repubblica.it/ricerca/repubblica?query=%22protezione+civile%22&view=repubblica&mode=all&fromdate=2004-01-01&todate=2014-01-19&author=&sortby=ddate>

¹⁰⁷ "Mr Fix-it in a fix", *The Economist*, 18 February 2010, <http://www.economist.com/node/15549561>

¹⁰⁸ Bonaccorsi M. and De Marco, R. *Potere assoluto. La protezione civile al tempo di Bertolaso*, Edizioni Alegre: Rome, 2009. Puliafito, A. *Protezione Civile Spa. Quando la protezione civile si fa business*, Aliberti: Reggio Emilia, 2010.

¹⁰⁹ Stella, G.A. "Urla inascoltate della terra ferita", *Corriere della Sera*, 20 November 2013,

http://archiviostorico.corriere.it/2013/novembre/20/URLA_INASCOLTATE_DELLA_TERRA_FERITA_co_0_20131120_6683d056-51ae-11e3-b627-e9178c75319e.shtml

¹¹⁰ Alfonso, D. et al. "Treno deraglia per la frana. "Poteva essere un disastro", *La Repubblica*, 17 January 2014, http://genova.repubblica.it/cronaca/2014/01/17/news/strade_chiuse_e_rischio_frane_la_pioggia_assedia_la_liguria-76157870/

¹¹¹ "A lezione di emergenza: 175 aspiranti volontari", *La Prealpina*, 04 April 2012,

http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/resources/cms/documents/rass_4_4_12_3.pdf

¹¹² "Rassegna", *ANPAS Piemonte*, 2014. <http://www.anpas.piemonte.it/area-stampa/rassegna/>

Cross website.¹¹³ Unlike the inconsistent CPD press archive, this archive offers the possibility to showcase centrally the large number of activities, especially by the local Italian Red Cross committees, in areas as training,¹¹⁴ recruitment of new volunteers,¹¹⁵ and the contribution to disaster relief operations (e.g. Sardinia floods on 17-19 November 2013).¹¹⁶

2.4.5.2 Use of media and communication technologies

In terms of social media, to date the CPD does not have an official Twitter account and has only a linked Facebook account related to its magazine,¹¹⁷ which includes also updates about its press releases and activities, active since 2010.

National bodies involved in the management of emergencies don't seem to have a coordinated presence on social media either. The Italian blogger Luca Tempestini reports that at the local level the presence on social media as Twitter also differs very much, depending on the region of the country (with Toscana, Lazio and Lombardy in the top places), and mostly related to personal initiatives and profiles rather than part of larger institutional strategy.¹¹⁸

Among other national bodies present on Twitter, at the date of this report, the Coast Guard had 1422 tweets and 2357 followers¹¹⁹; the Italian Red Cross 242 tweets and 4496 followers¹²⁰; the State Police only 3 tweets from May 2012, but 4067 followers¹²¹; ANPAS, a national network of volunteers that assist in disaster relief and civil protection at the local level, 3683 tweets and 1833 followers¹²²; and, what seems to be the most effective use of the medium, the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology (INGV) has a beta version of its account that includes an automatic feed of all the seismic events in Italy, with 12909 tweets and 100796 followers¹²³. With this tool, citizens can be alerted in real time about earthquakes from an official source and have a confirmation about events happened in their area and information regarding the epicentre and magnitude of the seismic event.

The absence of the CPD from the social media world has been widely criticized¹²⁴, and in this vacuum, it has been up to social media-savvy citizens to alert the(ir) public about recent events as the earthquakes in Abruzzo in 2009 and in Emilia-Romagna in 2012.

For example, local blogger Gianluca Diegoli tweeted at 4.13am on 20 May 2012, 10 minutes

¹¹³ "La Croce Rossa cerca nuove forze", *La Gazzetta di Reggio*, 16 January 2014, <http://www.ow8.rassegnestampa.it/crocerossaitalianaac/Search.aspx>

¹¹⁴ "Imparare ad usare il defibrillatore. Partono i corsi della Croce Verde", *Il Giornale di Vicenza*, 17 January 2014, <http://www.ow8.rassegnestampa.it/crocerossaitalianaac/PDF/2014/2014-01-17/2014011726536983.pdf>

¹¹⁵ "La Croce Rossa cerca nuove forze", *La Gazzetta di Reggio*, 16 January 2014, <http://www.ow8.rassegnestampa.it/crocerossaitalianaac/PDF/2014/2014-01-16/2014011626528978.pdf>

¹¹⁶ "Cento della Croce Rossa in aiuto agli alluvionati", *La Nuova Sardegna – Sassari*, 29 November 2013, <http://www.ow8.rassegnestampa.it/crocerossaitalianaac/PDF/2013/2013-11-29/2013112926181670.pdf>

¹¹⁷ "Protezione Civile" - *Magazine del Dipartimento della Protezione Civile*, <https://www.facebook.com/protezione.civile.magazine>

¹¹⁸ "Twitter e Protezione Civile → Si può fare di più", <http://www.socialwebstorm.com/twitter-e-protezione-civile-si-puo-fare-di-piu/>. This page includes also an embedded Excel file that lists the civil protection related Twitter accounts at the local level, classified by region

¹¹⁹ Costiera, "Guardia Costiera (guardiacostiera) on Twitter, 2013, <https://twitter.com/guardiacostiera>

¹²⁰ Croce Rossa Italiana, "Croce Rossa Italiana (crocerossa) on Twitter, 2014, <https://twitter.com/crocerossa>

¹²¹ Polizia di Stato, "Polizia di Stato (poliziadistato) on Twitter, 2013, <https://twitter.com/poliziadistato>

¹²² ANPAS Nazionale, "ANPAS Nazionale (Anpasnazionale) on Twitter, 2013, <https://twitter.com/Anpasnazionale>

¹²³ INGV Terremoti, "INGVterremoti (INGVterremoti) in Twitter, 2013, <https://twitter.com/INGVterremoti>

¹²⁴ Jacona, Alessio, "Terremoti: a cosa serve Twitter", *L'Espresso*, 29 May 2012, <http://espresso.repubblica.it/dettaglio/terremoti-a-cosa-serve-twitter/2182111>

of the event. In this case, even the INGV (Figure 2.19) feed proved to be late though: as the image below illustrates, the tweet was released only 40 minutes later, at 4.50am.

New media sociologist Giovanni Boccia Artieri has remarked that, in the case of the Emilia earthquake the first tweet was done by a citizen, the first advices were given by citizen experts in safety matters and many social media users tried, to the best of their ability, to map the events, providing an effective and geolocalized brief collectively constructed by citizens.¹²⁵

Figure 2.19: The INGV tweet informing the public about the Emilia Earthquake on 20 May 2012, 40 minutes after the event

Unsurprisingly, as Bologna's municipality contact person for the Digital Agenda, Michele D'Alena, has argued, the level of citizen response, and the usefulness of this response, heavily depends on the extent to which 1) local authorities are paying attention to citizen responses and, relatedly, 2) citizens know that their responses is being paid attention to.

For example, in the case of the heavy snowfall in the Bologna area in February 2012, citizens equipped with smartphones and tablets started to share and provide information on Facebook and Twitter with the hashtag #boneve, helping the local authority to direct the intervention through geo-referenced information on the local conditions.¹²⁶

In other words, D'Alena suggests, the keyword is participation from both sides, authorities and citizens, to help to construct a trustworthy relationship where the latter see themselves as active collaborators. Institutions, when coordinating their social media communications, should also monitor the sources, locate a unique hashtag to combine the information, then select, verify and share all the information that can be useful to the general public.

Therefore, the probability that governmental authorities reach out, identify and interact with citizen experts via digital media is higher where there is strong presence of civil protection culture, which is usually associated to levels of volunteerism, and a local government approach to the relationship with its citizens, that is open to listen to them and make a consistent and useful use of inputs given by the public.

Where the CPD and the organisations parts of the NCPS have started to make a more comprehensive use of digital and social media potentials for the purposes of awareness and

¹²⁵ Ibid.

¹²⁶ Ibid.

training, there seems to be no structural efforts to make a more comprehensive use of crowdsourcing, geotagging and social media tool at the national level.

Experiments are carried out at the local level (e.g. Bologna in the case above) or by researchers and operators that look also to international experiences (e.g. Haiti, USA) when trying to implement new solutions to support the emergency relief operations in Italy, with the purpose to help also the development of networks of citizen experts that can specialize in various types of emergencies and who can take initiative in the absence of efficient top-down co-ordination.

Emergency communication experts as the Italian scholar Elena Rapisardi have highlighted how the earthquake that hit the city of L’Aquila and its surroundings at 3.36am on 6th April 2009 as the first of the ‘web 2.0’ era in Italy as it prompted a relevant level of response by citizens. She reports that establishment of 130 Facebook groups, as well as high levels of Twitter and Facebook updates activities that, among other things, had the purpose to share information on victims and on the overall situation in the area, support rescue interventions and the search for relatives and friends.¹²⁷

However, Rapisardi remarks how there is still much to do in order to use the full potential that networked citizens can have as first responders in case of emergencies. Indeed, apart from those trained as emergency responders that are part of the support teams of registered voluntary associations, there is the possibility to include all those users equipped with smartphones to help document the situation in a particular area and provide reliable information that can help the authorities to deal with emergencies more efficiently.

The evaluation of the current status of web 2.0 tools within the Italian status is illustrated in the SWOT (Figure 2.20), which also shows how low levels of web literacy, collaboration among NCPS bodies and the lack of investment in experimenting with and implementing such technologies is hindering the potential of citizens to be a proactive actor in the emergency situations.

	Strength	Weakness
Opportunities	<p>Italian Civil Protection systemic approach</p> <p>Networking</p> <p>Volunteers Commitment</p> <p>Web 2.0 Community</p>	<p>«Web Divide»</p> <p>Common Approach</p> <p>Low Budget</p> <p>Free web 2.0 platforms</p>
Threats	<p>Variety of Bodies</p> <p>Lack of common approaches</p> <p>Participation and Collaboration</p> <p>Reliable Sources</p>	<p>Low Web and english literacy</p> <p>Past Dependencies</p> <p>Low Collaboration</p> <p>Slow pace of change</p> <p>Low Budget</p> <p>Lack of Continuance</p>

Figure 2.20: SWOT analysis of web 2.0 use in emergency communication in Italy Coordination¹²⁸

¹²⁷ Rapisardi, Elena “Building Civil Protection 2.0”, 2010, <http://www.slideshare.net/elenis/building-civil-protection-20-updated>

¹²⁸ Rapisardi, Elena “Building Civil Protection 2.0”, 2010, <http://www.slideshare.net/elenis/building-civil-protection-20-updated>

2.5 INVOLVEMENT OF CITIZENS AS VOLUNTEERS: REPORT ON UK

2.5.1 Introduction

Serious flooding can happen at any time and the UK has often been the victim of severe flooding several times over the last few years (Figure 2.21). It is estimated that more than 5 million properties, around 16% of UK properties, face a risk of flooding.¹²⁹

In 2007, flooding caused damage to more than 55,000 properties in the UK, took the lives of 13 people, and left 350,000 people without water supply. Estimates indicated that about 7,300 businesses were affected. These damages caused billions of spending by central government.¹³⁰ The risk of flood events in the UK has historically been high. Presently, around 5 million people live in areas with a risk of flooding in England and Wales, which raises concerns among government officials as to the best possible ways to respond to these types of incidents.¹³¹

Figure 2.21: Disaster occurrence in the UK (1980-2010).¹³²

In this report partners will focus their attention to one government and two non-government organizations based in the UK and their efforts to approach the public in order to raise awareness among the public regarding not only flooding but also other risks that may occur in their everyday life. These organizations are listed and described below.

¹²⁹ Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, "Reducing the threats of flooding and coastal change", UK, 13th December 2013. <https://www.gov.uk/government/policies/reducing-the-threats-of-flooding-and-coastal-change>

¹³⁰ Pitt, M., "The Pitt Review: Learning Lessons from the 2007 Floods", Cabinet Office, London, 2008. http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20080906001345/http://cabinetoffice.gov.uk/thepittreview/final_report.aspx

¹³¹ Kapucu, Naim, "Emergency and Crisis Management in the United Kingdom: Disasters Experienced, Lessons Learned, and Recommendations for the Future". in David McEntire (ed.). Comparative Emergency Management, 2010. <https://www.training.fema.gov/emiweb/edu/Comparative%20EM%20Book%20-%20Chapter%20-%20Emergency%20and%20Crisis%20Mgmt%20in%20the%20UK-Disasters.%20Lessons%20and%20Recomm.doc>

¹³² PreventionWeb. "Disaster Statistics - United Kingdom - Europe - Countries & Regions - PreventionWeb.net." <http://www.preventionweb.net/english/countries/statistics/?cid=183>

Environment Agency

They are an Executive Non-departmental Public Body responsible to the Secretary of State for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs.¹³³ They are responsible for the following:

- regulation of major industry
- flood and coastal risk management
- water quality and resources
- waste regulation
- climate change
- fisheries
- contaminated land
- conservation and ecology
- navigation

They may not be an emergency service, but they are considered a Category One responder under the Civil Contingencies Act, which means that they play a significant role in preparing for and supporting the response to emergencies in England. The Agency also has a responsibility to manage the risk of flooding from main rivers and the sea, as well as being a coastal erosion risk management authority.

British Red Cross (BRC)

The BRC is a volunteer-led humanitarian organisation that helps people in crisis both domestically and abroad. They help citizens prepare and respond to a variety of emergencies in their own communities. Finally, when the emergency situation is over, BRC provides aid to the people affected and help them recover.¹³⁴ The British Red Cross is a member of a global network of volunteers and staff, responding to natural disasters, conflicts and individual emergencies. Key facts about the organization:¹³⁵

- They are the UK's leading emergency response charity.
- They have around 3,500 staff and 32,500 volunteers.
- They help more than a million people in the UK every year, and many more around the world.
- They are part of the International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement, which works in 188 countries and has around 13.1 million volunteers worldwide.¹³⁶

Royal Navy Lifeboat Institute (RNLI)

The Royal National Lifeboat Institution is a charity registered in England and Wales. A specialized division of RNLI, the RNLI Flood Rescue Team is available 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, to deploy to flooding events in the UK, Ireland and abroad to perform search and rescue. The team has been trained for all the risks that are involved during such crises, for example when working in or around fast moving flood water.

¹³³ Environment Agency, "Environment Agency - About us", UK. <http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/aboutus/default.aspx>

¹³⁴ British Red Cross, "Who we are | British Red Cross". <http://www.redcross.org.uk/About-us/Who-we-are>

¹³⁵ British Red Cross, "Introducing the British Red Cross - Handbook", http://www.redcross.org.uk/About-us/~media/BritishRedCross/Documents/About%20us/GC_Intro_BRC_2012.pdf

¹³⁶ British Red Cross, "How to volunteer", Volunteer Handbook, UK. <http://www.redcross.org.uk/Get-involved/Volunteer/Thinking-of-volunteering/~media/BritishRedCross/Documents/Get%20involved/Volunteering/Volunteering%20handbook.pdf>

The team was formed back in 2000 and now have 250 members who can respond to a flood in the UK and Republic of Ireland within six hours, thanks to six divisional teams who have been placed strategically throughout the country. Out of these 250 members fifty of them form the international Flood Rescue Team, who can deploy anywhere in the world within 24 hours.¹³⁷

2.5.2 Citizen training and participation in emergency preparedness

The Environment Agency tries to raise public awareness on the matter of flooding in three different ways: education, various awareness programmes that involve visiting communities and mass communication campaigns.

First of all, in collaboration with the local authorities in Wales, they train and protect staff and pupils from flooding by creating flood plans for schools that are most often hit by floods. They also influence the Welsh Joint Education Committee (WJEC) Curriculum in order to ensure that flooding is covered through taught Geography lessons in schools.¹³⁸

The Environment Agency participates in the Flood Awareness Wales programme, which aims to communicate valuable knowledge and educate the public regarding the risks of flooding and how to prepare for such incidents and respond when such an incident occurs. They also visit homes, businesses, schools, farms and whole communities to raise awareness of flood risk and help people take actions to prepare. Realizing that the risk of flooding increases as weather patterns become more and more erratic, the Agency tries to propagate the message that people can no longer rely solely upon flood defences to protect themselves. Their motto is “we can't prevent flooding, but we can help people prepare for it”.¹³⁹

The Environment Agency also launches Flood Awareness Campaigns, which are four weeks campaigns to raise awareness about flooding. They urge people and get prepared during the critical months from September to April and also realize that flooding can't always be prevented but citizens can always prepare for it.¹⁴⁰

As far as participation of citizens is concerned, the Environment Agency also works closely with communities to encourage Flood Plan Leads. The Agency utilizes Flood Plan Leads, who are volunteers acting as a communication link between the community and Environment Agency before, during and after a flood. Their role includes the following responsibilities:

- Flood Plan Leads help ensure that the Agency's flood warning messages reach the local community.
- The Leads update the Agency about any issues relating to flooding in their community.

¹³⁷ Royal National Lifeboat Institution. "RNLI | About us | Flood rescue", UK. <http://rnli.org/aboutus/aboutthernli/Pages/Flood-rescue-team.aspx>

¹³⁸ Environment Agency. "Environment Agency - Flood awareness through education", UK, 5th September 2013. <http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/130029.aspx>

¹³⁹ Environment Agency. "Environment Agency - Flood Awareness Wales", UK, 17th December 2013. <http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/113810.aspx>

¹⁴⁰ MKWEB, "The Environment Agency is launching its annual Flood Season Awareness Campaign to warn people of the growing risk of flooding this winter. September marks the start of the winter ... | Education, Religion, Politics & Volunteering Information in Milton Keynes". <http://www.mkweb.co.uk/Community/The-Environment-Agency-is-launching-its-annual-Flood-Season-Awareness-Campaign-to-warn-people-of-the-growing-risk-of-flooding-this-winter-September-marks-the-start-of-the-winter.htm>

- They Lead may act as a coordinator of a flood plan which will help manage the potential impacts of flooding.
- Where a flood plan has been developed the Flood Plan Lead will be provided with a direct communications link to the Agency's Flood Operations room during an incident.
- A means of contact will also be made available to report issues such as blockages in river channels outside an incident.¹⁴¹

The British Red Cross is a leading voluntary organisation for emergency response, which has a large number of specially trained volunteers who provide a range of services to people in emergencies, including practical and emotional support and first aid services. The Red Cross, with 160 affiliated groups in England and Wales, launched a coordination program that proved to be timely and co-ordinated response before the 2007 UK floods to assist vulnerable people across areas threatened by flooding in the UK.¹⁴²

The partners were not able locate exact information regarding the training that volunteers are given when they first join the BRC. On the other hand, members of the public have the opportunity to receive training on providing first aid and emergency life support to their family or colleagues during or after an emergency event has occurred. A list of such courses can be seen in Figure 2.23 while the summary of the course is shown in Figure 2.24. BRC also provides an online learning service as an alternative more flexible way of providing training to citizens.¹⁴³

HOME, SWEET HOME?

Figure 2.22: Environment Agency's Flood Awareness Campaign poster.¹⁴⁴

According to their website, RNLI places great importance on the quality of training that volunteers receive. The organisation “uses a competence-based training framework to ensure

¹⁴¹ Environment Agency, "Environment Agency - Flood Awareness Wales - working with communities", UK, 3rd January 2014. <http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/homeandleisure/news/events/120166.aspx>

¹⁴² British Red Cross, "How the UK floods crisis unfolded | British Red Cross", UK, 2nd August 2007. <http://www.redcross.org.uk/What-we-do/Emergency-response/Past-emergency-appeals/National-Floods-Appeal-2007/How-the-crisis-unfolded>

¹⁴³ British Red Cross, "Online learning - First aid at work - Red Cross Training". <http://www.redcrossfirstaidtraining.co.uk/What-we-do/Online-learning.aspx>

¹⁴⁴ Malvern Hills District Council, "Flood Awareness Campaign", 25th November 2013. <http://www.malvern hills.gov.uk/cms/communications/news/2013/november/flood-awareness-campaign.aspx>

all volunteer crew and lifeguards are trained to an appropriate and safe standard that reflects individual job roles”.¹⁴⁵

The RNLI also tries to improve the skills and professionalism of all crew members and lifeguards by including externally accredited courses to their training. Volunteers risk their lives to save others, this being the main reason for RNLI’s efforts to enhance their skills and training. This has been recognised in 2003 and again in 2008 when the RNLI received a National Training Award.¹⁴⁶

Emergency life support ⓘ Hands-on, practical course with minimal clinical content.	4 hours AM or PM
Everyday First Aid ⓘ Flexible and informal session using real-life scenarios.	2 hours AM or PM
General first aid ⓘ Basic first aid skills with some clinical background.	1 day AM and PM
Practical first aid ⓘ A full-first aid course with a hands-on focus.	2 days AM and PM
Save a life ⓘ Quick introduction to basic first aid.	2 hours AM or PM

Figure 2.23: First Aid courses provided by BRC.¹⁴⁷

Figure 2.24: Brochure containing BRC’s first aid training course summary.

RNLI provides four kinds of training to its volunteers. These are operational training, lifeboat crew training, technical training courses and mobile training units. These are further analyzed below.¹⁴⁸

Volunteers are trained on operational aspects of their work at RNLI College and also at lifeboat stations, on beaches and in swimming pools to meet exacting fitness standards. They are also provided with study guides, online resources and other educational material to study at home. At the moment 4,000 lifeboat crew and lifeguards, following recommendation by their training divisional inspector or area/divisional lifeguard manager, participate in one or more of nearly 40 different courses currently on offer at RNLI College. The RNLI provides first-class training and equipment, guidance and support. Training is an ongoing process for the duration of a lifeboat crew member's service.

Every crew member undergoes a structured training programme, and trainee crew members undertake a 12-month probationary period, working through a crew development plan. In the first few months, the trainees learn about.¹⁴⁹

¹⁴⁵Royal Navy Lifeboat Institute, "RNLI | About us | Lifeboat training".

<http://rnli.org/aboutus/training/Pages/Lifeboat-training.aspx>

¹⁴⁶ Ibid.

¹⁴⁷ British Red Cross, "First aid courses | Red Cross Training", UK.

<http://www.redcrossfirstaidtraining.co.uk/Courses.aspx>

¹⁴⁸ Royal National Lifeboat Institution, "RNLI | About us | Lifeboat training", UK.

<http://rnli.org/aboutus/training/Pages/Lifeboat-training.aspx>

- the roles and responsibilities of people at the station and in their operating division
- how to use and look after their personal protective equipment
- the layout and equipment on their station's lifeboat(s)
- tying a range of knots and how to work with ropes safely.

The duration of the basic training is six months during which the volunteers get acquainted with the coxswain/helmsman and crew, they can then go on to RNLI College in Poole and attend a Trainee course.

RNLI also offers technical training courses for lifeboat mechanics and crew in a range of specialist engine types used in RNLI lifeboats. The courses are delivered by experts who support approved hands-on courses. Training courses are also offered to mechanics, crew and lifeguards for every aspect of launching and recovering lifeboats and other rescue craft safely. RNLI mechanics are trained in subjects such as Introduction to DC Electrics, mechanical fault finding, radar and electronic navigation aids and lifeboat mechanics.

Since the volunteers are basically citizens who have jobs and/or families outside RNLI, an effort is placed on not disrupting these commitments. For this reason, training is not only delivered in Poole at RNLI College but it is also provided around the coast by mobile training unit (MTU) trainers. The MTU trainers deliver courses and provide different types of training locally for crews and lifeguards, who do not have the means or time to travel to Poole. These courses may be delivered either during the day or in the evening depending on the crews' requirements. MTU trainers provide courses that range from search and rescue to boat handling and seamanship.

A special division of RNLI, called Flood Rescue Team and formed in 2000, receives a different kind of training. Specialist training is provided to this team as the work that they do is very different from their RNLI sea rescue role. They are indeed experienced lifeboat crew, but the conditions that exist during inland flooding may be very different to the ones they face during sea rescues. Team safety is essential in rescue operations; hence, regular training exercises are performed to ensure team members can work safely and effectively together in the unfamiliar terrain and diverse, high-risk environment of flood-affected areas.

Additional training is given to volunteers to become Floodwater Rescue Technicians and Flood Water Rescue Boat Operators because of the aforementioned diverse conditions that exist in flooding scenarios. This training covers skills such as operating boats in fast flowing water in narrow spaces similar to the streets of a town and performing rescues using two boats.

2.5.3 Training materials

The Environment Agency works with individuals, businesses, schools, farms and whole communities to raise awareness of flood risk and help people take actions to prepare. In order to help all of the above mentioned stakeholders, the Environment Agency offers flood plan templates on its website, which can be completed for a community, a business, a school, a caravan park or even to create a personal flood plan.¹⁵⁰ They also provide a document whose

¹⁴⁹ Royal Navy Lifeboat Institute, "Lifeboat crew training", <http://rnli.org/aboutus/training/Pages/Lifeboat-crew-training-tabs/Lifeboat-crew-training.aspx>

¹⁵⁰ Environment Agency, "Environment Agency - Flood Awareness Wales", UK, 17th December 2013. <http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/113810.aspx>

purpose is to inform flood plan leads about their duties during a flood.¹⁵¹ Specifically, the document explains the role of the Lead by analyzing the following topics:¹⁵²

- **Responsibilities of Plan Leads do prior to a flood:** Some of the responsibilities in this case include the identification of problem areas, the identification of vulnerable residents in an area and the encouragement of people to complete individual household plans.
- **Responsibilities of Plan Leads do during a flood:** The main role of a Lead during a flood is to provide a communication channel between the Environment Agency and the community.
- **Responsibilities of Plan Leads do after a flood:** After a flood has occurred the Lead will help with issues such as helping people by providing information on organizations that can assist them in clearing up their homes and reviewing the local Flood Plan.

On their website, the Environment Agency have also posted a leaflet regarding the preparation of a flood kit, which contains a list of items that are valuable during or after a flood has passed.¹⁵³

The Agency also utilizes Social Media to educate civilians on the risks of flooding and the ways that they can protect themselves. An example is shown below, where the Agency provides “Tips & Tricks” for citizens to protect their own homes.

Figure 2:25: Environment Agency's YouTube video.

As was mentioned earlier, partners could not find any educational material that is provided by the BRC to volunteers relating specifically to flood preparedness. BRC does offer advice on its website regarding the preparation of citizens for crises such as flooding, heat waves and

¹⁵¹ Environment Agency, "Who are flood leads", UK, 17th December 2013. http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/static/documents/20120821_FAW_Flood_Plan_Lead_Web_Version.doc

¹⁵² Ibid.

¹⁵³ Environment Agency, "Prepare a flood kit", UK, 17th December 2013. http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/static/documents/Leisure/Make_a_Flood_Pack_Kit_-_bilingual_combined.pdf

terrorist attacks.¹⁵⁴ The information for each crisis is divided into three phases, what citizens should do before, during and after a crisis.

BRC also utilizes social media, such as YouTube, as educational means for training citizens. An example can be seen in Figure 2.26 where first aid tips are providing for the cases of poisoning and performing Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) on adults.

Based on partners' research, RNLI does not provide any educational material that directly relates to preparedness in case of flooding. They do promote preparedness on other situations though when people's lives may be in danger such as when kayaking or surfing, as shown in the leaflets of Figure 2.27.

Figure 2.26: BRC's YouTube training videos on providing first aid.

Figure 2.27: Leaflets provided by RNLI concerning safety when surfing or kayaking.¹⁵⁵

¹⁵⁴ British Red Cross, "How to prepare for emergencies | British Red Cross", UK. <http://www.redcross.org.uk/What-we-do/Preparing-for-disasters/How-to-prepare-for-emergencies>

2.5.4 Recruitment and networking of new members

The Environment Agency, being a government agency, has government personnel and does not recruit citizens. Most citizens who want to volunteer and participate in their local communities have the opportunity to do so at their local town or city level and the Environment Agency facilitates the communication between citizens and local authorities or agencies by posting volunteer vacancies on their website. For example, the South Hams village of Yealmpton was looking for emergency volunteers, after more than 25 properties in Yealmpton and the nearby village of Yealmbridge were flooded in 2012. The Agency posted on their website an article urging potential emergency volunteers to come forward and help reduce the impact of future floods on their families, neighbours and colleagues.¹⁵⁶

BRC mostly use their website to recruit new volunteers. They provide a volunteer's handbook and a list of all the necessary steps that a potential volunteer must take in order to become a member of the BRC (Figure 2.28).¹⁵⁷ ¹⁵⁸ A database with all available openings is also available on the website, an example of which is provided in the Figure 2.29.

Figure 2.1: BRC's volunteer handbook.

¹⁵⁵ Royal National Lifeboat Institution, "Staying safe on the beach with the RNLI", UK. <http://rnli.org/safetyandeducation/stayingsafe/beach-safety/Pages/Beach-safety-advice.aspx>

¹⁵⁶ Environment Agency, "Environment Agency - Can you help Yealmpton in a flood or other emergency?", UK, 12th September 2013. <http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/news/148662.aspx?page=4&month=7&year=2013>

¹⁵⁷ British Red Cross, "How to volunteer", Volunteer Handbook, UK. <http://www.redcross.org.uk/Get-involved/Volunteer/Thinking-of-volunteering/~media/BritishRedCross/Documents/Get%20involved/Volunteering/Volunteering%20handbook.pdf>

¹⁵⁸ British Red Cross, "How to volunteer | British Red Cross", UK. <http://www.redcross.org.uk/Get-involved/Volunteer/Thinking-of-volunteering/How-to-volunteer>

<u>Title</u>	<u>Division</u>	<u>Activity</u>	<u>Interest Area</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Position Type</u>
<u>(FESS) Fire and Emergency Support Service Volunteer</u>	Volunteering	Fire and Emergency Support	Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland & Isle of Man	Forth Valley	Volunteer
<i>Imagine it's 3am and a family's just lost everything they own in a house fire. Everyone is safe but the children are cold and they have nowhere to go. Our volunteers turn up day or night to offer practical help and support. Could you help people in their time of need? Training and Interviews will be taking place from April 2014</i>					
<u>Admin and mentoring volunteer for ER planning dept</u>	Volunteering	Emergency Planning & Response	Volunteering (outside UK office, London)	Essex	Volunteer
<u>Admin and Reception Volunteer - Refugee Support Service</u>	Volunteering	Refugee Support	Volunteering (outside UK office, London)	London	Volunteer

Figure 2.29: Indicative volunteer job openings at BRC.¹⁵⁹

RNLI predominantly utilizes its website for recruitment purposes. There exists a separate section of the website dedicated to volunteering where potential volunteers can locate information on ways they can get involved ranging from joining the lifeboat and shore crew to fundraising and becoming a Volunteer Education Presenter whose focus is to ignite interest in RNLI and give advice on how to stay safe on or near the water. A database of available vacancies is also online, as shown in Figure 2.30.

All current vacancies

Overview of all vacancies at the RNLI. (Click on role titles for more information and to apply)

Volunteer Community Fundraising Assistant - Blackpool

Location : Blackpool
Time commitment: Flexible
Volunteer area: North Region
Volunteer type: Fundraising Volunteer
Closing Date: 06-04-2014
Reference: V3693

[More info](#)

Volunteer Community Fundraising Assistant - Liverpool

Location : Liverpool
Time commitment: Flexible
Volunteer area: North Region
Volunteer type: Fundraising Volunteer
Closing Date: 06-04-2014
Reference: V3694

[More info](#)

Figure 2.30: RNLI relies on its website to recruit new volunteers to be placed at a variety of positions.¹⁶⁰

2.5.5 Media coverage and use of media for citizen outreach programs

The Environment Agency utilizes not only traditional media, such as television and radio, to communicate its actions and other information to citizens all over the UK but also a variety of social media, such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube. The main purpose of using traditional and new communication technologies is to issue warnings on possible storms which could

¹⁵⁹ British Red Cross, "British Red Cross - Home Page | British Red Cross", UK, 2010.

http://gs11.globalsuccessor.com/fe/tpl_redcross02.asp?newms=se

¹⁶⁰ Royal National Lifeboat Institution, "Current vacancies - The RNLI is the charity that saves lives at sea", UK. <https://volunteering.rnli.org/vacancies.html>

lead to flooding rather than asking for civilians to participate in volunteering actions. An example of such warnings and alerts are shown on a map of the UK, as shown in Figure 2.31.

Figure 2.31: The Environment Agency issues flood warnings and alerts on its Twitter and Facebook accounts.

Environment Agency’s YouTube channel (also called as EnvironmentAgencyTV) provides constant updates on flooding events and operations throughout the UK as well as educational material and advertisements which aid promote flood preparedness among citizens. An example of such an advertisement is shown in Figure 2.32.

Figure 2.32: Environment Agency’s advertisement on promoting flood preparedness.

BRC mainly utilizes social media for the same purposes as the Environment Agency does, which is mostly for providing information to their followers regarding flood warnings and

alerts as well as logging their recent actions. Nevertheless, television adverts, such as the one shown in Figure 2.33, also appear frequently to reach the public.

Figure 2.33: BRC's television advert aiming to reach the public and raise awareness.

An example is shown in Figure 2.32 where the BRC informs the citizens of the actions of volunteers who have been distributing sandbags to elderly people in Belfast in an effort to secure their homes from the water.

Furthermore, BRC's YouTube channel is also used extensively for reasons such as to educate the public on a variety of matters (e.g. HIV awareness), to inform of events that BRC has organized and to provide practical instructions on how to deal with certain emergency incidents such as the one shown in Figure 2.34 (right).

Figure 2.34: (Left) Facebook post from BRC. (Right) Education video on BRC's YouTube channel.

As far as RNLI is concerned, partners could not find any indications as to whether traditional media, like the television and radio, are used to promote their actions or for recruitment purposes. It seems that their social media accounts are more active in that respect, with the Twitter, Facebook and YouTube accounts constantly being updated with new content relating to fundraising events and opportunities, recruitment call outs and finally information, in the form of text, photos and videos, of both recent and older operations that they have participated in. Examples of such information are shown in Figure 3.35.

Figure 2.35: RNLi’s Twitter and Facebook accounts are used to disseminate information relating to, among others, recruitment opportunities, fundraising events and description of recent operations.

2.6 INVOLVEMENT OF CITIZENS AS VOLUNTEERS: REPORT ON GREECE

2.6.1 Introduction

Earthquakes are natural phenomena that occur frequently in many countries around the world. According to the tectonic plate theory, most earthquakes occur at the edges where the plates come in contact with each other. Since the Western part of Greece is where the Eurasian and African plates converge, the country is considered as having high seismic activity and, in fact, Greece is considered the number one country in seismicity in Europe (Figure 2.36) and sixth worldwide.¹⁶¹

Figure 2.36: European Earthquake Hazard Map.¹⁶²

Also, as shown in Figure 2.37, with 20 events, earthquakes were the most frequent type of disaster occurring in Greece between 1980 and 2010. This was followed by floods, and wildfires.

¹⁶¹ GR Reporter, "Greece is sixth in the world by seismic activity | GRReporter.info- News from Greece - Breaking News, Business, Sport, Multimedia and Video", 4th March 2010. <http://www.greporter.info/en/greece-sixth-world-seismic-activity/2183>

¹⁶²Prevention Web, "Europe: earthquake hazard map - Maps - Professional Resources - PreventionWeb.net", January 2010. <http://www.preventionweb.net/english/professional/maps/v.php?id=3825>

Figure 2.37: Disaster Occurrence in Greece (1980-2010)¹⁶³

Strong earthquakes in Thessaloniki in 1978, Volos in 1980, and Athens in 1981 and 1999, illustrated the need to establish agencies responsible for designing the country's earthquake policy. Other non-governmental organizations (NGOs) were also formed to aid government agencies in raising public awareness and preparedness for such events.

This report will focus on one government organization and one NGO and on their efforts, or lack thereof, to improve emergency preparedness among citizens so that when earthquakes strike, they will be able to execute certain actions to mitigate the effects of the earthquake. Specifically, partners will study the aforementioned efforts in terms of communication between citizens and organizations, through face-to-face contact, through conventional media channels, or through more recent forms of communication such as social media, but also other strategies that organizations employ to educate and involve citizens as much as possible in the preparedness effort.

The report will present the preparedness plans of the following organizations:

Organization for Anti-Seismic Design and Protection (OASP), Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks

The OASP is a public law legal entity, supervised by the Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks. Founded in 1983, its purpose is to elaborate and design the national earthquake policy, in the context of government direction and coordination of the operations of public and private resources for the implementation of this policy.

Hellenic Rescue Team (HRT)

The Hellenic Rescue Team is a non-governmental search and rescue organization, whose members have been participating in operations since 1978 on a volunteer basis. Since 1994, the team operates as an Association. The Central Administration of the Hellenic Rescue Team is based in Thessaloniki and it has 34 branches throughout Greece.

¹⁶³ Prevention Web, "Disaster Statistics - Greece - Europe - Countries & Regions - PreventionWeb.net". <http://www.preventionweb.net/english/countries/statistics/?cid=68>

The HRT has been certified by the General Secretariat for Civil Protection of the Ministry for Public Order as well as by the United Nations' International Search and Rescue Advisory Group (INSARAG) since June 23, 2005. The HRT is in continuous collaboration with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the European Union (through the European Community Humanitarian Office). It is also a full member of the International Maritime Rescue Federation (IMRF), the Global Federation for Mountain Rescue IKAR-CISA, and the International Rescue Dog Organization (IRO).

With a force of more than 2,000 volunteers across Greece, the HRT participates in search and rescue operations in emergencies and mass disasters, wherever they may occur both in Greece and abroad. It is staffed by professional and amateur rescuers with excellent scientific and technical training, acting through a sense of volunteer duty.

2.6.2 Citizen training and participation in emergency preparedness

The OASP focuses on raising public awareness along three main axes. The first axis involves a volunteer programme operated by the OASP; the second involves various research projects in which the organization participates, such as FP7 and other EU-funded projects; and the third axis involves cooperation with other Greek agencies and organizations to promote preparedness and awareness among citizens.

The Volunteer Action for Crisis & Risk Management and Emergency Event Handling educational programme "Protecting Myself and Others" aims to help volunteers develop skills in risk management and crisis and emergency response, so that they may be able to help their fellow citizens during an emergency event.

Since 2001, when the programme commenced, approximately 8,500 volunteers have been trained in 210 municipalities across Greece. Furthermore, in collaboration with the National Public Administration Centre, the OASP has also implemented 20 two-day workshops on risk management issues for the training of 2,500 employees in Public Administration and Local government authorities. Finally, training seminars have been implemented through various programmes, for workers in hospitals, utilities and other entities.

The OASP collaborates with other Greek entities to organize events, such as workshops and seminars, where citizens can be educated on the hazards of earthquakes and other disasters. The poster of one such workshop is shown in Figure 2.38.

The OASP also participates in EU-funded projects, such as FP7 and Community Support Framework projects. An example of an FP7 project is "Raising Earthquake Awareness and Coping Children's Emotions" (RACCE).¹⁶⁴ The coordinator of this project is the Natural History Museum of Crete in Heraklion, whose activities regarding citizen preparedness will be described in detail later on. The other actors involved in the project are: the Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest, the EPPO, the Centro Studi e Formazione Villa Montesca– Italy, the Centre for Educational Initiatives – Bulgaria, the Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia–sezione di Napoli Osservatorio Vesuviano – Italy, and the Association pour la Gestion de la Reserve Naturelle Geologique de Haute Provence – France.

¹⁶⁴ Project co-funded by the EU, Civil Protection Financial Instrument, Grant Agreement No.070401/2010/579066/SUB/C4, "RACCE". <http://racce.nhmc.uoc.gr/>

Figure 2.38: OASP workshop poster.

The project aims primarily to inform children and other groups about the risk of earthquakes, and to develop innovative methodologies and training materials to reduce psychological and other effects of earthquakes on children.

Another project that the OASP participated in is called “Seismopolis”¹⁶⁵, a Pilot Integrated System that facilitated familiarization with earthquakes and raising public awareness about earthquake protection. The aim of the project was to familiarize citizens (preschool or primary school students, teachers, the general population, volunteers, members of Civil Protection authorities, etc.) with earthquakes, and to provide training in earthquake protection with the assistance of modern pedagogy and technology. To achieve this objective, the ‘Seismopolis’ centre was created, hosted in an area of the Municipality of Agios Ioannis Rendis (Attica) (Figures 2.39 thru 2.42).

Figure 2.39: Educational activities at the festival for children in Agios Nikolaos, Crete, held on June 10, 2012.

Figure 2.40: Earthquake Simulator at the Natural History Museum of Lesvos, one of the project partners.

¹⁶⁵ OASP, "«Σεισμόπολις» (Πιλοτικό Ολοκληρωμένο Σύστημα για την εξοικείωση με τους σεισμούς και την πληροφόρηση του κοινού σε θέματα αντισεισμικής προστασίας) | Ο.Α.Σ.Π". <http://www.oasp.gr/node/211>

Figure 2.41: Virtual Reality during an earthquake.

Figure 2.42: Educational classes at the Seismopolis centre.

Finally, within the framework of the International Day for Natural Disaster Reduction on October 14, 2013, the OASP, in collaboration with the Urban Rail Transport [STA.SY.] SA, provided information to citizens using the underground railway about protective measures in the event of an earthquake. The purpose of this event was to create awareness and educate the general population so as to reduce the negative effects of earthquakes through prevention and preparedness activities. Figure 2.43 shows the poster for this educational event.

As an NGO, the HRT has organized and participated in a variety of projects aiming to raise public awareness not only for earthquake preparedness, but also for other kinds of natural disasters. The HRT, always focused on its goal to educate citizens, frequently implements activities on prevention and handling of emergency events, including earthquakes. Within the framework of this axis of its activity, HRT members frequently visit schools, organizations, associations and businesses, educating the people there on the appropriate ways to be prepared for an earthquake, but also for the correct way to handle the event as it happens and after it is over. However, HRT's contribution is not limited to providing theoretical information. Subsequently, if requested from HRT members, practical training is provided on aspects such as safe evacuation of a building and releasing trapped individuals.

INDES – MUSA
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Πρόσκληση

Ο Οργανισμός Αντισεισμικού Σχεδιασμού και Προστασίας (ΟΑΣΠ - ΠΤΣΑΚ), το Εθνικό Αστεροσκοπείο Αθηνών, Γεωδυναμικό Ινστιτούτο και η GEOSYSTEMS HELLAS A.E. στα πλαίσια του προγράμματος INDES - MUSA σας προσκαλούν στην ενημερωτική εκδήλωση με τίτλο

INDES - MUSA :
Πρωτοποριακό ερευνητικό πρόγραμμα στο Καλοχώρι Θεσσαλονίκης

Ημερομηνία & ώρα
Πέμπτη 31 Οκτωβρίου 2013, 6μμ - 9μμ

Χώρος φιλοξενίας
Αμφιθέατρο ΤΕΕ, Μεγ. Αλεξάνδρου 49, Θεσσαλονίκη

Είσοδος Ελεύθερη

Περισσότερες πληροφορίες θα βρείτε στην ιστοσελίδα www.indes-musa.gr

Figure 2.43: Poster of educational event hosted by OASP.

Recently, the HRT participated—together with other volunteer organizations from Thessaloniki – in the first large-scale drill on the organization and administration of a camp in the event of an earthquake.

Figure 2.44: HRT visit to a Greek public school

Figure 2.45: HRT visit to a company

Specifically, on September 27-29, 2013, the HRT participated in a programme organized by the Municipality of Thermi under the name “Aegis 2013”. This was an original, large-scale drill and it was the first time the general population participated actively, towards the goal of being better prepared for natural disaster conditions, such as following an earthquake or flood. The drill involved the setting up of a camp, which under real circumstances would function as a shelter for many individuals and families. Visitors to the drill location were able to participate interactively (Figure 2.46, Figure 2.47).

Figure 2.46: “Aegis” exercise poster.

Figure 2.47: Camp created by HRT for the needs of exercise “Aegis”.

The drill, an initiative of the Municipality of Thermi, took place in the area of the Thermi Dam, where a mock camp was set up according to the specifications provided by the OASP. The camp included 60 tents and the entire technical infrastructure necessary for the proper and smooth operation of the camp (bathrooms, potable water supply, lighting, power supply, fire safety network). During the drill, various unpredictable event scenarios were played out, such as searching for missing persons that were supposedly lost in their attempt to reach the camp through a mountain road, two fire events within the camp, three injury events, and two fainting episodes. However, what added value to the drill was that the general population was

able to actively participate for the first time, and receive information on how to be properly prepared for natural disasters.

At the same time, the HRT organizes drills and training sessions for the members of its branches all over Greece, for the continuous improvement of their level of operational readiness, so that they can be ready to intervene effectively whenever and wherever it is required.

2.6.3 Training materials

The OASP webpage contains a variety of educational material on preparedness in emergency situations. These include videos, instructions, PowerPoint presentations, brochures and handbooks on how different population groups should react in the event of an earthquake in their area. There are also instructions on where and how to place furniture and objects in their home, in order to avoid being hit by large objects falling during an earthquake.

Specifically, the website defines seven different population categories that should be well educated on how to mitigate the impact of an earthquake:

- General population
- Teachers
- Students
- Volunteers
- Persons with disabilities
- Tourists
- Civil Protection agencies

For the general population that does not have any training, the website lists a series of clear instructions on how citizens should prepare for an earthquake, what their actions should be focused on during an earthquake and, finally, what they should do right after the earthquake. In addition to the list of instructions, which are valuable but not detailed, the OASP website also provides educational material in separate files with more information on the above-mentioned topics, which can be downloaded by users. Similarly, for the other population categories, OASP provides information tailored to each, taking into consideration the diverse characteristics of each population group.

Figure 2.48: Educational material found on the OASP website.

In the past year, the HRT, with the assistance of its sponsors, INTERAMERICAN and GENESIS PHARMA, issued four informational brochures. Two of these dealt with “Proper preparation for an eventual earthquake” and “Dealing with extreme weather conditions”, and were distributed free of charge to the audience during public information events, visits and promotional events organized by the HRT. In their effort to spread knowledge, HRT has used press releases and newsletter to forward the contents of these brochures to the media and to their partners, while at the same time the information was also posted on their website and on the HRT profiles on social media.

It should be noted that the training material on proper preparedness for earthquakes is also included in the contents of the Basic Training School handbook, which is distributed to all the trainees at HRT schools at all HRT branches.

Figure 2.49: HRT brochure on protection from floods.

Figure 2.50: HRT brochure on preparedness against earthquakes.

The HRT website also contains valuable information on how citizens can be prepared for events such as earthquakes or tsunamis. Just like on the OASP website, HRT focuses on preparedness actions before an earthquake strikes, as well as instructions on how citizens can protect themselves during and after the earthquake. National emergency telephone numbers are also provided.

2.6.4 Recruitment and networking of new members

Since 2001, the OASP has been a member of the national Volunteer Action for Crisis & Risk Management and Emergency Event Handling programme “Protecting Myself and Others”, coordinated by the General Secretariat for Lifelong Learning, of the Ministry for Education, Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs.

The programme offers 100 hours of training over 2.5 months. It trains citizens – volunteers so that they can develop the necessary skills to manage risks and emergencies. It is under the auspices of two Ministries and involves eight different agencies competent on diverse programme areas. It takes place in collaboration with Local Government Authorities and other entities.

The volunteers receive training in the following areas:

- Panic Management
- Fire – Flood
- Earthquake and Protective Measures
- Maritime Accidents – Marine Environment Protection
- First Aid

To this day, approximately 6,000 volunteers have been trained across Greece. The programme's website is at www.ethelontismos.gr.

The recruitment of new HRT members takes place all year round, through all available communication channels. However, the largest recruitment campaign takes place shortly before the commencement of the Basic Training School, which is organized by the HRT Central Administration in Thessaloniki. This campaign involves at least two press releases sent to print and electronic media, several social media posts, primarily on the HRT profile on Facebook which has 7,086 followers, and it is also promoted through the website at www.hrt.org.gr.

There are also many people who decide to become members of the HRT human resources after participating in day conferences, events, or seminars that are organized frequently all over Greece. At such events, participants learn about the HRT's work and subsequently express an interest in volunteering to help. Another effective measure has proven to be the handing out of brochures shortly before the commencement of the Basic Training School.

Finally, the promotion of HRT through the media, via television and radio advertisements, has led a lot of people who were looking for volunteer opportunities to contact the Hellenic Rescue Team.

2.6.5 Media coverage and use of media for citizen outreach programs

Both the OASP and the HRT utilize traditional media outlets such as newspapers, radio and television channels to communicate their actions to the public. HRT also has several accounts in the most popular social media such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube.

Specifically, the OASP uses newspaper and online articles as well as radio advertisements to either inform citizens of imminent events which could be of interest to them, or to disseminate the results and findings of such events.

Figure 2.51: The OASP educational television message.

Press releases are sent to the media whenever the HRT participates in any search and rescue operation, but also for trainings, exercises, seminars or sponsor events. In an effort to take advantage of the interactive experience offered by social media, all of HRT's press releases are first posted on their Facebook page, ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΟΜΑΔΑ ΔΙΑΣΩΣΗΣ – HELLENIC RESCUE TEAM, and on their website at www.hrt.org.gr.

HRT's contact with the media and the important volunteer work accomplished by HRT members have resulted in the journalistic coverage of their activities, in the form of news reports, interviews on television, radio, print or electronic media, as well as special reports mostly on television shows. This gives HRT the opportunity to make their work widely known. Furthermore, with the Assistance of the National Council on Radio & Television, the television and radio advertisements of the Hellenic Rescue Team are broadcasted twice a year by all Greek media, free of charge.

It should be noted that, in addition to Facebook (Figure 2.52), the Hellenic Rescue Team also has profiles on Twitter, @HellenicRescue, and on LinkedIn, Ελληνική Ομάδα Διάσωσης – Hellenic Rescue Team, as well as a YouTube channel (Figure 2.53), Hellenic Rescue Team. HRT uses social media to inform the public of their current actions, forthcoming events and also for recruitment purposes.

Figure 2.52: HRT Facebook page.

Figure 2.53: HRT YouTube channel.

2.7 CONCLUSION

In this chapter partners focused their attention on several organizations, both governmental and voluntary, based in four different countries, namely Italy, Turkey, UK and Greece; and researched their efforts in raising public awareness in potential emergency incidents, such as flooding and earthquakes.

In Turkey, several government agencies and volunteer organizations actively engage in preparing citizens of emergencies. The types of activities that these organizations undertake include public education programs, mass media campaigns, as well as, research and development activities. Since Turkey is in a highly active seismic region, most of these organizations seem to emphasize (and prioritize) preparedness of earthquakes in their activities. On the one hand, given the salience of earthquakes as the major type of disaster that has claimed most lives (and property) in Turkey, combined with the vividness of experiences of the Turkish public in recent high-impact earthquakes, this approach may prove fruitful in terms of getting and keeping public's attention on emergency preparedness. On the other hand, this approach may reduce attention paid to other common types of disasters, like floods, which are increasingly more likely to take place with climate change.

In terms of training of citizens and volunteers, we see that organizations in Turkey are utilizing a considerably large set of approaches that can appeal to different population groups. For example, AKUT, a volunteer organization that provides emergency recovery and rescue services use methods like mobile earthquake simulators to musicals (targeting children) to increase awareness. Likewise, AFAD, a government agency, under its "The Reduction of Seismic Risk and Crisis Preparation in Istanbul" (ISMEP) project uses a mix of cartoons, games, and quizzes to reach out to children while at the same time providing workshops, brochures and handbooks for adults. These training materials address a wide range of topics such as emergency preparedness, safety during emergencies, physical and psychological help in the aftermath of emergencies (earthquakes). Another government agency, AADYEM, stands out from among the organizations partners analyzed in terms of the wider range of emergencies that are covered by their educational materials. These include floods, droughts, avalanches, terrorism and earthquakes.

With respect to availability and accessibility of training materials, the Turkish Red Crescent, UMKE, and AKA seem to fall behind AFAD, AADYEM and AKUT. In the case of the Turkish Red Crescent, training materials that are available on their website are mostly information about the projects and do not provide detailed information for training citizens. Given that it targets medical professionals, UMKE's training materials are unsurprisingly too complicated for citizens. Most interesting case is that of AKA: the organization requires member sign up for access to its training materials.

In terms of involvement of citizens in emergency preparedness and response in Turkey, we see that some of the government and volunteer organizations are highly active in terms of recruiting and training volunteers. For example, while AKUT's emphasis is on recruiting and training rescue volunteers, AFAD seems to be active in recruiting volunteers that can act as a bridge between government and communities and help trickle down information regarding emergency preparedness. In addition, AFAD also seems to be active in terms of getting citizens to contribute to know-how and technology for emergency response. For example, through National Earthquake Research Program, it solicits projects from citizens (as well as researchers and industry). On the other hand, partners have also observed that in some cases

organizations do not provide sufficient information about how volunteers will be recruited and may produce too much red-tape during registration processes.

Finally, we observed that most of the organizations in Turkey utilize a highly diversified media mix, potentially increasing the chances that they will reach out to different segments of the population. Almost all of them have social media presence (e.g., Youtube channels, Facebook pages), they utilize outdoor advertisements for campaigns, some utilize television programming and advertisements, and, last but definitely not the least, they utilize face-to-face contact with citizens through information booths.

In Italy, the overall management of disasters relief operations and the activities that aim to raise awareness on natural disaster risks affecting the country is the responsibility of the Civil Protection Department (CPD), heading the National Civil Protection Service (NCPS), which includes local, regional and national stakeholders that intervene at their respective levels in case of calamities. The NCPS system includes 2,500 voluntary organizations and 1,300,000 volunteers, 60,000 of whom can be deployed within a few minutes, and 300,000 in a few hours. The volunteers are called to action by their respective authorities, with CPD taking the overall command of operation in case of large disasters. Most of the volunteers that operate locally are equipped with basic emergency relief skills provided at the local and regional level by the voluntary organizations.

The CPD also coordinates national awareness campaigns, most notably on earthquake risks, with the campaign “I don't risk” (Io non rischio) promoted locally by the nation-wide voluntary organization ANPAS. The documentation is released in both Italian and English, and includes a presence on social media networks as Twitter, Facebook, Youtube and Instagram. Another awareness project coordinated by the CPD, aiming to instil a culture of prevention among young people, is the Summer School Camp which is organized in coordination with regional voluntary organizations across the country. Regions and Municipalities complement the activities of the CPD by publishing booklets and put in place campaigns at the local level by focusing on the possible natural disaster risks in their own specific areas.

Simulations of disaster and emergency response are also part of the CPD approach, and such exercises are organized at the regional and macro-regional level to test the operationality and response of all those involved in the chain of command, as well as the rapidity and criticalities of the civil protection system.

Where a wide range of activities is put in place, a recent OECD report¹⁶⁶ has however warned that there is still resistance in some parts of Italy in making the public aware of the real potential risk of natural disasters, and their consequences, due to the belief that this might provoke unnecessary panic. OECD has recommended the Italian authorities to engage further in awareness activities in order to equip citizens in risk-prone areas with the basic skills that can permit them to be effective first responders if needed.

In terms of training materials, the CPD hosts a range of publications on its website including brochures (in PDF format) that inform the public about risks in different areas of Italy and educational material for families and schools that aim to spread a culture of risk prevention among the general population. These educational materials also aim to inform the public on

¹⁶⁶ OECD, *OECD Reviews of Risk Management Policies: Italy 2010. Review of the Italian National Civil Protection System*, 2010, http://www.keepeek.com/Digital-Asset-Management/oecd/governance/oecd-reviews-of-risk-management-policies-italy-2010_9789264082205-en, p.84

what to do in case they need to get further information after/during a disaster, and how to organize the family and how to ask for help. The training provided to volunteers who are part of the NCPS is not addressed centrally but devolved to the regional branches of the CPD. Indeed, regional and local authorities organize training courses based on the specific needs of their territories, providing them with the flexibility of designing advanced courses that differ from region to region according to the circumstances.

As for the recruitment of volunteers, Italy suffers from regional imbalances, as some regions are much better equipped than others. The aforementioned OECD report pointed out how the country has a large number of motivated and skilled volunteers, with Northern regions leading the way in terms of financial resources and prepared workforce in case of disasters. The recruitment drives are done locally, with CPD having only the role to promote the importance of volunteering at the national level, mainly only through its website. To our knowledge, CPD does not utilize outdoor or mainstream media (TV, Radio, press) advertising for this purpose. In practice, if an individual decides to become a volunteer, it will have to contact its local voluntary civil protection organization (which needs to be listed in a national register administered by the CPD) become a member and attends the necessary basic training modules. Local volunteering organizations utilize their own social media presence and local media publicity to advertise their recruitment drives.

The digital and social media presence of Italian disaster relief organizations has been, and still is, subject of discussion among researchers and practitioners, as the CPD has not been using fully the possibilities offered by social media networks to raise awareness and to assist in disaster relief operations, allegedly not learning for best practices performed elsewhere in the world (e.g. Haiti, USA). In the absence of national coordination, the use of social media during recent disasters, like the 2009 Abruzzo and the 2012 Emilia-Romagna earthquake, has been led by social media-savvy citizens or groups of volunteers who have been trying to provide useful geo-localized information to the public. However, there are examples of good practice at the local level, in places where there is a strong awareness and prevention culture as in the case of the municipality of Bologna, where citizens and local authorities engaged in a successful use of social media to support the response of municipality and voluntary organizations during the heavy snowfall that hit the area February 2012. Moreover, since the 2009 Abruzzo earthquake, citizens have also been engaging in using social media for the purpose of sharing information about the victims and about the overall situation in areas affected by disasters, to support rescue interventions and to help citizens search for relatives and friends. However, at this time, Italy may still be considered as lagging behind the other cases we analyzed in terms of the use of networked citizens to support authorities and responders in their tasks of effective intervention during and in the aftermath of natural disasters. This is mainly due to the absence of common approaches at the national level, extremely low budgets aimed at the development of technological solutions and low levels of collaboration among the components of the NCPS system.

The UK based organizations, namely the Environment Agency, the British Red Cross and the Royal Navy Lifeboat Institute, try to involve citizens in the preparation of potential emergency incidents, such as flooding, either by asking them to volunteer in various positions within their organizations or by facilitating the communication between them and the voluntary organizations or local authorities and communities that may exist in their local area.

The Environment Agency is a government organization whose contribution to raising public awareness of the risks of flooding is threefold. In Wales, they train and protect staff and pupils from flooding by creating flood plans for schools that are most often hit by floods.

They also participate in the Flood Awareness Wales programme, whose aim is to ensure that communities at risk of flooding know how to prepare and how to respond during a flood incident. They work with individuals, businesses, schools, farms and whole communities to raise awareness of flood risk and help people take actions to prepare for such an incident. Finally, the agency also launches Flood Awareness Campaigns, which are four week communication campaigns to raise awareness about flooding. The Agency also utilizes Flood Plan Leads, who are volunteers acting as a communication link between the community and Environment Agency before, during and after a flood.

The Agency hosts a number of helpful documents on its website regarding flood preparedness in an effort to assist citizens in preparing for flooding. First of all, it provides flood plans templates for businesses, schools, homes and other facilities so that each person can tailor his/her plan according to their needs. There is also a document on Flood Plan Leads and their role before, during and after a flood. Finally, information is provided on a Flood kit that should be present at every home that faces the threat of flooding.

Since the Agency is a government organization it does not recruit volunteers as the other two organizations do, but they facilitate the communication between citizens and local authorities or agencies by posting volunteer vacancies on their website so that everyone who wants to volunteer and help the community can easily do so.

Lastly, the Environment Agency utilizes social media almost solely to inform citizens of imminent storms and floods and of their own rescue operations and to the best of the partners' knowledge it does not provide information on possible volunteering opportunities.

The British Red Cross is a voluntary emergency response charity having around 3,500 staff and 32,500 volunteers. During their research, partners could not find information on the exact training procedure that the newly accepted volunteers go through. On the other hand, training courses do exist for members of the public who may want to be trained on providing first aid to their family or colleagues during or after an emergency event has occurred. The educational material for those courses were also difficult to locate and the only training resources that were found were limited to content on the BRC's website and YouTube channel where BRC provides practical lessons mostly of providing first aid to fellow citizens.

BRC mostly use their website to recruit new volunteers. They provide a volunteer's handbook and a list of all the necessary steps that a potential volunteer must take in order to become a member of the BRC. A database with all available openings is also available on the website, so that citizens can apply to one that suits their skills and background knowledge.

BRC's most widespread means of communication with the public, apart from its website, are its social media accounts. BRC's Facebook, Twitter and YouTube accounts are regularly updated with information on their recent rescue operations, first aid training and warnings of imminent crises.

The Royal National Lifeboat Institution is a voluntary charity registered in England and Wales. A specialized team within the institution, namely the Flood Rescue Team, responds to search and rescue operations during severe flooding. RNLI's volunteers undergo four kinds of high quality training. These are operational training, lifeboat crew training, technical training courses and mobile training units. The Flood Rescue Team's training in particular focuses on working safely and effectively in the unfamiliar terrain and diverse, high-risk environment of flood-affected areas. They are also given additional training to become Floodwater Rescue Technicians and Flood Water Rescue Boat Operators. The RNLI does not have any

educational material on their website or social media accounts which could offer significant advantage to civilians when dealing with a crisis such as a flood. They do however provide leaflets for other types of hazards that may arise during activities like kayaking and surfing.

On their website, RNLI have dedicated a separate section to volunteering where potential volunteers can locate information on ways they can get involved. They are also offered a list of current vacancies so that they can apply for the position that interests them the most as well as the one that is closest to their homes.

Finally, RNLI tries to disseminate information on its operations and volunteering opportunities for citizens mainly through its social media accounts. Text, photos and videos are regularly uploaded to inform citizens and potential volunteers of fundraising events and opportunities, recruitment call outs and information on both recent and older operations.

In Greece, the focus was on two organizations, the Organization for the Anti-Seismic Design and Protection (OASP), which is supervised by the Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks and the non-profit Hellenic Rescue Team (HRT) organization, in order to provide some insight as to how these two organizations approach and inform citizens in matters of emergency preparedness.

In the case of OASP, raising public awareness is a threefold procedure. OASP organizes a volunteering programme, where citizens are trained in matters of crisis management in order to provide aid to their fellow citizens during or after a crisis. OASP also participates in various research projects, such as FP7 and other European funded projects which incorporate tasks such as educating and training citizens when dealing with certain crises. Finally, OASP also cooperates with other Greek bodies to promote preparedness and awareness among citizens.

OASP provides educational material mostly through its website where citizens may find a variety of brochures, books and PowerPoint presentations relating but not limited to security before, during and after an emergency event such as an earthquake.

As far as the recruitment of new members is concerned, since OASP is a government organization, it consists of government personnel. Nevertheless, as was mentioned earlier in the chapter, OASP participates and promotes a national volunteering programme in which citizens can be trained to deal with the impacts of certain crises such as earthquakes.

Finally, in order to inform the public of important events and actions performed, OASP utilizes traditional means of communication such as the television, the radio and its website. Sadly, OASP has yet to be involved with social media meaning that a large portion of the population, mostly of younger age, does not have the opportunity to stay informed on important safety topics.

HRT on the other hand tries to raise public awareness by regularly visiting schools, various types of organizations and companies in order to educate them regarding the right ways of preparing for a possible earthquake, but also to instil the right mentality and noteworthy actions that should be performed during or after an earthquake. Since HRT has a more hands-on approach in raising awareness, it is easier to disseminate educational material, such as leaflet and brochures, in person. Nevertheless, HRT's website also provides information on how citizens can protect themselves before, during and after an earthquake.

Regarding the recruitment of new members, HRT broadcasts registration invitations to citizens throughout the year on every possible media outlet, either traditional such as the television and radio or through its social media accounts, which get updated regularly with content relating to new events, such as workshops and seminars that take place all over Greece, or information on the location of HRT premises so that citizens who would like to volunteer can visit.

Finally, unlike OASP, HRT utilizes social media, such as Facebook and Twitter, for reasons such as to inform the public about events, such as seminars and workshops, to issue recruitment invitations and to disseminate information on its current search and rescue missions.

Chapter 3: Citizens as Social Activists

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3 CITIZENS AS SOCIAL ACTIVISTS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter of the report focuses on social activists and examines how they organize, engage, communicate and collaborate and how they utilize various new media tools for these purposes. In this context, the first section summarizes the main characteristics of an activist networks. This section also analyzes the implications of these characteristics by using examples from recent events.

The second section constructs a typology of activist formations according to their organizational logic. The typology is based on three axes: “looseness”, “ecology of presence” and “objective of presence”.

The third section looks at the repertoire of actions activists take. First, types of offline actions and online actions are summarized and then the section discusses the prominent characteristics of how these actions are executed today.

In the fourth section, the report will use examples from recent protests to discuss how mass media and new media technologies are utilized by activists. This part examines the ways in which new media constitute an important alternative space to mass media for sharing and producing information, particularly in authoritarian regimes.

The last section examines the types of communicative activities that are significant to activists. It discusses how they take decisions, mobilize and operate, practice counter-surveillance activities and build global awareness.

3.2 CHARACTERISTICS OF NETWORK FORMATIONS

In 1999, thousands of people participated in the anti-globalization protests organized during the World Trade Organization Ministerial Conference in Seattle, marking a key moment in the growth of anti-corporate globalization movement. With the advances in information and communication technologies, activists from various political backgrounds were able to network and organize the famous transnational protest of Seattle with great speed and flexibility.

There had been other transnational grassroots protests before, such as the protests during the Earth Summit in Rio (1992) or the international support for the uprising of Zapatistas in Chiapas in late 1990's; however, Seattle was the most apparent to date in terms of revealing the potential of the Internet and mobile technologies in facilitating the formation of activist networks. Naomi Klein described the protests as follows: "What emerged on the streets of Seattle and Washington was an activist model that mirrors the organic, decentralized, interlinked pathways of the Internet—the Internet came to life."¹⁶⁷

The Seattle protests were coordinated through existing global networks. One of those networks was People's Global Action (PGA). PGA's importance stems from the fact that its organizational principles notably reveal the characteristics of networks underlying contemporary activism. PGA was initially formed during the transnational meeting organized by Zapatista Army of National Liberation and officially launched in 1998 in a meeting held in Geneva.¹⁶⁸ PGA's main objective was to contribute to communication and coordination among activist groups, provide support¹⁶⁹ and organize Global Action Days of resistance around the world. PGA had dissolved in time; however, the principles embodied by PGA represent the formational characteristics of activist networks today.¹⁷⁰ They rely on the Internet as the primary medium for communicating and coordinating globally.¹⁷¹ They emphasize heterogeneous, decentralised and autonomous formations, "rejecting all forms of domination."¹⁷²

It is important to note that contemporary activism scene is a highly complex one and network organizations are manifold. Yet, the de-centred networking logic is inherent,¹⁷³ opposing the vertical structures. Networking logic is highly shaped by Internet. Internet does not only provide the infrastructure for networking by enhancing communication, speed and extent of information flows "transcending the geographical and temporal barriers"¹⁷⁴, but it also largely influences it.¹⁷⁵ This networking logic of the Internet, which is decentralized, adaptable,

¹⁶⁷ Klein, Naomi, "The Vision Thing", *The Nation*, 10 July 2000,

<http://www.thenation.com/article/vision-thing?page=0.0>

¹⁶⁸ Routledge, Paul, "Convergence Space: Process Geographies Globalization Networks of Grassroots", *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, Vol. 28, No.3, 2013, pp. 333-49.

¹⁶⁹ Ibid.

¹⁷⁰ Juris, Jeffrey Scott, "The New Digital Media and Activist Networking Within Anti-Corporate Globalization Movements," *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, Vol. 597, No. 1, 2005a, pp. 189-208, p. 198.

¹⁷¹ Routledge, 2013, p. 339.

¹⁷² Ibid., p. 344.

¹⁷³ Juris, Jeffrey Scott "The Networked Social Movements: Global Movements for Global Justice", *The Network Society*, in Manuel Castells (ed.), *The Network Society: A Cross-Cultural Perspective*, Edward Elgar Publications, 2005b, pp. 341-361.

¹⁷⁴ Donk, Wim van de, Loader, Brian D., Nixon, Paul G. and Rucht, Dieter, "Introduction Social movements and ICT's", in Wim van de Donk (Editor), Brian D. Loader, Paul G. Nixon and Dieter Rucht (eds.), *Cyberprotest: New Media, Citizens and Social Movement*, Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2005, pp.1-23, p.18.

¹⁷⁵ Juris, 2005, p. 349

flexible, self-directed and horizontal, shapes the practices produced by contemporary social activists. As Manuel Castells argues, contemporary social activism in the network society entails:

1. building horizontal ties and connections among diverse, autonomous elements;
2. the free and open circulation of information;
3. collaboration through decentralized coordination and directly democratic decision-making; and
4. self-directed or self-managed networking.¹⁷⁶

Sample Organizational Principles of PGA

- The PGA is an instrument for coordination, not an organisation. Its main objectives are:
 - Inspiring the greatest possible number of persons and organisations to act against corporate domination through civil disobedience and people-oriented constructive actions.
 - Offering an instrument for coordination and mutual support at global level for those resisting corporate rule and the capitalist development paradigm.
 - Giving more international projection to the struggles against economic liberalisation and global capitalism, as well as to the struggles of indigenous people and original cultures.
- The organisational philosophy of the PGA is based on decentralisation and autonomy. Hence, central structures are minimal.
- The PGA has no membership.
- The PGA is an instrument for coordination, it is not an organisation.

In keeping with PGA's philosophy, all communication processes will be diverse, decentralised and coordinated.¹⁷⁷

On the next section of this chapter, we discuss the main characteristics of contemporary activism which are grounded on the networking logic.

3.2.1 Glocalization

The first one is glocalization, referring to the combination of idea of globalization with local concerns. Even if the activist group is dedicated to a very local cause, the organizational components and logic of the group are no longer tied to a particular time or geographical location: "Using the Internet as technological infrastructure, such movements are increasingly 'glocal,' operating at both local and global levels, while seamlessly integrating both online and off-line political activity."¹⁷⁸

By using network technologies, activists share information real-time while they coordinate and collaborate at a transnational level with different individuals and/or groups around the world. Getting in contact with other activists around the world working for mutual causes and

¹⁷⁶ Castells, Manuel, *The Internet Galaxy: Reflections on the Internet, Business, and Society*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001, p. 55.

¹⁷⁷ "Organizational Principles", *People's Global Action (PGA)*, no date., <http://www.nadir.org/nadir/initiativ/agp/cocha/principles.htm>

¹⁷⁸ Juris, 2005b, p. 347.

building networks with them has become an essential activity.¹⁷⁹ They coordinate globally and protest for the same reasons.¹⁸⁰ Perhaps, the most significant aspect of the glocal nature of contemporary social activism is that most of the activists consider themselves as part of a global movement even when they are protesting in the name of local issues. For contemporary activists, the well-known adage “Think globally, act locally” describes a common understanding.

3.2.2 Participatory politics and horizontal organization structures

Another characteristic of activist networks is how highly they value attributes of participatory democracy, horizontal connectedness and decentralization. As Jeffrey S. Juris puts it:

Network-based forms of political organization and practice based on non-hierarchical structures, horizontal coordination among autonomous groups, open access, direct participation, consensus-based decision-making, and the ideal of the free and open circulation of information.¹⁸¹

This is what many activists from 15M Movement in Barcelona call “the new way of doing politics”¹⁸² and also what some activists claim as “Politics 2.0 (open-source politics)”¹⁸³ for these attributes are highly associated with rise of new Information Communication Technologies (ICT's) and new media.¹⁸⁴ We will look closely into this relation between new media and today's activist movement in the forthcoming sections of this chapter.

The idea of participatory politics was one of the key concepts in the Occupy Wall Street (OWS) movement during which public spaces were utilized as spaces for gathering. These gatherings were called assemblies. In assemblies, each participant was to have an equal voice. Principles of direct democracy were applied and in most cases, each decision required unanimous consent of the participants. David Graeber, a widely known figure in OWS, summarizes the decision making as “... no formal leadership structure that could be co-opted or coerced; ... no majority could bend a minority to its will, but that all crucial decisions had to be made by general consent.”¹⁸⁵

Open participation and non-hierarchical structure of assemblies/forums challenge representative democracy and traditional methods of organizing. Assemblies/forums as experimental spaces for face-to-face dialogue and decision-making were embraced in many other protests before and after WTO. One of the most recent one is Gezi Park Protests in Istanbul, Turkey (Summer 2013) during (and after) which groups of activists gathered in parks in various parts of the city and organized forums where they shared their experiences, ideas and elaborated on the sustainability of the movement. The last section of this chapter will discuss the decision making processes in assemblies in more detail.

¹⁷⁹ Routledge, 2013, p.335.

¹⁸⁰ Laer, Jeroen Van and Aelst, Peter Van, *Cyber-Protest and Civil Society: the Internet and Action Repertoires of Social Movements*. *Information, Communication & Society*, pp.1–26.

¹⁸¹ Juris, 2005b, p.351

¹⁸² Juris, 2005a, p. 198.

¹⁸³ “Crashing the System”, *Mother Jones*, 19 June 2007, <http://www.motherjones.com/politics/2007/06/crashing-system?page=2>

¹⁸⁴ Garrett, R. Kelly, “Protest in an Information Society: A Review of Literature on Social Movements and New ICTs”, *Information, Communication and Society*, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp. 202-224.

¹⁸⁵ Graeber, David, “Occupy Wall Street's Anarchist Roots”, *Aljazeera*, 30 November 2011, <http://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/2011/11/2011112872835904508.html>

3.2.3 Autonomous flexibility

The autonomous character of activist networks is related to the aforementioned participatory nature of politics and governance in contemporary social movements. This characteristic has two dimensions. First, autonomy is related to the rejection of the established political arena. In other words, contemporary activism avoids being connected to established political parties and other political forces, such as transnational companies, of contemporary representative democracies. Second, contemporary movements see the idea of self-managed autonomous networks as “organizational bedrocks of autonomous society.”¹⁸⁶

Contrary to traditional political organizations, networks are more inclusive, dynamic, flexible and less bound to physical and spatial conditions. In addition, contemporary activists tend to diffuse into different networks and participate in diverse networks rather than participating in a single network. For example, studies indicate that there is a positive correlation between participation of the individual in multiple organisations and Internet usage.¹⁸⁷ Consequently, the activist individual is no longer bound to a single group. As we have stated before, Internet enhances the networking logic. However, it is important to note that the assumption made here is not that the Internet by some means causes contemporary activists to be more autonomous, more flexible, rely more on participatory democracy. It is rather manifold. Internet can be used in many forms, “from closed and hierarchical to open and broadly distributed. Preferences for the latter pattern reflect the social, personal, and political contexts in which many global activists define their mutual relationships.”¹⁸⁸

By welcoming any person “as long as they agree with the network hallmarks” and via a structure that allows “maximal coordination and communication”¹⁸⁹, autonomous networks with minimal structures and flexible memberships can be more conducive to organization of immediate collective actions. Occupy Sandy is an example of how an activist network can be “far more nimble”¹⁹⁰ compared to traditional ones (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1: A poster by Occupy Sandy accentuates the absence of the government in the relief efforts.

¹⁸⁶ Roos, Jerome, “Autonomy: An Idea Whose Time Has Come”, *Roar*, 23 June 2013.

<http://roarmag.org/2013/06/autonomy-revolution-movements-democracy-capitalism/>

¹⁸⁷ Della Porta, Donatella, and Lorenzo Mosca, “Global-Net for Global Movements? A Network of Networks for a Movement of Movements”, *Journal of Public Policy*, Vol. 25, No. 1, May 2005, pp. 165–190.

¹⁸⁸ Bennett, W. Lance “Communicating Global Activism: Strengths and Vulnerabilities of Networked Politics”, in in Wim van de Donk, Brian D. Loader, Paul G. Nixon and Dieter Rucht (eds.), *Cyberprotest: New media, Citizens and Social Movement*, Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2005, pp. 110-128, p. 111.

¹⁸⁹ Juris, J., 2005, p.197.

¹⁹⁰ Dowson, Ashley, “Occupy Sandy and Emerging Forms of Social Organization”, 11 May 2013, <http://ashleydawson.info/2013/05/11/occupy-sandy-and-emerging-forms-of-social-organization/>

After Hurricane Sandy struck in October 2012, Occupy Wall Street (OWS) participants got together in order to help the local community recover. They build hubs in churches where they offered daily cooked meal for affected community and distributed donated goods.

According to some critics, in contrast to the OWS movement's ability to quickly provide relief to citizens in the wake of the hurricane, the government was slow to act. This was to a part due to the operational procedures that government agencies had to follow, like helping people according to their citizenship status, and, thus, making victims fill long forms. A first responder from Occupy Sandy claimed later that "for a long time they were the only people on the field doing the relief work."¹⁹¹

¹⁹¹ Fauer, Alan. "Occupy Sandy: A Movement Moves to Relief", *New York Times*, 9 November 2012, http://www.nytimes.com/2012/11/11/nyregion/where-fema-fell-short-occupy-sandy-was-there.html?_r=0

3.3 TYPOLOGY OF SOCIAL ACTIVISTS

When we look at contemporary activism, we see a rather complex space involving many actors including individuals from various backgrounds, organizations, and coalitions with different ideologies. Information and communication technologies (ICTs) and new media offer both individuals and organizations the ability to access, communicate and link with each other in real-time, thereby facilitating the formation of diverse and fluid structural relations among different actors.

The scope of this section is to assess activist networks according to their organizational logic, not their ideological framework. In order to do so, we build on the previous disaster organization typology provided in Deliverable D1.1, which categorized organizations as established, extended, expanding and emergent.¹⁹² We base our typology on three axes. The first one is their ecology of offline or online presence. The other dimension pertains to the looseness of the organization—strong vs. weak ties—referring to the extent to which a group tends to stay together, and the last axis is the objective of presence, that is whether they are more ad-hoc based or looking for presence in the representative politics.

In describing this typology, we will start with the assumption that individual activists constitute a potential network and hence regard them as one of the main categories who are situated at the centre of the axes.

3.3.1 Individuals

Influenced by the network logic, the individual activist is the smallest potential component of a network involved in practices of gathering information, interpreting and disseminating information to other people. New media such as blogging, live video streaming, instant messaging, micro blogging and other social networks is making instantaneous networking, real-time communication and coordination possible.

Even the individual activist has the potential to initiate a protest or an online organization in what Manuel Castells labelled as “self-directed networking.” The concept refers to “the capacity for anyone to find his or her own destination on the Net, and, if not found, to create and post his or her own information, thus inducing a network.”¹⁹³ The ability of the individual to constitute political forms through networks or even start a network “contrast with the ‘modernist’ tendency to forge social and political order through mutual identifications with leaders, ideologies and memberships in conventional social and political groups.”¹⁹⁴ As Bennett and Segerberg argue, this “also creates the potential for personal networks to play a more prominent role in a protest.”¹⁹⁵

Such was the case with the Voter March, an online organization, which was started in 2000 by four founding members from Washington D.C. and New York, “who wanted to express their opposition to the irregularities and egregious conduct of Election 2000 and the direction in

¹⁹² Watson, Hayley et al., “Deliverable D1.1: Report on security crises with high societal impact”, *COSMIC*, 2013.

¹⁹³ Castells, Manuel, *The Internet Galaxy: Reflections on the Internet, Business, and Society*, Oxford University Press, 2001, p.55.

¹⁹⁴ Bennett, W. L., 2005, p.112.

¹⁹⁵ Bennett, W. Lance and Alexandra Segerberg, “Digital Media and the Personalization of the Collective Action”, *Information, Communication & Society*, Vol. 14, No. 6, 2011, pp. 770-799, p. 772

which an illegitimate administration was taking the country.”¹⁹⁶ Voter March is one of the early examples of Internet based activist community using a blog, Google groups and Twitter to organize its activities going back and forth between online and offline domains. They have organized several nationwide protests calling for an election reform. Now they have an online community of 10,000 activists from 50 states.

3.3.2 Network-based organizational forms

A network is typically defined as a set of identified nodes linked by specific ties, in a context delimited by particular boundaries. Nodes can consist of individuals, organizations or any kind of social agency.

Networking logic and its distinctive aspects like being de-centred, horizontal and flexible reproduce itself in activist practice and affects the formations of organizations. In other words, network-based organizations are groups of individuals who coordinate, share information, and organize action for a common cause. Networks usually emerge during times when a movement is mobilized to provide information, call for action and provide the space for real-time decision-making. As they are formed by individual initiatives, they may later continue to exist, overlap with other movements, become idle, and cease to exist as a movement or go into transformation in short amounts of time. As a movement, networks “may quickly change their forms, strategy, tactics and even some of its goals.”¹⁹⁷ As we mentioned before, Occupy Sandy is an example for transformation of Occupy Wall Street Movement into a relief effort. One of the activists who initiated the effort, describes Occupy Sandy as the “‘third phase’ of the Occupy Wall Street movement”¹⁹⁸

3.3.2.1 Online umbrella hubs

New media facilitate quick formation of linkages, enabling new actors to appear and evolve into central organizing hubs for various players.¹⁹⁹ These hubs, which can be called as “online umbrella hubs” are online platforms where diversified organizations, groups and individuals meet without losing their autonomy.²⁰⁰ They usually appear in social media but evolve into both online and offline converging centres for movements.

The objective of online umbrella hubs is mostly to expand the network and establish connectivity between different networks. They also act as platforms where globally concurrent protests are coordinated. The study done by Smith, Peter J. and Elizabeth Smythe on online umbrella hubs demonstrates how these hubs were linked to other organization sites the Seattle protests: “the official WTO site was the link leader (2129 recorded links), followed by several protest hubs with impressive network links: One World (348); Institute for Global Communications (111), Seattlewto.org, the sponsored site of the NGO coalition (92); and Corporate Watch (74)”²⁰¹

¹⁹⁶ “About Voter March”, n.d. <http://votermarch.blogspot.com/p/about-voter-march.html>

¹⁹⁷ Donk et al., 2005, p.2.

¹⁹⁸ Bush, Liam Barrington “Occupy Sandy: Horizontal lessons in community-based disaster recovery”, 20 June 2013, <http://rabble.ca/news/2013/06/occupy-sandy-horizontal-lessons-community-based-disaster-recovery>

¹⁹⁹ Bennett, W. L., 2005.

²⁰⁰ Juris, 2005b, p.351.

²⁰¹ Bennett, 2005, p.124.

3.3.2.2 Affinity groups

An affinity group is a smaller group of people who share common perspectives with equal voice. Some affinity networks may be loose in form and exist only during a particular protest; others may last working together for years. They can exist as a part of or independent from larger movements. They are also ad-hoc, more task based in that they are usually gathered together to achieve a certain objective.²⁰²

3.3.2.3 Hacktivist groups

Hacktivist groups consist of activists who enact hacking for political change. Hacktivist actions can be regarded as illegal or legal depending on the type of action and the legal system. Hence anonymity of the activist is a requisite in the case of hacktivist groups and that tends to make the hacktivist groups more tight-knit. However, they are the groups who inherently embrace the networking logic and its ensuing weak ties. Thus, hacktivist groups tend to develop strong ties among main members and weak ties with volunteers.²⁰³

It can be argued that hacktivist groups have become one of the crucial aspects of social movements. They are increasingly seen as the leading images of social activism. Their potential ability to cause the collapse a whole network symbolizes a threat to the existing system. The hacktivist group, Anonymous was notably notorious during Occupy Wall Street. They made series of videos to support OWS. The intimidating tone in the videos reveals the threat they represent. Below is an excerpt from one of their videos, which was banned from YouTube for “promoting hate speech”, because it was exposing the officer attacked the activists.

An Excerpt from a video by Anonymous, during OWS

“If we hear of brutality in the next 36 hours then we will take you down from the Internet as you have taken the protesters' voices from the airwaves.”
 “When we say something, we will do it.”²⁰⁴

3.3.2.4 Network parties

The idea of networking inevitably has effects on representational politics arena. Existing political parties are becoming increasingly more aware of the power of social media and they are trying to adopt by having social media presence and making campaigns online. They are using Facebook as an additional outlet to acquire supporters, release propaganda etc. For example, more than 50% of the representatives in the Turkish Parliament now have a Twitter page through which they declare their thoughts and make announcements. Likewise, the Democratic Party in the U.S. can be regarded as a successful example in terms of adeptness in using social networking. MoveOn.org, a website owned by Democratic Party, “acts more as an interest organization, mobilizing pressure on specific issues moving through legislative processes.”²⁰⁵ It has more than 8 million members, which is a considerable size for a network.

²⁰² Anton, Anatole and Richard Schmitt, *Toward a New Socialism*. Lanham, MD: Lexington Books, 2007, p. 445.

²⁰³ Cammaerts, Bart, “Networked Resistance: The Case of WikiLeaks”, *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, Vol. 18, No. 1, 2013, pp. 420–36.

²⁰⁴ “Anonymous Warning to NYPD”, 29 September 2011, <http://theanonmessage.blogspot.com/2011/09/youtube-bans.html>

²⁰⁵ Bennett, W. Lance. “Changing Citizenship in the Digital Age.” W. Lance Bennett. The John D. and Catherine T. MacArthur (eds.), *Civic Life Online: Learning How Digital Media Can Engage Youth*, Foundation Series on Digital Media and Learning. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press, 2008, pp. 1–24, p. 10.

Here we use the phrase “network party” to refer to new parties emerging as political actors that run in the elections. As we have argued, most of the major political parties now have social media presence to recruit and mobilize supporters.²⁰⁶ However, network parties are the ones developed in the last ten years inherently carrying the dynamics of networking such as the Pirate Party (Germany) and the Movimento 5 Stelle (Italy). They are challenging the conventions in representational politics arena in ways that was difficult to imagine 10 years ago.²⁰⁷

Movimento 5 Stelle (M5S - 5 Star Movement) in Italy introduced a new outset in the party political system. Beppe Grillo, who is a popular comedian in Italy, published a blog in 2005. Through this blog he started organizing offline meetings all around the country focused on political and societal problems. In 2007 and 2008, he led events called V-days during which the movement became known by larger audience and gained acceleration.²⁰⁸ In the 2013 general election, the M5S won the 25.6% of the votes. In many respects, M5S is the epitome of a new type of political party. Since the early days of the party, Internet has been the one of the primary venues through which M5S organized. Indeed, as mentioned earlier, the party originated from a blog and extended and organized through social media. The party still proclaims to be “firmly attached to Internet and its culture.”²⁰⁹

3.3.2.5 Established organizations

By established organization we refer to any political group like unions and political parties which require more conventional means of membership and are typically organized around a more central governance system. As we have argued before, contemporary activist networks are rather loose, decentralized, horizontal and active participation is encouraged.²¹⁰ However, established organizations continue to be important players in the activism scene today.

Such organizations have been actively adapting new media into their existing communication networks.²¹¹ “Open source unionism” is an example of such endeavour. For example, as companies get more global, this caused also the workers of the same company to be geographically spread. Hence the traditional unionism which depends on face-to face communication is forced to utilize new media like chat rooms, websites and adopt more fluid memberships. Alliance@IBM is a successful example of open source unionism started in 1999 which has members from Germany, Italy, Japan, Canada and Australia.²¹²

3.4 REPERTOIRE OF ACTIONS BY SOCIAL ACTIVISTS

Activists take varieties of actions usually going against the accustomed routine of everyday life. Although various categorisations of activist actions can be made based on their

²⁰⁶ Bartlett, Jamie; Froio, Caterina, Litter; Mark, McDonnell, D., “*Social Media is changing politics across Europe...*’ *New Political Actors in Europe: Beppe Grillo and the M5S*”, Demos, London, 2013.

²⁰⁷ Ibid. p.11

²⁰⁸ Ibid.

²⁰⁹ Hopper, John, “Beppe Grillo's Five Star Movement Becomes Italy's Election Success Story”, *The Guardian*, 25 February 2013, <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/feb/25/beppe-grillo-italy-election-success>

²¹⁰ Juris, 2005a, p. 198.

²¹¹ Ibid., p. 198.

²¹² Bimber, Bruce; Flanagan, Andrew J. and Cynthia Stohl, “Reconceptualizing Collective Action in the Contemporary Media Environment”, *Communication Theory*, Vol. 15, No. 4, 2005, pp. 365–88, p. 378.

distinctive characters, the following categorization made by Postmes and Brunsting²¹³ is the most relevant one for the purpose of this report because it has the potential inclusiveness to accomodate possible activist actions emerging with new media.

Figure 3.2: Map of Social Activist Actions²¹⁴

According to Postmes and Brunsting, actions can be mapped in two axes. One dimension distinguishes between *collectivistic* and *individualistic* action, a distinction based on the amount of participation an action requires. The second dimension uses a continuum ranging from *persuasive* on the one end and *confrontational* on the other to categorize actions in terms of their nature.

In this section of the chapter we will focus on various forms of action. First we are going to give examples to different types of “offline” actions and describe how offline action has evolved recently. Then we will focus on online forms and try to illustrate the most recent ones with examples. In doing so, we will try to position each into the Postmes and Brunsting model.

3.4.1 Offline action

Many different forms of action, such as boycotts, strikes, street demonstrations, sit-ins and hunger strikes have frequently been used offline by activists. These can be considered as more

²¹³ Postmes, Tom and Suzanne Brunsting, “Collective Action in the Age of the Internet”, *Social Science Computer Review Fall*, Vol. 20, No. 3, 2002, pp. 290–301.

²⁴ Ibid.

traditional methods of activism which had been practiced in modern societies and we are acquainted to see them today.

3.4.1.1 Demonstrations

According to the Oxford Dictionary “demonstration” means “a public meeting or march protesting against something or expressing views on a political issue.”²¹⁵ There are different types of demonstrations such as marches, sit-ins, rallies, nudity which are mostly categorized as “collectivistic”, but sometimes they can evolve into being “confrontational”.

3.4.1.2 Strikes

Strikes are sometimes part of a bigger campaign to force the government to change the existing policies. Then they are called “general strike” involving the participation of workers from different workplaces. As Postmes and Brunsting suggested in their model, strikes are “collectivistic” and “confrontational” at the same time.

3.4.1.3 Hunger strikes

Hunger strikes are a type of activism that are usually carried out by the most vulnerable or marginalized part of the public like prisoners who are usually not acknowledged by mass media. Hunger strikes are usually terminated by force-feeding the participant. Hunger strike is a rather “persuasive” kind of activism.

3.4.1.4 Occupation

Occupation is taking over a space. Occupation of a public square has become a prevalent type of action used by contemporary activists. Occupation of a public square symbolizes challenging state authority and reclaiming the power of the public. As such occupations become a means of resistance against the regulative power of the state dictating where and how individuals situated in urban space.^{216, 217} As a form of action, occupations offer many positive effects for the movements. Tent cities have become spaces where “forms of self-management and solidarity” are experimented.²¹⁸ Activists have exercised participatory democracy in which anyone can make a proposal, participate and be a part of decision making. Also, occupations can often help enhance networking, strengthening previously established online networks, and their ability to collaborate, share and do planning. Occupations can also make movements more visible in the mass media and can become a venue within which movements can get in contact with the interested public members.²¹⁹

In these respects, occupations are “collectivistic” and “persuasive” kinds of action. However, as recent political crises in Turkey (June 2013) and Ukraine (December 2013) suggest, because of the advantages for activists (and relatedly its disruptiveness) and connotations of occupying public space that were mentioned above, state authorities won't let the activists

²¹⁵ Definition of Demonstration in English, *Oxford Dictionary*, no date, <http://www.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/demonstration>

²¹⁶ Juris, Jeffrey Scott, “Reflections on #Occupy Everywhere: Social Media, Public Space, and Emerging Logics of Aggregation,” *American Ethnologist*, Vol. 39, No. 2, May 8, 2012, pp. 259–79, p.268

²¹⁷ Lynch, Marc, “After Egypt: The Limits and Promise of Online Challenges to the Authoritarian Arab State”, *Perspectives on Politics*, Vol. 2, No. 2, 2011, pp. 301-10, p. 306.

²¹⁸ Castells, Manuel, *Networks of Outrage and Hope*, Polity Press, Cambridge, 2012, p. 59.

²¹⁹ Juris, 2012, p.268.

occupy for long periods of time, this causing frequent clashes between activists and security forces.

3.4.2 Online actions

In this section we are going to review the types of activist actions that are typically performed online. Internet has had a profound effect on collective actions by enabling different forms of actions to emerge and other existing forms of actions to strengthen.²²⁰ Hence some of the actions described below are merely adaptation of existing repertoire of actions, meaning they are not utterly new but modification of a familiar one. Such is the case for online petitions, which are not necessarily effective but are widely used because rather it is familiar type of action.²²¹

3.4.2.1 Online petitions

According to a study done by Della Porta and Mosca, online petitioning is one of the most widely known and widespread form of action among activists.²²² Online petitioning is signing a pre-created online form in order to support a cause by entering information such as name, surname and email. It is widely practiced via platforms like change.org and avaaz.org. Signing an online petition is so easy that it is criticized for slacktivism - meaning that it has not any particular effect on the cause, it just makes the individuals feel good about themselves for having contributed. Online petitioning, like the traditional petitioning, is “collective” and “persuasive” activist action.

3.4.2.2 Online strikes

An online strike is blacking out and replacing the content on the main page of a website to protest for a cause. SOPA Strike is an influential example of online strikes. On January 18, 2012 of the largest online protest was initiated against two proposed Internet-related laws in US; the Stop Online Piracy Act (SOPA) and Protect IP Act (PIPA) which were essentially criticized for posing potential threats to freedom of speech. Series of actions were taken in order to stop the legislative process. Over 115.000 websites including some of the large web companies and organizations such as Google, Yahoo and Wikipedia joined the strike. For example Google put a black box over the logo on the search page with a link to the SOPA petition page.²²³ Online strike is “collectivistic” and “persuasive”.

3.4.2.3 Hacktivism

Hacktivism is politically mediated hacking indicating the use of hacking for political purposes and not personal ones. Hacktivism includes actions like information release, virtual sit-ins, doxing and website defacement. Omega, a member of the hacking group, Cult of the Dead Cow, is the first one to coin the word “hacktivism.” One of the first popular hacktivist groups is Electronic Disturbance Theatre (EDT) which was established in 1997. They are known for

²²⁰ Postmes and Brunsting, 2002, p.294.

²²¹ Rolfe, B., “Building an Electronic Repertoire of Contention”, *Social Movement Studies*, Vo. 4, No.1, 2005, pp. 65-74, p. 67.

²²² Della Porta, Donatella, and Lorenzo Mosca, “Global-Net for Global Movements? A Network of Networks for a Movement of Movements,” *Journal of Public Policy*, Vol. 25, 2005, pp. 165–90.

²²³ McCullagh, Declan, “How SOPA would affect you: FAQ”, *CNET*, 18 January 2012, http://news.cnet.com/8301-31921_3-57329001-281/how-sopa-would-affect-you-faq/?tag=TOCmoreStories.0

initiating virtual sit-ins on websites like Pentagon site.²²⁴ Hacktivist action might be labelled as 'civil disobedience' or as 'cyber terrorism' depending on the action taken and the perspective. Hacktivist actions are more aligned with civil disobedience actions hence they aim interruption in the system rather than destruction.²²⁵ And depending on the number of people joining in, hactivism might be collectivistic or individualistic. The types of hacktivist actions are as follows:

Information release: One of the most widely known slogans of hacktivism is "Information wants to be free." The phrase belongs to Steward Brand in late 1960's. He used it in the more economical context that information should be cheap and available for everyone. Hacktivists use it more politically to refer to how technology can be used to liberate people.

Wikileaks is one of the most commonly known examples to contemporary hacktivist groups which work on liberating information and communication.²²⁶ They publish confidential information. They are known for breaking important stories on war crimes, torture, corruption, counter-intelligence and etc. They are criticized for not releasing all the documents in their database at once, but doing it partially. Although Wikileaks itself is not known for getting into hacking practices to obtain information, they work in close contact with famous hacktivist groups. For example Jeremy Hammond, a hacktivist from Anonymous, was sentenced to 10 years for hacking Stratfor (a global intelligence company). He leaked millions of emails to Wikileaks.²²⁷

Virtual sit-in/DDOS: A virtual sit-in is making the website unavailable by making it work slowly or crash totally. Most common way involves accessing the website at the same and repetitively which causes server overload and the website can no longer respond to its intended users.

In 2010, the hacktivist network Anonymous attacked the websites of Visa, MasterCard and Paypal and caused the websites to slow down. This attack, called Operation Payback, was in response to these companies freezing the accounts of Wikileaks. Approximately 6.000 people joined the attack.

Doxing: Doxing is finding and releasing personal information on targeted person or group. Anonymous and Redhack, a Turkish hacktivist group, revealed several times the names of polices who used violence on the protesters. Redhack also published personal phone numbers of parliamentarians as a reaction to police attacks on protesters during the Occupy Gezi protests in Turkey in 2013.

Website defacement: Website defacement is replacing the main page of the targeted website with a different content usually containing a political message. Government websites are regularly defaced by activists to reveal the impotency of the system. For example, Syrian Electronic Army (SEA), group of hackers who are known for supporting the government of

²²⁴ Laer, Jeroen Van, and Peter Van Aelst, "Cyber-Protest and Civil Society: the Internet and Action Repertoires in Social Movements", in Yvonne Jewkes and Majid Yar (eds.), *Handbook on Internet Crime*, Abingdon, UK: Willan Publishing, 2009, pp. 230–54.

²²⁵ Cammaerts, Bart, "Networked Resistance: The Case of WikiLeaks," *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, Vol. 18, No. 1, 2013, pp. 420–4-36, p. 421.

²²⁶ Ibid.

²²⁷ Pikington, Ed, "Jailed Anonymous hacker Jeremy Hammond: 'My days of hacking are done'", *Guardian*, 15 November 2013, <http://www.theguardian.com/technology/2013/nov/15/jeremy-hammond-anonymous-hacker-sentenced>

Bashar al-Assad in Syria, recently defaced US president Barack Obama Facebook and Twitter accounts to redirect to a video they were trying to promote.

3.4.2.4 Internet-supported action

So far, this section has divided activist actions as offline or online; however many actions that can be categorized as offline because they are carried out in the physical/corporal domains, increasingly have their roots on online networks. Internet is used for disseminating information, organising, mobilising mass transnational demonstrations.²²⁸ Van Laer gives the example of the peace demonstration against the war in Iraq in February 13, 2003 which took millions of protesters out to the streets in 60 different countries. He claims that it wouldn't have been as massive as it was if the Internet was not utilized.²²⁹ We will discuss in further detail the opportunities presented by new media technologies in the subsequent sections of this chapter.

3.4.3 Prominent characteristics of contemporary activist actions

An important goal for contemporary activism is becoming more visible in media. Being theatrical and creative in taking action are what we might call “tactics” for getting standing in media (including mass media), with the hope that the coverage will lead to higher public attention (and support). To some extent, this explains how recent protests have transformed into powerful image events.²³⁰ Networking allows activists to share their actions almost instantly and these actions, especially the creative ones, are reproduced independent of the national boundaries. We are going to look deeper into these aspects and try to illustrate them with examples.

3.4.3.1 Theatricality

There is a perpetual adaptation of theatrical forms in contemporary activism. They “produce highly visible, theatrical images for mass-mediated consumption, including: giant puppets and street theatre, mobile street carnivals and etc.”²³¹

The widespread use of Guy Fawkes masks is an example to diffusion of theatrical forms in activism. Guy Fawkes was an anarchist who planned to blow up the British parliament in 1605 and the mask symbolises rebellion against the state. The mask became a symbol for the hacktivist group, Anonymous and was frequently used by activists in Occupy Movement and other social movements. Also it has a very practical function. It protects the anonymity of the activist as it conceals the face.

“Duran Adam” (Standing Man) is a more unique individualistic civil disobedience enacted during Occupy Gezi protests in Turkey. After a weekend of overly harsh attacks by the police, on June 17, 2013, a man, who was later identified as Erdem Gündüz (who turned out to be a dancer and a choreographer), started standing on the main square, right adjacent to Gezi Park, which was at that time banned for public gatherings. As he stood still for hours, his action

²²⁸ Castells, 2012.

²²⁹ Van Laer, Jeroen, “Activists ‘online’ and ‘offline’: Internet as an Information Channel for Protest Demonstrations”, *Mobilization: An International Journal*, Vol. 15, Issue 3, 2010, pp. 404-18, p. 405.

²³⁰ Juris, Jeffrey Scott and Geoffrey Henri Pleyers, “Alter-activism: Emerging Cultures of Participation Among Young Global Justice Activists”, *Journal of Youth Studies*, Vol. 12, Issue 1, 2009, pp. 57-75,

²³¹ Juris, 2005b, p.346.

spread on Twitter via hashtags, #Duranadam and #standingman.²³² Many other people joined him, standing still on the same square and spread to the other cities. His silence but powerful performance standing against violence became an iconic protest of Gezi Protests (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Erdem Gündüz performing 'Standing Man'²³³

3.4.3.2 Creativity

Tarrow argues that being creative is one of the essential features of activist movements: “They draw people into collective action through known repertoires of contention and by creating innovations around their margins.”²³⁴ Challenging the forms of actions is a way of creating social impact in the public space, and this helps them succeed in reaching critical mass. Thereby, they sustain the necessary friction with the state and other opposition groups.²³⁵

One of the tactics used by contemporary activists is culture jamming. Culture jamming is a way of protesting in which mainstream cultural images belonging to consumerism culture is transformed to make a disruptive effect. Generally culture jamming is associated with altering brand advertisements and using their power of influence against themselves. Here we will look at cultural jamming from a broader perspective, correlate the next example to creative culture jamming.

A political media collective in Barcelona has taken numerous innovative actions. One of their most notorious culture jamming projects is called “YOMANGO” meaning “I steal” started in 2002. It also refers to the Spain-based multinational clothing brand “Mango.” Yomango encourages people to steal from international companies and organizes collective events where shoplifted items are exhibited.²³⁶ Yomango aims to turn shoplifting into an activist

²³²Talbi, Karim, “Turkey's 'Standing Man' Protest By Erdem Gunduz Spreads Across Country”, *Huffington Post*, 18 June 2013,

http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2013/06/18/turkey-standing-man-protest-erdem-gunduz_n_3458390.html

²³³ Doney, V., Photograph, EPA, *The Guardian*, 18 June 2013,

<http://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2013/jun/18/turkey-standing-man>

²³⁴ Tarrow, Sidney, *Power in Movement*, Cambridge U press, 1994, p. 1.

²³⁵ Ibid.

²³⁶ Juris, 2005a.

action against capitalism: “something that has nothing to do with producing a way of life that is dedicated to consumption, but rather moves toward inventing new possible ways of living.”²³⁷ “Yomango-Tango” was an example of Yomango action diffused into other countries. In Argentina, a crowd of dancers took hundreds of bottles of champagnes from Carrefour, the supermarket, and drank them inside a branch of Banco Stander. Both of these brands were associated with the economic crisis in Argentina.²³⁸

During Gezi Protests Turkish police was solemnly criticized for using disproportionate force against protesters, particularly for firing teargas canisters directly at protesters from close range as pointed out by Human Rights Watch.²³⁹ Berkin Elvan, a 14 year old boy, got shot in the head by a tear gas grenade fired by the police during Gezi Park protests and as of this report (January 2014) is still in coma (for more than 200 days). Allegedly, he was shot when he went out for grocery shopping. His not being part of the protests made this particular police attack a moving example of police brutally aiming at people. The images displayed in Figure 3.4 provide examples to culture jamming activities that aimed to raise awareness about the police violence during the protests. On the banknote on the left, it writes to the future bearers of the banknote “You might get shot by the police while you get out with this money to buy bread. Berkin Elvan is still in coma.” On the banknote on the right, it writes “Child, don't go out to buy bread with this money, you'll get shot! #direnberkinelvan .

Figure 3.4: Turkish Lira banknotes with messages protesting police violence during Gezi Protests in Turkey.

²³⁷ “Yomango Fashion Show”, *Actipedia*, 5 July 2002, <http://actipedia.org/project/yomango-fashion-show>

²³⁸ *Ibid.*

²³⁹ “Turkey: End Incorrect, Unlawful Use of Teargas”, *Human Rights Watch*, 17 July 2013, <http://www.hrw.org/news/2013/07/16/turkey-end-incorrect-unlawful-use-teargas>

3.5 USE OF MEDIA BY ACTIVISTS

3.5.1 Mass Media

Although there is a recognisable decline, particularly among youth, in consumption of mass media (see highlights below), mass media still continue to be the dominant venue of communicating to the public.

Media Use Patterns of Youth, Age 18-25²⁴⁰

- Read a daily newspaper (GSS): Down from 44% in 1975 to 19% in 2002, but then back up to 28% in 2004.
- Watch the TV news at least twice a week (NES): down from 79% in 1980 to 44% in 2004.

Particularly in countries like Egypt where illiteracy rate is very high around 30%,²⁴¹ television continues to be the main source for news and control over broadcasting remains to be among the key factors that determine whose voice can be heard by the public. For example, during the first 20 days of the Egyptian Revolution, from 25th January 2011 to Mubarak's resignation, the Egyptian state TV portrayed the thousands of people protesting the regime as a bunch of troublemakers and they disseminated a very different version of what was really happening on the streets. After the military coup, this time state media was in line with the new militaristic governance. On 9 October 2010, when military forces killed dozens of peaceful protesters of Coptic Christian group, the state Radio and TV accused the protesters for attacking the military and called public to protect their military.²⁴² (Figure 3.5)

Figure 3.5: (left) A graffiti about the state's media: "Say no to drugs . . . and to Egyptian Television"²⁴³ (right) Egyptian Armed Forces outside the Egyptian state television and radio building.

At the same time, Al Jazeera's coverage of the protests in Egypt shows the potential that mass media have in terms of diffusing the ideas of a social movement. Al Jazeera is a media network owned by the government of Qatar, which can be watched in various regions in the world. They do programming in English, as well as in Arabic, making the content, potentially, far more reachable for international community. During the Arab Spring, Al Jazeera's

²⁴⁰ Bennett, 2008, p. 6

²⁴¹ "Adult and Youth Literacy, 1990-2015 Analysis of Data for 41 Selected Countries", UNESCO, 2012, <http://www.uis.unesco.org/Education/Documents/UIS-literacy-statistics-1990-2015-en.pdf>

²⁴² Iskandar, Adel, "Free at Last? Charting Egypt's Media Post-Mubarak", *Jadaliyya*, 19 December 2011, <http://www.jadaliyya.com/pages/index/3641/free-at-last-charting-egypts-media-post-mubarak>

²⁴³ Ibid.

coverage was the key in terms of spreading the ideals of the protests throughout the region.²⁴⁴ Even after the coup when international media started losing their interest in Egypt, Al Jazeera continued to report from Egypt and be a news source bridging the protesters with the global community.

As Bennett and Segerberg argue, “while new media grant protest organizers crucial means of bypassing mass media, ability to disseminate claims through mass media is still assumed to be central.”²⁴⁵ Hence for activists to be in the public agenda, it is almost requisite for them to be visible in mass media. Offline forms of activism like boycotts, street demonstrations can’t intrigue the attention of mass media unless they contain extreme and/or creative acts (such as the ones we described above). Even a small number of activists can alter the public opinion if they can manage to make a statement that will reach and resonate with masses. Therefore, although many of the contemporary social movements may often be born and expand online, they still do need to engage with mass media to reach out to the public and build awareness locally and globally.

A case in point is concerns how a group of Turkish activists used Indiegogo, a crowdfunding website, to fundraise \$53,000 for a full page ad in New York Times to raise global awareness for the Occupy Gezi. The ad proposes several demands such as “end to police brutality” and “free media”. One of the founders of the campaign says that he joined because he felt Turkish mass media was being insensitive to what has been going on.²⁴⁶ This ad is important to demonstrate that activists still rely on mass media to be recognised.

!

WHAT'S HAPPENING IN TURKEY?

Millions of Turkish citizens have been outraged by the violent reaction of their government to a peaceful protest aimed at saving Istanbul's Gezi Park. Outraged, yet not surprised.

Over the course of Prime Minister Erdogan's ten-year term, we have witnessed a steady erosion of our rights and freedoms. Arrests of numerous journalists, artists, and elected officials; restrictions on freedom of speech, women's rights, and even alcohol sales have all demonstrated that the ruling party is not serious about democracy. Time and again, the Prime Minister has mocked and trivialized his nation's concerns while Turkey's own media has remained shamefully silent.

The people protesting bravely throughout Turkey are the proud inheritors of Atatürk's legacy. We are not looters or extremists. We are students, teachers, workers, mothers, fathers. We represent various ethnicities and creeds, religions and ideologies. We stand united now because of our concern for Turkey's future.

We demand an end to police brutality.
We demand a free and unbiased media.
We demand an open dialogue, not the dictate of an autocrat.

We hope that you will join the conversation and stand with us in solidarity.
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2013_protests_in_Turkey

#GeziPark #OccupyGezi #DirenGeziParki

THIS STATEMENT IS CROWDFUNDED BY CONCERNED INDIVIDUALS FROM AROUND THE WORLD.

Millions of people in **Turkey** have been outraged by the violent reaction of their government to a peaceful protest aimed at saving Istanbul's Gezi Park. Outraged, yet not surprised.

this isn't just about a park

Over the course of Prime Minister Erdogan's ten-year term, we have witnessed a steady erosion of our rights and freedoms. Arrests of numerous journalists, artists, and elected officials; alongside restrictions on freedom of speech, minority and women's rights all demonstrate that the ruling party is not serious about democracy.

Time and again, the Prime Minister has mocked and trivialized his nation's concerns while Turkey's own media has remained shamefully silent.

The people protesting bravely throughout Turkey are mere citizens. We are not looters or extremists. We are students, teachers, workers, mothers, fathers. We represent various ethnicities and creeds, religions and ideologies. We stand united now because of our concern for Turkey's future.

We demand an end to police brutality.
We demand a free and unbiased media.
We demand an open dialogue, not the dictate of an autocrat.
We demand an investigation of the recent abuse of power by government forces that have led to the loss of innocent lives.
We hope that you will join the conversation and stand with us in solidarity.

These are actual tear gas shells fired by the thousands on peaceful protestors in Istanbul.

Crowdfunded Entirely by Concerned Individuals from Around the World.

Become a part of the conversation and stand with us in solidarity.
@WAnonIndiegogo #WAnonIndiegogo #OccupyGezi #DirenGeziParki #GeziPark

Figure 3.6: An ad published in New York Times to raise global awareness about Occupy Gezi.

²⁴⁴ Castells, 2012, p. 26.

²⁴⁵ Bennett, W. Lance, and Alexandra Segerberg, “Digital Media and the Personalization of Collective Action,” *Information, Communication & Society*, Vol. 14, No. 6, September 2011, pp. 770–99, p. 775.

²⁴⁶ “Turkish Protestors Use Indiegogo To Help Fund New York Times Ad”, Huffington Post, 3 June 2013, http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2013/06/03/turkish-protestors-indiegogo_n_3381340.html

3.5.2 New media technologies

As discussed in Deliverable 2.2., particularly at times of political crises, many media users will not consider mainstream media, especially when they are controlled by governments and conglomerates with clientelistic relationships with states, to be reliable sources of information.²⁴⁷ In such cases, online media constitute an important alternative outlet for receiving, sharing, and producing information or opinions. It is in this respect that for the first time in the history of activism, contemporary activists have the opportunity to bypass conventional mainstream media and act as gatekeepers and disseminators of information.²⁴⁸ The information can move more freely in relation to mass media as it is less filtered by editors and journalistic codes.²⁴⁹

Especially in authoritarian regimes, platforms like blogs, online forums and other forms of online communication applications provided the public space where information can be shared and issues can be discussed more freely.²⁵⁰ This also can potentially mitigate the repression of the government over the information, particularly where mass media is controlled by the state.²⁵¹ Relatedly, recent studies suggest, new media platforms like blogs may play an important role in political domains with authoritarian regimes by bringing up issues censored/ignored/filtered out by the mainstream media.²⁵²

Likewise, the recent protests in Spain, also known as the 15-M Movement, have shown how online media can help people “overcome a media block. The capacity of mass self-communication and self-organization online has allowed people to overcome a media block. In outlet that did come to the press conference we organized around the 15-M demonstrations, BTV (Barcelona TV).”²⁵³

Figure 3.7 compares the front page surface dedicated to 15M Movement in Spanish newspapers and total number of tweets using the most popular hashtags #15M and #spanishrevolution. Accordingly the page surface dedicated to and the number of tweets are about the 15M movement are highly correlated, suggesting a symbiotic existence between these two forms of public space, and potentially weakening the monopoly that mass media have as a gate-keeper.²⁵⁴

²⁴⁷ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., “Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *COSMIC*, 2013, pp.22-23.

²⁴⁸ Bennett, 2005.

²⁴⁹ *Ibid.* p. 124.

²⁵⁰ Tüfekçi, Zeynep and Christopher Wilson, “Social Media and the decision to participate in political protest: Observations from Tahrir Square”, *Journal of Communication*, Vol. 62, Issue 2, 2012, pp. 363-79, p. 366.

²⁵¹ Etling, Bruce; Faris, Robert; and John Palfrey, “Political Change in the Digital Age: The Fragility and Promise of Online Organizing”, *SAIS Review*, Vol. 30, Issue 2, 2010, pp. 37-49.

²⁵² Fahmy, Nagwa A., “Revealing the ‘Agenda-Cutting’ through Egyptian Blogs: An Empirical Study, 2010, <https://online.journalism.utexas.edu/2010/papers/Fahmy10.pdf>

²⁵³ Castells, 2012.

²⁵⁴ Bennett, p. 124.

Figure 3.7: Coverage of 15-M Movement in Twitter and Newspapers.²⁵⁵

3.5.2.1 Social Media

Recent protest movements in Iran, Moldova, Egypt, Tunisia, Turkey and various other countries raised the debates on the importance of social media and their effects on politics.²⁵⁶ The Prime Minister of Turkey, Recep Tayyip Erdoğan accused social media for the protests and depicted social media “as the worst menace to the society.”²⁵⁷ As it was the case in Turkey, social media and other forms of new media pose a challenge for governments in authoritarian states by

1. “Promoting contentious collective action;
2. Limiting or enhancing the mechanisms of state repression;
3. Affecting international support for the regime;
4. Affecting the overall control of the public sphere.”²⁵⁸

The most used social media platforms, Twitter and Facebook also contribute to the creation of collective identity by creating a sense of connectivity between the activists. They create a space for solidarity as activists interact, interconnect with other activists around the world and show support.²⁵⁹

Facebook

According to a research made by Ovum, 80% of Egyptian owned mobile phones at the end of 2010, just before the “Arab Spring.” More than 25% of the population in the main cities had access to Internet in their homes. In February 2011, there were approximately 5 million

²⁵⁵ “Coding online is easier: help PageOnex find its bugs!”, *Numeroteca*, n.d.

<http://numeroteca.org/2012/08/31/superficie-portadas-de-periodico-15m-vs-twitter/>

²⁵⁶ Christensen, Christian, “Twitter revolutions? Addressing Social Media and Dissent”, *The Communication Review*, Vo. 4, Issue 3, 2011, pp. 155-57.

²⁵⁷ Letsch, Constanza, “Social Media and Opposition to Blame for Protests, Says Turkish PM”, *The Guardian*, 3 June 2013, <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/jun/02/turkish-protesters-control-istanbul-square>

²⁵⁸ Lynch, 2011, p. 304.

²⁵⁹ Juris, 2012.

Facebook users in Egypt and 600.000 of them had started using Facebook just before the revolution in January and February 2011.²⁶⁰ “We are all Khaled Saeed” Facebook page is one of the important examples to social media usage in Egypt. In 2010, Wael Ghonim, a young Egyptian working at Google, created the page dedicated Khaled Seed, who was tortured to death by police. The page became an online gathering space against police brutality and a campaign to end corruption in the government. Ghonim made a call on the page to go out on 25th of January; “Today is the 14th of January. In 10 days, we have a police day. If 100,000 of us take to the street, no one is going to stop us.” And as Ghonim puts it, “That was the beginning.”²⁶¹

Twitter

Twitter is a microblogging service designed to let users post a maximum of 140 characters of text. Twitter lets the users follow any other user they want and the content created by the users is publicly accessible unless it is specified otherwise by the user. Twitter’s potential as a venue that enables rapid dissemination of information is among the main reasons why activists increasingly rely on it to coordinate action.²⁶² This was also the case during the Egyptian protests, with Facebook facilitating the planning and Twitter facilitating the coordination.²⁶³ As Castells points out, according to a data analysis of Tweets sent from Tahrir Square in 24-29th of January, Tweeting was perhaps one of the most effective messaging tools to influence the actions of individuals.²⁶⁴ Figure 3.8 represents the distribution of information flow source types in tweets comparing Tunisian and Egyptian protest. Information flow source indicates “the user who first posted the content”.²⁶⁵ It is important to note that there is a significant increase in the number of source information Tweets Tunisia to Egypt.

Figure 3.8: Distribution of information flow by source²⁶⁶

²⁶⁰ Castells, 2001, p. 64

²⁶¹“Wael Ghonim, Creating a 'Revolution 2.0' in Egypt”, npr books, 9 February 2012, <http://www.npr.org/2012/02/09/146636605/wael-ghonim-creating-a-revolution-2-0-in-egypt>

²⁶² Lotan, Gilad; Ananny, Mike; Gaffney, Devin; and Danah Boyd, “The Revolutions Were Tweeted : Information Flows During the 2011 Tunisian and Egyptian Revolutions Web Ecology Project Web Ecology Project,” *International Journal of Communication*, Vol. 5, 2011, p. 1375-405.

²⁶³ Castells, 2012.

²⁶⁴ Castells, 2012, p. 58.

²⁶⁵ Lotan, 2011, p. 1388.

²⁶⁶ Lotan, 1388.

On the other hand, during the “Green Revolution” in Iran in 2009, Twitter was not used widely. Most of Tweets were created or Retweeted not by people in Iran, but by other people around the world for support.^{267 268} The claim by an Iranian activist blogger, Vahid Online, confirms the data about Twitter use in Iran:

Twitter never became very popular in Iran. [But] because the world was watching Iran with such [great interest] during those days, it led many to believe falsely that Iranian people were also getting their news through Twitter.²⁶⁹

Hence, he rejects the claims that call the protests after the elections a “Twitter revolution”.²⁷⁰ However, it is still possible to observe the impact of other social media tools other than Twitter. Facebook was blocked again by the government just before the election as it started to turn into a space where oppositional ideas were shared.²⁷¹ Yet, the greatest effect of social media may be a mobilising one for the protests. A case in point was the YouTube video showing the tragic death of Neda Agha Soltan who was shot death during the 2009 protests. The video drew international attention and according to some helped sustain the momentum of the protests.^{272 273}

Alternative media websites

There are many debates on what can be called an alternative media. Within the context of this report we will use a definition outlined by Fenton and Barassi (2011): “production of small scale media that are linked to the realities of social movements (but not exclusively), and that are defined by collective practices of participatory communication within a given group.”²⁷⁴

Internet provides the space to publish and disseminate alternative points of view and alternative media websites are composed of activists producing media in a collective manner. These “communication practices and the construction of collective discourses are often central to the creation of and consolidation of political groups”.²⁷⁵ As it was the case with Independent Media Centre, also known as Indymedia which is one of the first alternative media websites. It was first launched in 1999 to report on the World Trade Organization protests in Seattle and became a major source of information. During the Seattle protest it acted as the converging media space for the participant groups like unions, anarchists, social justice groups; and provided an alternative view of the protests. The network expanded over time and now there are more than 150 Indymedia sites around the world. Indymedia is based on open publishing, meaning that it is open platform where activists can create and submit their own news online.

As Indymedia might be the most widely known alternative media website, there are other news websites, blogs and wikis that provide news on the social movements which are

²⁶⁷ Etling, et al., 2010, p. 11.

²⁶⁸ Morozov, Evgeny, *The Net Delusion: The Dark Side of Internet Freedom*, Public Affairs, New York, 2011, p.16.

²⁶⁹ Esfandiari, Golnaz, “The Myths And Realities Of New Media In Iran's Green Movement”, *RFE/RL*, 11 June 2010, http://www.rferl.org/content/Irans_Green_Movement_And_New_Media/2068714.html

²⁷⁰ Ibid.

²⁷¹ Ibid.

²⁷² Etling, 2010, p. 11.

²⁷³ “Irani Tehran: wounded girl dying in front of the camera, Her name was Neda”, 20 June 2009, <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bbdEf0QRsLM>

²⁷⁴ Fenton, Natalie, and Veronica Barassi, “Alternative Media and Social Networking Sites: The Politics of Individuation and Political Participation”, *The Communication Review*, Vol. 14, No. 3, 2011, pp. 179–96.

²⁷⁵ Fenton and Barassi, 2011, p. 188.

basically run by activist volunteer working in collaboration.²⁷⁶ For example, helping collaboration and cooperation between activists was the motivation behind the media project Infoespai (Infospace), which started in 2003 after a series of political protests.²⁷⁷ Infospace was providing a space for activists where shared resources are held like free internet access, tools for publishing and editing, other computer resources and an activist research room to enhance research and debate.²⁷⁸ As Juris argues, the online and offline actions were interconnected.²⁷⁹ With projects like Moviments.net, Infoespai created a web-based database where all the social-political groups and organisations in Catalunya can be found.²⁸⁰ Infoespai is an example of how technical capabilities can be merged with activism and used for enhancing social transformation.²⁸¹ It is important to mention that Infoespai was also a precedent for more recent networks that emerged in Spain like Democracia Real Ya! which will be discussed in the next pages.

²⁷⁶ Lievrouw, Leah A., "Oppositional and activist new media: Remediation, reconfiguration, participation." in I. Wagner and J. Blomberg (eds.), *Proceedings of the Participatory Design Conference '06*, Trento, Italy, 2006, pp. 115-24.

²⁷⁷ Izaskun and Robin, "Infoespai: putting theory into practice", *Moviments.net*, 10 November 2004, <http://moviments.net/tiki-index.php?page=InfoespaiArticleEN>

²⁷⁸ "Infoespai - communication in Barcelona", 7 May 2004, <http://eu.d-a-s-h.org/infoespai>

²⁷⁹ Juris, 2005a, p. 205.

²⁸⁰ Izaskun and Robin, 2004.

²⁸¹ Juris, 2005a, p. 205.

3.6 COMMUNICATIVE ACTIVITIES

3.6.1 Network building

As we discussed in the preceding sections, networking in various forms is one of the main components of contemporary activism. Network building technologies (Internet, mobile phones etc.) are essential because they constitute the main platform for the movements to continuously evolve and expand. As the Spanish thinker and activist Javier Toret puts it “a mutant network system with moving boundaries, hybrid, cyborg, a collective body that resists time and can extend through space.”²⁸²

In an early account of the potential of new media, Etzioni and Etzioni questioned whether “computer-mediated communication” can replace face-to-face communication. They conclude that hybrid systems combining both modes are more effective to form and maintain some sort of community.²⁸³ Likewise, for contemporary activism, it should be noted that activists can sustain and improve the face-to-face networks they have formed in a protest by continuing to communicate through new media.²⁸⁴

Indignadas Movement in Spain presents the power of networking where self-organized networks evolved into a massive collective action. The organizations which are significant to the Indignadas Movement were started online just before the movement began. The movement used personal contacts, social media, and other networking channels in ways that not only supplements but also, to some extent, supplants traditional membership approaches.²⁸⁵ According to Anduiza and colleagues, nearly 55% of protesters heard about the demonstrations via alternative online media and 49% through social media.²⁸⁶

On May 15 2011, demonstrations had taken place across Spain in 50 different cities and approximately 130.000 people joined. They were organised mostly over the Internet, led by an online platform called “Democracia Real Ya” (Real Democracy Now). This platform was actually a Facebook group that developed into an activist umbrella hub joining more than 400 organizations under the motto. At the beginning the group was composed of few hundred people who considered the current system incapable of representing public.

Inspired by the Arab Spring and the platform decided to go into action. Thus they made a call to the public on March 2 2011 saying “Real Democracy Now! Go out into the streets. We are not goods in the hands of politicians and bankers.”²⁸⁷ There wasn't any political party, labour union or any other established organization behind this call, but the call was heard. By Facebook, Twitter and various other networking platforms the call got disseminated and on 15th there were thousands of people protesting in the streets and that protest was the first of the protests, which was called Indignadas or 15M (Figure 3.9).

²⁸² Gutierrez, Bernardo, “What do Brazil, Turkey, Peru and Bulgaria have in common?” 7 September 2013, <http://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/2013/09/20139572247949239.html>

²⁸³ Etzioni, A. and Oren Etzioni, "Face-to-Face and Computer-Mediated Communities, A Comparative Analysis" "The Information Society", Vol. 15, No. 4, 1999, pp. 241-48.

²⁸⁴ Donk, W., 2005, p. 88.

²⁸⁵ Anduiza Eva; Cristancho, Camilo and José M. Sabucedo , “Mobilization through Online Social Networks: The Political Protest of the Indignados in Spain”, *Information, Communication & Society*, 2013.

²⁸⁶ Ibid. p. 9.

²⁸⁷ Castells, 2012, p.107.

Often, it is hard to reach a decision even by considerate consensus. Usually it is very time consuming and debates can last for hours causing the decision making processes to be very slow.²⁹¹ In addition, dominance of the majority in consensus decision making may be problematic because “even in the practice of considerate consensus, there is almost inevitably a certain pressure on dissenters to eventually remain silent, even against their will.”²⁹² As such, while each participant has the power to reject a proposition, in cases when the assembly is on the verge of making a decision, it is most likely that the dissenter will yield to the will of the majority.²⁹³

3.6.2.2 New media and decision making

There are many opportunities that new media presents in terms of enabling various linkages between diverse networks. As we have argued before, the horizontal and flexible structuring of the networks may cause the networks to be rather ideologically thin²⁹⁴. This can affect the decision making process in a negative way. Increasing heterogeneity in networks may cause more ideological divisions thus may create fragmentation of approaches on decision making. In online networks, coordinating and acting decisively can be rather difficult.²⁹⁵

3.6.3 Mobilization, coordination and operational information sharing

Contemporary activists make particularly effective use of new media to globally share information to mobilize and coordinate action. During action, real time circulation of information through networks allows activists to determine strategies and take simultaneous actions accordingly. It should be noted that online and mobile communication tools do not replace face-to-face interaction between the activists, rather they complement it. As Juris, J. indicates, activities like complex planning and close-relationship building continued to be done in physical settings.²⁹⁶

Social media, especially microblogging and video sites like Twitter or Vine, are used for dissemination of information on current situation and tactics for evading a current predicament such as the question of which routes to be taken to avoid police.

The following tweet from Egyptian Revolution, is an example of such:

@wilyawil: Im hearing from friends inside Tahrir Sq that best entrance is from Falaki st. #jan25 #egypt [Retweeted 18 times]²⁹⁷

Moreover Tweeter is used to call for help from remote:

@occupiedcairo: Medical supplies needed at temp. hospital at Tahrir: neck supports and stitching thread #jan25 [Retweeted 39 times]²⁹⁸

²⁹¹ Ibid.

²⁹² Haug, Christoph, “Assembly Publics and the Problem of Hegemony in Consensus Decision-making”, *Open Democracy*, 1 October 2012, <http://www.opendemocracy.net/christoph-haug/assembly-publics-and-problem-of-hegemony-in-consensus-decision-making>

²⁹³ Ibid.

²⁹⁴ Bennett, 2005.

²⁹⁵ Bennett, 2005.

²⁹⁶ Juris, 2005a, p. 196.

²⁹⁷ Starbird, Kate, “(How) Will the Revolution Be Retweeted ? Information Diffusion and the 2011 Egyptian Uprising,” *CSCW’12*, 2012, p.7.

In addition, some websites provide participants with the practical information on what to wear, bring and other detailed information on where to stay. They also encourage people to participate and give the calendar of actions they can attend. Information on precautions against tear gas, plastic bullets and legal rights in custody are given if there is a clash with the police forces. Bar Association of Istanbul made an announcement from its website, on June 7, 2013 titled “You have your rights”. The announcement, widely disseminated online, was a list briefly summarizing the legal rights of a citizen in case of custody.²⁹⁹

Also, activists use mobile tools thoroughly. Information sharing and verifying service Sukey, social networking services like Vibe and Celly and SMS broadcasting app, I'm Getting Arrested are examples of applications launched during Occupy Protests. Vibe was noticeably used during Occupy Wall Street as an alternative to Twitter for coordinating and circulating information. Twitter in its logic is an information source open to public; hence making the strategic information shared within the activists available for police monitoring. Vibe, on the other hand, allows the users to define for how far and how long that they want their messages to be visible. So the user can limit the message to be shared within 50 meters, which presumably creates a more secure area for people to communicate in close range.

As information on Internet provides rich and multiple aspects of a particular event, the reliability of the information is a problem. Some protest websites like Sendika.org in Occupy Gezi provided activists in action with updates and other logistical information.

3.6.4 Sousveillance

There is a constant practice of recording by the activists such as taking pictures and videos and sharing them in social media. As discussed in Deliverable 2.3, one of the most important drives that urges activist to record is sousveillance.³⁰⁰ During an action, information and communication technologies (and increasingly portable recording devices) make it possible for the activists to constantly document their interaction with government authorities and law enforcement.

Such documenting has become an effective tool for the activists to expose misconduct by those in power. For example, the possibility of sousveillance by activists, particularly live-streaming—broadcasting real-time video content through the Internet—works as a protection against excessive police force. As a side note, it should be mentioned that during the recent Occupy Gezi protests in Turkey, police utilized counter-sousveillance techniques such as disguising the ID numbers on their helmets with black tape and other types of wrapping stickers (Figure 3.10).

Release of evidence by hacktivist groups can be regarded as another form of sousveillance. Abdullah Cömert was the second protester who was killed during Occupy Gezi, however authorities didn't take any action about the case. As a response, the hacker group Redhack leaked documents uncovering the identities of the police officers who had been working in the area during which Abdullah Cömert was killed.

²⁹⁸ Ibid., p.7.

²⁹⁹ “You have your rights”. Bar Association of Istanbul, 7 June 2013, <http://www.istanbulbarosu.org.tr/detail.asp?CatID=1&SubCatID=1&ID=8207>

³⁰⁰ Scifo, Salvatore, and Lemi Baruh, “Deliverable 2.3: Report on the adverse use and reliability of new media”, *COSMIC*, 2013, pp.23-25.

Figure 3.10: Police officers hiding their ID numbers to counter sousveillance by activists during the Gezi Protests

3.6.5 Building global awareness

As discussed previously in this chapter, expansion of new media has significantly enhanced the ability of activists to share information, ideas and news. Contemporary activists argue that problems of justice in the society are related to global corporations and organizations like World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF).³⁰¹ Hence global activism is “characterized by long-running communication campaigns to organize protests and publicize issues aimed at transnational organizations, corporations, and other targets.”³⁰²

Organizing campaigns is surely not new in the activism scene; however, before it was largely carried by established organizations like trade unions and NGO’s. Now many of these global campaigns are led by more decentralised networks containing diverse actors have become more difficult to turn on and out.³⁰³ The series of global justice protests in U.S. and in Prague in 2000 following the Seattle protests and how they were quickly triggered and organized by list-serves demonstrate the potential of networks spurring boundless of time and spatial location.³⁰⁴

Today, beyond list-serves, using new media to circulate information through global networks has become kind of reflexive behaviour of the activists.³⁰⁵ Twitter, with about a 900 million registered accounts,³⁰⁶ provides the capability for social activists in political crises to address issues in a “global” arena which can, in turn, lead to gaining support from the global community. During Egyptian Revolution “written messages and images circulating on Facebook, Twitter, and blogs appeared to strengthen the collective identity of Egyptians worldwide.” Several Facebook pages were created to get support from Egyptians living abroad: “Voice of Egypt Abroad,” “Egyptians Abroad in Support of Egypt,” and “New United Arab States.”³⁰⁷

³⁰¹ Bennett, 2005. p. 6.

³⁰² Ibid.

³⁰³ Bennett, 2005, p. 8.

³⁰⁴ Juris, 2005, p. 348.

³⁰⁵ Juris, 2005b, p. 201.

³⁰⁶ Edwards, Jim “Twitter's 'Dark Pool': IPO Doesn't Mention 651 Million Users Who Abandoned Twitter”, Business Insider, 6 November 2013, <http://www.businessinsider.com/twitter-total-registered-users-v-monthly-active-users-2013-11>

³⁰⁷ Eltantawy, Nahed and Julie B. Wiest, “Social Media in the Egyptian Revolution: Reconsidering Resource Mobilization Theory,” *International Journal of Communication*, Vol. 5, 2011, pp. 1207–24, p.1218.

3.7 CONCLUSION

This chapter of the report focused citizens as social activists and reviewed how activists organize, engage, communicate and collaborate. Also, the chapter discussed the ways in which activists utilize media tools, including social media, for these purposes. We used the term “contemporary” to frame the activist formations we explored to differentiate it from the “traditional” activism. The report starts with the Seattle Protest in 1999 as it marks a significant shift in activism and continues by discussing recent events held since.

Networking logic and its connotations are frequently repeated throughout the chapter to emphasize the ways in which new media bring about new opportunities for coming together, mobilizing, coordinating, creating a public spaces and etc. We adopted the term “formation” to define flexible, organization-like convergences.

Characteristics of Contemporary Activism

- **Glocalization:** Partly as a result of the capabilities new media provide, activists are no longer bound by spatial and temporal limits. Hence they have the ability to network with other activist groups or/and individuals at global levels. Even when they are working for ostensibly local causes, they increasingly network and share their arguments and demands looking for solidarity. They tend to consider themselves as part of a global community of people who share similar concerns.
- **Participatory Politics and Horizontal Organization Structures:** Based on the networking logic, contemporary activist formations are non-hierarchical and have horizontal structures. They try to practice alternative ways of decision making based on direct participation and open-access. In so doing, they challenge traditional ways of doing politics.
- **Autonomous Flexibility:** “Autonomy” reflects two distinct characteristics contemporary activism formations manifest. One of them is that they avoid any attachment with established political parties and other institutions involved in contemporary representative politics. The second one is they regard autonomy as a practice that will build the ground for autonomous society. Flexibility is a very much integrated concept with autonomy: activist networks today are inclusive and dynamic giving the ability for individuals and groups to freely diffuse in and out of various networks.

Typology of Activists Today

- **Individual:** With the advent of new media, every individual has the potential to induce or be the locus of a network, a movement or a protest. New media make instantaneous networking, communicating and networking possible thus facilitating the capacity of the individuals which highly contrasts with traditional politics based on rigid leadership structures that are not conducive to engagement of individuals.
- **Online Umbrella Hubs:** Online umbrella hubs can be described as online platforms where various activist groups and individuals participate. They usually emerge in order to coordinate global protests.

- **Affinity Groups:** It is a smaller group of people with mutual purposes.
- **Hactivist Groups:** Hactivist groups are activists who adopt hacking for political purposes. They are a rather important for activists as they symbolize the potential to collapse the existing system. Anonymous is the most notorious among them.
- **Network Parties:** The concept of network party refers to new political parties that emerged as political actors in the last 10 years. They are challenging the traditional representational politics scene. Movimento 5 Stelle in Italy is an example of network party which originated from a blog page and then extended into a movement later a political party.
- **Established Organizations:** It refers to any political group that is more conventional in organizational policies and procedures. However, we see that these types of organizations are also trying to adapt to and benefit from new media. “Open source unionism” is given as an example of such endeavour.

Repertoire of Activist Actions

In this report we categorized activist actions in two main categories; offline and online and described them briefly with recent examples. We positioned each type into the Postmes and Brunsting model mapping actions on collectivistic–individualistic and persuasive–confrontational dimensions. “Demonstration”, “strike”, “hunger strike” and “occupation” were reviewed as examples of offline actions.

“Occupations” were especially discussed in more detail because it has become a highly preferred action in the last few years. Occupations have several benefits for movements:

1. They create spaces where forms of autonomy are experimented.
2. They facilitate the development, extension and strengthening of networks
3. They help increase public visibility
4. They help intensify the experience of solidarity.

“Online action” category comprises actions which are primarily performed online. Some of the actions are adaptation of existing offline actions such as “online petitions”. Others, like “website defacement” and “DDOS”, are comparably new and original as they are intrinsically related with the medium itself.

Finally, it is important to note that while the dichotomy of online vs. offline helps categorization, we have observed that, increasingly, there is a symbiotic relationship between offline and online activism. And more importantly, both online and offline activism require involvement of mass media to reach the wider public. It is in this respect that “theatricality” and “creativity” (to receive media and public attention) are the key distinguishing characteristics of activist actions.

Use of Media

- **Mass Media:** Although there has been a significant decrease in mass media consumption, mass media continue to be the dominant venue to communicate with the public especially in countries like Egypt where illiteracy rate is high. This is why Egyptians witnessed a power play over the Egyptian state TV by Mubarak’s regime and later the militaristic government; and that is why Al Jazeera’s coverage of protests was of high importance.

- **New Media:** New media have become an alternative outlet to mass media for reaching, sharing and producing information and opinions. Especially in authoritarian regimes where mainstream media are censored or under pressure, platforms like blogs, forums and other types of new media tools provide an alternative space for information flow.
- **Social Media:** Social media pose a challenge for authoritarian governments by promoting collective action, limiting or enhancing state repression, helping build international and national support. Twitter and Facebook are currently the most frequently used social media platforms. They create a space where activists can interact at global levels and experience solidarity and collective identity. Twitter enables rapid information dissemination, making it a preferable tool for coordinating action; on the other hand, Facebook is more used for action planning.
- **Alternative Media Websites:** Alternative media websites are spaces where alternative points of views are published and disseminated. They produce small scale content in a collectivistic manner which is mostly linked to social movements.

Activists and Communicative Activities

- **Network Building:** Networking is one of the main features of contemporary activism. Although new media cannot replace face-to-face communication, they provide the tools for the networks to expand and the movements to evolve.
- **Decision Making:** Contemporary activists try to implement governance methods that rely on participatory politics. They form assemblies for collective decision-making where each individual has the right to speak, make a proposition, discuss and ask questions. There are debates (and doubts) about the effectiveness of such decision-making processes. The decision-making processes are also problematic as networks may become ideologically thin.
- **Mobilization, Coordination and Operational Information Sharing:** Activists make effective use of new media for sharing real time operational information to mobilize, coordinate, determine strategies and take simultaneous actions. We witnessed the use of new social media services, such as Vibe, which presumably create a more secure space for communication by making it possible for the user to determine the reach-distance of messages, as an alternative to Twitter which is highly susceptible to police monitoring.
- **Sousveillance:** Activists today have the facilities to constantly document their interaction with governmental forces and share them real time social media. Sousveillance has become an effective tool to expose misconduct. Additionally, the possibility of sousveillance can potentially protect citizens from excessive police force.
- **Building Global Awareness:** Expansion of new media has significantly increased the ability of the activists to share information, ideas and news. Today, circulating information through global networks has become a reflexive behaviour for activists; by building situational awareness they can get support in the global arena.

Chapter 4: Citizens as Journalists

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4 CITIZENS AS JOURNALISTS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Emergence of new information and communication technologies has brought about important changes not only in the profession of journalism but also in how news is consumed. According to Fortunati et al., one important change pertains to the growing role readers/audiences have:

Audiences slowly become true actors in the course of time (they are better educated, have more money to spend, have different media choices, are more individualized), as all the media system is based on the purchasing power, the selective capacity, and the hermeneutic ability and activity of the audience. The advent of the Internet potentially enhances the role of audiences even more and pushes scholars to revisit both media effect and audience theories.³⁰⁸

Waldman suggests that citizens are empowered in the new media environment through the ability to publish their account of the events without mediation; hence, citizen journalism serves as a tool of empowerment by giving voice to citizens who have the necessary resources, ability and motivation to publish their reports and opinions.³⁰⁹ For example, the concept of smart aggregation refers to a new type of gatekeeping and authentication in which various Internet-based sources offer quality content in the endless informational possibilities of the digital age. Likewise, in citizen journalism, authentication is said to be based on “crowds” rather than professional editors. In terms of witnessing, citizen journalism provides more immediate ways of reporting with the use of cameras in mobile phones and devices. The concept of sense making underlines a new form of agenda-setting within which commentaries by diverse voices in the Internet help citizens make sense of the flows of information in a context and raises the blogosphere as a potential fifth-estate.³¹⁰

Given these changes in the landscape of journalism and production and consumption of news, the aim of this chapter is to examine the role that citizen journalists play in news dissemination during times of crisis. The chapter will start (Section 2) with a brief overview of the concept of journalism, particularly focusing on the impact of ICTs on the emergence of citizen journalism as a concept and debates regarding what constitutes citizen journalism. The section to follow (Section 3) will discuss opportunities offered by and challenges to citizen journalism in the context of emergency communications. In terms of opportunities, this section will focus on decentralization and the ensuing democratization of news making, what citizen witnessing offers during crises, and the potential benefit of citizen journalism as a fifth estate. At the same time, digital divide, ethical problems will be discussed as potential challenges that citizen journalism faces.

The next two sections (Section 4 and Section 5) will utilize a subsample of case studies (Xynthia Storm, Boston Bombings, Gezi Protests, and Haiti Earthquake) conducted for

³⁰⁸ Fortunati, Leopoldina, Mauro Sarrica, John O’Sullivan, Aukse Balcytiene, Halliki Harro-Loit, Phil Macgregor, Nayia Roussou, Ramón Salaverría, and Federico de Luca, “The Influence of the Internet on European Journalism,” *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, Vol. 14, No. 4, July 2009, pp. 928–963. [p. 932]

³⁰⁹ Waldman, Steven, “The Media Food Chain and the Functions of Journalism,” *The Information Needs of Communities: The Changing Media Landscape in a Broadband Age*, Carolina Academic Press, Durham, NC, 2011, pp. 242–247

³¹⁰ Cooper, Stephen D., *Watching the Watchdog*, Marquette Books, 2006. Goode, Luke, “Social news, citizen journalism and democracy,” *New Media & Society*, Vol. 11, No. 8, pp. 1287-1305.

Deliverable 2.2. of the COSMIC project³¹¹ to engage in a two-pronged analysis of citizen journalism. As a first part of this analysis, a content analysis of the reports published by a sample of bloggers who wrote about the emergencies listed above will be summarized (Section 4). In the second part of the analysis, results of online interviews conducted with the bloggers whose reports were content analyzed will be summarized.

Figure 4.1: Two-pronged analysis of citizen journalism during emergencies

This two-pronged approach will help understand in detail key dimensions of news selection and reporting processes by citizen reporters during emergencies and crises.

³¹¹ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., “Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *COSMIC*, 2013

4.2 CITIZEN JOURNALISM: AN OVERVIEW OF THE CONCEPT

The aim of this section is to briefly discuss the factors that have contributed to the rise of citizen journalism. These factors include 1) the diffusion of new information and communication technologies (ICTs) that enable individuals to produce, as well as consume, information; and 2) a “democratic deficit” that has, for a considerable time, excluded citizens from processes associated with news selection and dissemination. Next, the section will summarize different perspectives regarding the definition of what constitutes a “citizen journalist.”

4.2.1 New Media and the emergence of citizen journalism

Emergence of new forms of citizen journalism utilizing ICTs is rapidly changing our understanding of news reporting. In mainstream media, information gathering process mainly comprises “press releases, the news wire and first person interviews”³¹² which are conceptualized by Hindman as “official places.”³¹³ This practice of information gathering is found to be mostly “unidirectional” and limited to few information sources.³¹⁴ For example, with respect to television journalism, Liebes and Kampf states that:

Historically, from the earliest days of television, it was clear that the new medium, in which pictures are no less important than words, would be inclined to personalize politics. Nevertheless, the new dominant medium did not stray very far from the old adage that “news is what elites say, and what elites do.” Thus, the elites were increasingly personalized and the non-elites remained mobs, masses, and movements that disturbed the peace.³¹⁵

At the same time that mainstream journalism is criticized for being increasingly entrenched in “elite” institutions, it is also expected to act as a Fourth Estate and be a watch dog that will ensure accountability of institutions; thus, contributing to democracy and pluralism.³¹⁶ This contradiction between the role that mass media is supposed to play as a guardian of democratic systems of democracy on the one hand and projector of dominant elite interests on the other makes the new possibilities in news gathering and dissemination brought about by ICTs all the more important. To some extent, emergence of citizen journalism can be considered to be not only a consequence of emerging ICTs but also the result of this inherent contradiction in the institution of journalism. This contradiction is also referred to as “democratic deficit” which, according to Goode, refers to “non-transparency and over-

³¹² Heravi, Bahareh Rahmanzadeh, Marie Boran, and John G Breslin, “Towards Social Semantic Journalism,” *AAAI Technical Report WS-12-01*, Dublin, 2012, pp. 14–17 [p. 14].

³¹³ Hindman, 1998, p. 177, cited in Heravi, Bahareh Rahmanzadeh, Marie Boran, and John G Breslin, “Towards Social Semantic Journalism,” *AAAI Technical Report WS-12-01*, Dublin, 2012, pp. 14–17 [p. 14].

³¹⁴ Siegl & Foot, 2004, cited in Gillette, Shana, Jonathan Taylor, Deborah Chavez, Ron Hodgson, and Judith Downing, “Citizen Journalism in a Time of Crisis: Lessons from California Wildfires,” *The Electronic Journal of Communication*, Vol. 17, No. 3 & 4, 2007, pp. 1–11, [p.2]

³¹⁵ Liebes, Tamar, and Zohar Kampf, “Homullus Medius : Transforming the Logic of Reporting at Crisis,” *Dynamics of Asymmetric Conflict*, Vol. 3, No. 2, July 2010, pp. 86–98.

<http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/17467586.2010.531032> [p. 87]

³¹⁶ Newman, Nic, William H. Dutton, and Grant Blank, “Social Media in the Changing Ecology of News: The Fourth and Fifth Estates in Britain,” *International Journal of Internet Science*, Vol. 7, No. 1, 2012, pp. 6–22. http://www.researchgate.net/publication/228280144_Social_Media_in_the_Changing_Ecology_of_News_The_Fourth_and_Fifth_Estates_in_Britain/file/d912f5140717c673d4.pdf

determination of the story selection process and the incapacity for audiences to question or challenge those selections.”³¹⁷

It should be noted that this does not mean that media professionals, and particularly journalists, are not aware of the problems that contemporary journalism faces. For example, the concept of “public journalism” addresses the problems of mass media journalism by shifting away from the idea of media as the provider of information towards the idea of media as the catalyser of discussion among public actors.³¹⁸ Public journalism aims at reversing the traditional information collection and dissemination patterns in mass media by concentrating on the interests of ordinary citizens instead of elites.³¹⁹ However, critics of public journalism argue that it does not differ from other types of mainstream journalism in essential ways:

Despite its claims, public journalism, working as it does within the market and within long-standing organizational, institutional and professional structures, operates in similar ways to mainstream journalism (of which it is, after all, a part): ‘traditional and public journalisms adopt similar narrative strategies to effect essentially the same ends: placing the power of telling society’s stories in the hands of journalists’ (Woodstock, 2002: 37).³²⁰

Citizen journalism, on the other hand, is assumed to adhere to the notions of “equality” and “inclusion” against “hierarchical, elite-centred notions of journalism as a business.”³²¹ In other words, citizen journalism can be thought as a reaction against the “Big Media” in which the decision-making process excludes most attempts of participation by citizens.³²² According to Gillmor, news approach of mainstream media is like a “lecture,” while new media resembles a “conversation” in which distinction between production and consumption is no longer dominant.³²³ Beers also mention that there is a new line of thought, in which the concept of “emergent democracy” is used to refer to a new trend inversion of power relations in media, which argues for a shift away from the “one to many” approach to sharing of information in the professional journalism towards a “many to many” approach seen in citizen journalism.³²⁴ For example, as outlined in a previous COSMIC report (Deliverable 2.2), in the case of 2013 Gezi Protests in Turkey, individuals who could not be informed about the protests through mainstream media turned their attention to citizen journalism via social media for up-to-date information.³²⁵

In short, emergence of citizen journalism can, at least to some extent, be considered as a result of a “democratic deficit” inherent in mainstream media and professional journalism in its current form. And given that one of the factors that may have created the circumstances that contributed to the emergence of citizen journalism concerns this deficit in access to reporting, a question that has received due attention pertains to whether, and to what extent, citizen

³¹⁷ Goode, Luke, “Social News, Citizen Journalism and Democracy,” *New Media & Society*, Vol. 11, No. 8, November 24, 2009, pp. 1287–1305, [p. 1292]

³¹⁸ Haas, Tanni, and Linda Steiner, “Public Journalism: a Reply to Critics,” *Journalism*, Vol. 7, No. 2, May 1, 2006, pp. 238–254, [p. 239].

³¹⁹ Haas, Tanni, “Civic Mapping as a Public Journalism Tool,” 2008, pp. 1–11 [p. 3]

³²⁰ Atton, Chris, “What Is ‘Alternative’ Journalism?,” *Journalism*, Vol. 4, No. 3, August 1, 2003, pp. 267–272, [p. 268]

³²¹ *Ibid.*, p. 268.

³²² Gillmor, Dan, “We the Media: The Rise of Citizen Journalists,” *National Civic Review*, 2004, pp. 58–63. [p. 60]

³²³ *Ibid.*, p. 60.

³²⁴ Beers, David, “The Public Sphere and Online, Independent Journalism,” *Canadian Journal of Education/Revue Canadienne de L’éducation*, Vol. 29, No. 1, 2006, pp. 109–130, [p. 119]

³²⁵ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., “Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *COSMIC*, 2013.

journalism can offer venues through which access to reporting and information dissemination can be democratized. In order to clarify how citizen journalism differs from professional journalism and mainstream media and to understand how it offers new possibilities for the future of content generation and information dissemination, a detailed discussion on the definition of citizen journalism will be provided in the next section.

4.2.2 Defining citizen journalism

Proliferation of ICTs made important contributions to the abilities of citizens to generate and publish their own content. In its simplest form, the concept of “citizen journalism” refers to this enhanced ability of citizens to write and share their own news stories. However, it is crucial to clarify the concept of “citizen journalism” so that it can be clearly distinguished from professional journalism and other journalism practices such as collaborative journalism and public/civic journalism. In this section, various definitions of citizen journalism will be mentioned and discussed in order to clarify the concept.

There are other concepts which refer to more or less the same phenomena – citizens as creators of content – such as grassroots journalism, participatory journalism, crowd-sourced journalism, etc.³²⁶ Bowman and Willis defines participatory journalism as “the act of a citizen, or group of citizens, playing an active role in the process of collecting, reporting, analyzing and disseminating news and information” and this act involves “little or no editorial oversight or formal journalistic work-flow dictating the decisions of a staff.”³²⁷ While authors prefer the concept of “participatory journalism,” same definition applies to the concept of “citizen journalism”. In this report, concept of “citizen journalism” will be used for reasons of convention.

According to Goode, citizen journalism refers to online journalistic activities of “ordinary” citizens such as “current affairs-based blogging, photo and video sharing, and posting eyewitness commentary on current events” while maintaining that limits of the concept are blurry and both strict and loose definitions of the concept can be generated and employed.³²⁸ According to Jack, main importance of citizen journalism lies in the shift away from the idea of “passive audience” to an “active audience” in terms of production and dissemination of media content.³²⁹ Dugan, Smith and Witt discuss citizen journalism in terms of a “redefinition” of the concepts such as “news” and “journalism:”

From today’s perspective, the ways in which ordinary members of the public— ‘accidental journalists’ in the view of some—engaged in impromptu newsgathering can be interpreted as signifying a tipping-point for online news, not least by opening

³²⁶ Kelly, John, “Red Kayaks and Hidden Gold: The Rise, Challenges and Value of Citizen Journalism,” 2009, [p. 17]

³²⁷ Bowman, Shayne, and Chris Willis, “We Media: How Audiences Are Shaping the Future of News and Information,” *The Media Center at the American Press Institute*, 2003, http://www.hypergene.net/wemedia/download/we_media.pdf , [p. 9].

³²⁸ Goode, Luke, “Social News, Citizen Journalism and Democracy,” *New Media & Society*, Vol. 11, No. 8, November 24, 2009, pp. 1287–1305, [p. 1288].

³²⁹ Jack, Martha, “The Social Evolution of Citizen Journalism,” *Canadian Journal of Media Studies*, Vol. 6, No. 1, 2010, pp. 95–158 [p. 96]

up for redefinition what counts as 'news' and who can be a 'journalist' in ways which continue to reverberate today.³³⁰

Therefore, the concept of "citizen journalism" implies existence of "ordinary" citizens who become "active" in terms of production and dissemination of media content. While it seems obvious enough, it is unclear what "ordinary" means in terms of citizens becoming engaged in journalistic practices. How does the concept of "citizen" create a difference between professional journalism and citizen journalism?

According to Mike Glaser, citizen journalism is defined as follows:

The idea behind citizen journalism is that people without professional journalism training can use the tools of modern technology and the global distribution of the Internet to create, augment or fact-check media on their own or in collaboration with others...³³¹

This definition of citizen journalism clarifies the concept of "ordinary citizen" – those without professional training of journalism –, identifies the main activities and points out the medium – computer and Internet technology – through which these activities occur. It should be pointed out that this definition is a narrow or strict definition of citizen journalism and we should also look at the blurry lines between professional journalism and citizen journalism.

According to Chung and Nah, a collaborative approach in which both citizen journalism and professional journalism contribute to generation of content is possible when both parties accept each other as legitimate sources of information and when they contribute to each other through compensating for each other's weaknesses.³³² Blurred lines between professional journalism and citizen journalism will be discussed in detail in the related section under the subtopic on challenges. In the next section, citizen journalism will be conceptualized as a component of the network society with detailed discussions on various opportunities it provides and challenges it brings.

³³⁰ Allan, Stuart, Prasun Sonwalkar, and Cynthia Carter, "Bearing Witness: Citizen Journalism and Human Rights Issues," *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, Vol. 5, No. 3, November 2007, pp. 373–389, [p. 378].

³³¹ Cited in Dugan, Molly A, Dan Smith, and Leonard Witt, "Journalism Ethics and the Independent Journalist," No. September 2004, 2007, pp. 801–811 [p. 804]

³³² Chung, Deborah S., and Seungahn Nah, "Collaborative, Complementary and Negotiated Journalistic Professionalism: A Case Study of OhmyNews in a Participatory Media Climate," *63rd Annual Conference of the International Communication Association*, London, 2013 [p. 31-2]

4.3 OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR CITIZEN JOURNALISM IN A NETWORKED SOCIETY

The concept of “network society” is defined by Castells as “a society whose social structure is made of networks powered by microelectronics-based information and communication technologies.”³³³ For Castells, a network is composed of communicating nodes and it does not have a centre;³³⁴ therefore, it differs from earlier types of societies in which concepts of “centre” and “periphery” refers to indispensable features of social organization. A network either includes or excludes; and networks either cooperate or compete among themselves.³³⁵ More efficient cooperation or performance within a network may contribute to its competitive power with other networks.³³⁶

The idea of a network society based on ICTs without a centre may contribute to a positive outlook in terms of the relationship between ICTs and democracy; however, we should also be cognizant of the potential to fall into the trap of “mythic thinking” which surrounds much of current discussions about ICTs and the future of democratic institutions.³³⁷ Mainly, there are two competing ideas on the relations between ICTs and democracy: while one approach views ICTs as remarkable tools for enhancing democracy since they allow bottom-up organizations without an all-powerful centre and create wider access to information; the other approach conceptualizes the network society as a surveillance society since ICTs are designed by powerful organizations such as governments and businesses rather than all citizens.³³⁸

Figure 4.2: ICTs, Democracy, Surveillance

As is the case in debates regarding the role that ICTs may play in contemporary democracies, the potential of citizen journalism as a tool for news gathering and dissemination is a highly contested issue. In other words, citizen journalism brings about new opportunities for information dissemination but at the same time poses certain challenges.

³³³ Castells, Manuel, ed., *The Network Society*, Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, UK, 2004. [p. 3]

³³⁴ Ibid, p. 3.

³³⁵ Ibid, pp. 3-4.

³³⁶ Ibid, pp. 3-4.

³³⁷ Mosco, Vincent, *The Digital Sublime: Myth, Power, and Cyberspace*, The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 2004.

³³⁸ Van Dijk, Jan, *The Network Society*, Sage Publications Ltd., London, 2012 [p. 105]

Opportunities brought by the citizen journalism can be discussed in terms of the following:

- Decentralization and democratization of news making
- Witnessing and citizen journalism
- Citizen journalism as the fifth estate

Challenges of citizen journalism can be discussed in terms of the following:

- Digital divide and citizen journalism
- Blurred Lines between Mainstream and Citizen Journalism
- Journalism ethics and citizen journalism

4.3.1 Opportunities

4.3.1.1 Decentralization and democratization of news making

According to van Dijk, “community of Internet” tends to favour a certain form of democracy called “participatory democracy” which is defined on the basis of “socialization of politics” and encouragement of “active citizenship.”³³⁹ In other words, participatory democracy approach criticizes currently established forms of democratic governance in terms of a lack of civic engagement. For van Dijk, Internet is conceptualized as a tool of democracy for the following reasons:

- “An *interactive* medium that departs from the one-sided communication of existing mass media.”
- “An *active* and *creative* medium enabling users to transform from viewers, listeners and readers to participants.”
- “A *direct* medium in which individual users are able to determine, at a distance, what happens in the centre of politics and the mass media, among others.”
- “A *platform* on which everybody is equal in principle as assumed expertise has to prove itself before being accepted.”
- “A *network* medium enabling the collective creation of products online, not primarily by individual authors or businesses.”³⁴⁰

In this respect, research on the use of social media platforms for news dissemination suggests that new technologies may help reshape the ways in which journalism is understood and conducted:

Twitter is one of a range of social media technologies that privileges contribution, conversation, community and connectivity, compared to the hierarchical structures within established news organizations that set the parameters for most news work.³⁴¹

The effect of new technologies of news collection and dissemination led scholars to argue for the emergence of a new media culture based on digital means.³⁴² This concept of new media culture refers to a participatory approach in which citizens assume an active role through

³³⁹ Ibid, pp. 107-8.

³⁴⁰ Ibid, p. 109.

³⁴¹ Hermida, Alfred, Seth C Lewis, and Rodrigo Zamith, “Sourcing the Arab Spring: A Case Study of Andy Carvin’s Sources During the Tunisian and Egyptian Revolutions,” 2012 [p. 11]

³⁴² Cited in, Graham, Todd, “Talking Back, But Is Anyone Listening: Journalism and Comment Fields,” in Chris Peters and Marcel Broersma (eds.), *Rethinking Journalism: Trust and Participation in a Transformed News Landscape*, Routledge, Abingdon, 2013, pp. 114–127 [p. 115]

activities like “(re)creating, challenging, questioning, correcting and personalizing news media” as opposed to a passive role as only recipients of news.³⁴³

In the context of emergencies, a good example for the use of new technologies is the use of hashtags. Messina argues that adoption of a new technological convention, such as Twitter hashtags, depends on “the informational needs and desires of users during an emergency.”³⁴⁴ In other words, a technological convention is accepted to a greater degree if it fulfills the need of information during emergencies and crises.

Microblogging engages bystanders and volunteers in providing continuous updates about different affected locations and developments of crises at particular points of time. Researchers are referring to this as ‘crisis informatics’, highlighting fast, constant and distributed updates through these “backchannel” communications as real and helpful contributions (Palen, Vieweg, Liu, and Hughes, 2009).³⁴⁵

Perng et al. give the example of Twitter use during and after the 2011 Norway attacks in which right-wing extremist Anders Behring Breivik confessed to the attacks which led to 77 deaths and 90 people being injured.³⁴⁶ According to Perng et al., Twitter use during and after the 2011 Norway attacks began with information seeking activities and continued with a search for possibilities of citizen involvement. For instance, citizens were recommended to donate blood for the victims of incidents, victims were recommended to go to Red Cross, and phone numbers were circulated for those who wanted to access to information about their loved ones.³⁴⁷

In addition, using their case study on the use of Twitter hashtag #egypt during the 2011 Egyptian protests, Papacharissi and de Fatima Oliveira propose the idea that citizen journalism offers a new kind of leadership:

#Egypt was energized by several key bloggers, activists, and informed citizens who turned to social networking platforms because other forms of opinion expression were not as accessible, under surveillance, or otherwise regulated. Digital platforms do not rob movements of their leaders. But they do permit a distributed or “crowdsourced” form of leadership based on mechanisms that reward those more involved in mobilization, and the reporting and curating of information, online and offline.³⁴⁸

Therefore, use of social media provides an opportunity not only for more democratic forms of news dissemination, but also in terms of involvement by citizens to the events of crises and emergencies.

Another important contribution of the new technologies in terms of journalism is that participatory journalism activities and approaches have been on the rise for professional

³⁴³ Ibid, p. 115.

³⁴⁴ Cited in, Starbird, Kate, and Jeannie Stamberger, “Tweak the Tweet weLeveraging Microblogging Proliferation with a Prescriptive Syntax to Support Citizen Reporting,” *Proceedings of the 7th International ISCRAM Conference*, Seattle, 2010, pp. 1–5 [p. 2]

³⁴⁵ Perng, Sung-yueh, Monika Büscher, Lisa Wood, Ragnhild Halvorsrud, Michael Stiso, Leonardo Ramirez, and Amro Al-Akkad, “Peripheral Response: Microblogging During the 22/7/2011 Norway Attacks,” *Proceedings of the 9th International ISCRAM Conference*, No., 2012, pp. 1–11. <http://eprints.lancs.ac.uk/id/eprint/61934> [p. 2]

³⁴⁶ Ibid, p. 3.

³⁴⁷ Ibid, p. 4.

³⁴⁸ Papacharissi, Zizi, and Maria de Fatima Oliveira, “Affective News and Networked Publics: The Rhythms of News Storytelling on #Egypt,” *Journal of Communication*, Vol. 62, No. 2, April 23, 2012, pp. 266–282. [p. 279]

journalism,³⁴⁹ as we will discuss in detail on the section on blurring lines between professional journalism and citizen journalism.

4.3.1.2 Witnessing and citizen journalism

In mainstream media, role of “mediation” is assumed by journalists. Consequently, “witnessing,” as we encounter in the mainstream media, is always “socially situated, perspectival and thus politicized.”³⁵⁰ Citizen journalism, on the other hand, may offer new possibilities for the relationship between creators of news content and the recipients through new forms of witnessing that “fosters points of human connection at a distance.”³⁵¹

Possibilities generated by citizen journalism are closely related to new forms of witnessing social events as well as new forms of news dissemination. While witnessing and eye witnessing has always been an important component of journalism, it had to be filtered through processes of prioritization and authentication which create a “discursive politics of mediation.”³⁵² On the other hand, citizen witnessing is creating necessary conditions to “reconfigure this geometry of informational power” via changing the relationship between creators and recipients of news content; and this also creates a challenge for citizen journalism in terms of the harmonization of “human connection” provided by online tools while upholding values of “trust, responsibility, and emphatic engagement.”³⁵³

In the days following the attack on the World Trade Center in New York in 2001, attempts were made to prohibit the people who were thronging to Ground Zero from taking pictures. “Put your cameras away! Show some respect!” yelled a policemen, as visiting professor Marianne Hirsch walked around the site. Yet everyone had a camera.³⁵⁴

The example above illustrates how a technological tool like a camera, which is available to virtually anyone with a cell-phone, may change the nature of witnessing in the digital era. Andén-Papadopoulos conceptualizes this new form of witnessing as “citizen camera-witnessing” which refers to “the ritualized employment of the mobile camera as a personal witnessing device to provide a public record of embodied actions of political dissent for the purpose of persuasion.”³⁵⁵ Thus, citizen camera-witnessing does not claim to be objective and impartial, as it is usually the case in mainstream media.³⁵⁶ While citizen journalism and associated forms of witnessing turns the traditional informational power structure upside down, it does not do so by claiming neutrality or objectivity.

³⁴⁹ Graham, Todd, “Talking Back, But Is Anyone Listening: Journalism and Comment Fields,” in Chris Peters and Marcel Broersma (eds.), *Rethinking Journalism: Trust and Participation in a Transformed News Landscape*, Routledge, Abingdon, 2013, pp. 114–127 [p. 116]

³⁵⁰ Allan, Stuart, Prasun Sonwalkar, and Cynthia Carter, “Bearing Witness: Citizen Journalism and Human Rights Issues,” *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, Vol. 5, No. 3, November 2007, pp. 373–389. [p. 388]

³⁵¹ *Ibid.*, p. 388.

³⁵² Allan, Stuart, “Online News Reporting of Crisis Events: Investigating the Role of Citizen Witnessing,” in Eugenia Siapera and Andreas Veglis (eds.), *The Handbook of Global Online Journalism*, Wiley-Blackwell, West Sussex, 2012, pp. 331–352 [p. 349]

³⁵³ *Ibid.*, p. 349.

³⁵⁴ Becker, Karin E., “Gestures of Seeing : Amateur Photographers in the News,” *63rd Annual Conference of the International Communication Association*, London, 2013 [p. 10]

³⁵⁵ Andén-Papadopoulos, K., “Citizen Camera-Witnessing: Embodied Political Dissent in the Age of ‘Mediated Mass Self-Communication’,” *New Media & Society*, May 31, 2013. [p. 4]

³⁵⁶ Andén-Papadopoulos, K., “Media Witnessing and the ‘Crowd-Sourced Video Revolution’,” *Visual Communication*, Vol. 12, No. 3, July 8, 2013, pp. 341–357.

In traversing binaries such as the private and the public, the body and the machine, the material and the virtual, the journalist and the citizen, the mobile camera phone is extending and modifying media languages, practices, and forms.³⁵⁷

Citizen journalism, in the context of citizen camera-witnessing and the wide availability of mobile cameras, is a result of both new technology that has become widely available and political demands which transcend traditional power structures embedded in media and other institutions.

4.3.1.3 Citizen journalism as the “Fifth Estate”

The concept of citizen witnessing also underlines the potential of citizen journalism to challenge existing power hierarchies concerning the relationship between those who are “being watched” and those who “do the watching.” Namely, as Bennett argues, while the concept of surveillance refers to a relationship of “watching” and “being watched” that is primarily characterized by organizations monitoring individuals’ activities, in contemporary societies, partly as a result of wearable and mobile technologies, the act of watching “embraces a range of practices where the individual monitors the organization”.³⁵⁸ The concept of “sousveillance” (composed of French words *sous* (below) and *veiller* (to watch)), which was also discussed in the previous chapter, refers to these activities through which people observe those in authority: an inverse panopticon.³⁵⁹

Likewise, with its emphasis on participatory democracy and citizen camera-witnessing, citizen journalism offers a way for citizens to watch those in authority even more closely than they were able to do through mainstream media. This potential of citizen journalism has been noted by commentators who proclaim the rise of a “Fifth Estate” that both supplements and checks the “Fourth Estate” (i.e., mass media):

Users can source their own information, independent of any single institution, using the capabilities provided by search and social media. Also users can create content in many forms – like blogs, email, tweets, comments on websites – that provide even greater independence from other institutions and offer a mechanism whereby public opinion can be directly expressed. This content can bypass or be amplified by the traditional mass media of the Fourth Estate, but in doing so it can fulfil many of the same functions of holding up the activities of government, business and other institutions to the light of a networked public. Thus the Fifth Estate is also a potentially potent political force, but without the centralized institutional foundations of the Fourth Estate.³⁶⁰

Hence, decentralized nature of the new media are their main difference from the mainstream media in which processes of news production and dissemination are always conducted within a centralized structure. An example to both the decentralized nature of new media and sousveillance is the dissemination of video recording of the death of Neda Agha-Soltan who was shot during the protests against the results of 2009 Iranian presidential elections.³⁶¹

³⁵⁷ Reading, Anna, “Mobile Witnessing: Ethics and the Camera Phone in the ‘War on Terror’,” *Globalizations*, Vol. 6, No. 1, March 2009, pp. 61–76. [p. 63]

³⁵⁸ Bennett, Colin J., *The Privacy Advocates: Resisting the Spread of Surveillance*, The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 2008 [p. 12].

³⁵⁹ Mann, Steve, Jason Nolan, and Barry Wellman, “Sousveillance: Inventing and Using Wearable Computing Devices for Data Collection in Surveillance Environments.,” *Surveillance & Society*, Vol. 1, No. 3, 2003, pp. 331–355, [p. 332]

³⁶⁰ Newman, Nic, William H. Dutton, and Grant Blank, “Social Media in the Changing Ecology of News: The Fourth and Fifth Estates in Britain,” *International Journal of Internet Science*, Vol. 7, No. 1, 2012, pp. 6–22, [p. 7].

³⁶¹ Jean-Gabriel Ganascia, “The Generalized Sousveillance Society,” *Social Science Information*, Vol. 49, No. 3, August 23, 2010, pp. 489–507, [p. 494]

Dissemination of such recording, which, as discussed in the previous chapter, helped maintain the momentum of the opposition movement in Iran, would be much less possible through centralized channels of news making since they can be controlled by totalitarian regimes.³⁶²

The analysis of centralized structure of mainstream media should not be limited to totalitarian regimes; commercial aspect of mainstream media must also be emphasized to fully understand the challenge that citizen journalists pose to the centralized/hierarchical mainstream media. According to Bowman and Willis, mainstream media are based on commercial activity which is pursued by hierarchical organizations such as companies and conglomerates; therefore, they focus on advertising and profitable activities in contrast to citizen journalism which prioritizes other concerns such as conversational, collaborative and egalitarian principles over concerns on profitability issues.³⁶³

Intersection of business and government interests can lead to biased and selective reports and under-representation or disregard of events as mentioned in the *Amnesty International* report on Gezi Park protests:

Journalists working for national media often faced pressure to refrain from critical reporting of the authorities' response to the Gezi Park protests by editors and media owners with strong business links to the government. The Journalists Union of Turkey reported on 22 July that 59 journalists had lost their jobs in relation to coverage of the Gezi Park protests, with 22 being fired and 37 journalists forced to resign.³⁶⁴

This example shows how concern for profitability—in association with strong links to the government in the cited example—combined with centralized editorial control over coverage of journalists can lead to decay in the role of media as the Fourth Estate. Under conditions of misrepresentation and lack of attention, Gezi Park protesters turned to social media to be informed about the events and to be able to express their views.³⁶⁵

4.3.2 Challenges

In this section, challenges that are faced by the emergent forms of citizen journalism will be defined and discussed. The challenges addressed in this report are the digital divide, blurred lines between mainstream and citizen journalism, and ethics of citizen journalism.

4.3.2.1 Digital divide and citizen journalism

Digital divide is defined as “the gap between individuals, households, businesses and geographic areas at different socio-economic levels with regard both to their opportunities to access information and communication technologies (ICTs) and to their use of the Internet for a wide variety of activities” and it may refer to the gap within societies as well as between societies.³⁶⁶ Selwyn and Facer argue that understanding of the digital divide should go beyond the simple dichotomy of users and non-users and should be extended to include other

³⁶² Ibid, p. 494.

³⁶³ Bowman, Shayne, and Chris Willis, “We Media: How Audiences Are Shaping the Future of News and Information,” *The Media Center at the American Press Institute*, 2003.

http://www.hypergene.net/wemedia/download/we_media.pdf [p. 12]

³⁶⁴ Cited in Amnesty International, *Gezi Park Protests: Brutal Denial of the Right to Peaceful Assembly in Turkey*, London, 2013. <http://www.amnesty.org.tr/ai/system/files/GeziParkiEN.pdf> [p. 49-50]

³⁶⁵ Ibid, p. 50.

³⁶⁶ OECD, *Understanding the Digital Divide*, 2001 [p. 5]

dimensions such as users who are unable to use new technologies adequately in order to access to, share and create information.³⁶⁷

During protests following the Iranian 2009 election Twitter permitted communication despite state censorship of other media coverage and access, affording citizens opportunities to publish information and broadcast news, audio, and video account to othermedia and the worldwatching. Nonetheless, these opportunities were limited to those with access to Twitter and the skills to use it as well as by the risks created by the government's online censorship and surveillance. In fact, the majority of tweets during the postelection protests came from outside the country, with only few updates coming from influential individuals inside the country (Christensen, 2009).³⁶⁸

Social groups which are more likely to be excluded from online tools and services include low income groups, the unemployed, the disabled people, rural communities and regions with few population.³⁶⁹ In addition, women, especially those in the low income groups, are less likely to use Internet than men.³⁷⁰

A recent report on digital divide by *The Economist Intelligence Unit* shows that there is an upwards trend in terms of worldwide Internet use while the gap between the “developed” world and the “developing” world continues to exist. As mentioned in the report, percentage of people who use the Internet rose from 50.9 in 2005 to 76.8 in 2013 in the developed world while the Internet use rose from 7.8% in 2005 to 30.7% in 2013 in the developing world. In total, worldwide Internet use has risen from 15.8% in 2005 to 38.8% in 2013.³⁷¹ However, as mentioned in the report, digital divide has declined only in the narrow sense of access, while the divide with regard to usage has deepened to include challenges of increasing quality of access and ability to use online tools and services.³⁷²

“Great amounts of people are only online in a narrow fashion and not making full use of what's available on the web,” adds Mr Richardson. His organisation conducted a survey together with the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) and found that over one in five (21%) people in the UK don't have the skills or ability to communicate via email, use a search engine or conduct transactions online. Whether businesses and consumers have the capability—and interest—to conduct useful services or enhance their situation is the next frontier in bridging the digital divide.³⁷³

In other words, digital divide continues to matter especially in terms of the quality of use with regard to digital literacy and usage of online tools and services as well as in terms of access to ICTs especially in the developing world.

Digital divide is an important challenge to consider when thinking about new media and citizen journalism, since it implies that not all segments of the population benefit from them equally. In other words, we should be aware that new media content is mostly available to those who have access to ICTs and to those who are able to use these technologies adequately

³⁶⁷ Selwyn, N, and K Facer, *Beyond the Digital Divide: Rethinking Digital Inclusion for the 21st Century*, 2007. <http://eprints.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/6220> [p. 12]

³⁶⁸ Papacharissi, Zizi, and Maria de Fatima Oliveira, “Affective News and Networked Publics: The Rhythms of News Storytelling on #Egypt,” *Journal of Communication*, Vol. 62, No. 2, April 23, 2012, pp. 266–282, [p. 269].

³⁶⁹ Ernest-Jones, Terry, *Closing Europe's Digital Divide*, 2008.

³⁷⁰ *Ibid*, p. 8.

³⁷¹ Andreasson, Kim, *Redefining the Digital Divide*, 2013 [p. 8]

³⁷² *Ibid*, p. 6.

³⁷³ *Ibid*, p. 8-9.

at least to follow online news sources such as blogs and social network sites (SNSs) and bypass filters that could impede on their ability to do so.

4.3.2.2 Blurred lines between mainstream and citizen journalism: follow the leader?

In their study on Andy Carvin, a senior strategist on online communities at National Public Radio in USA, and his use of Twitter during 2011 Tunisian and Egyptian demonstrations, Hermida, Lewis, and Zamith point to a new direction in the ways in which journalism may be conducted in the future: mainstream journalists who use a broader group of sources via social media to conduct “near real-time reporting.”³⁷⁴ Hermida et al. argue that:

In light of our findings, Carvin emerges as a central node in a networked media environment—one trusted to authenticate, interpret, and contextualize information flows on social awareness streams, drawing on a distributed and networked newsroom where knowledge and expertise are fluid, dynamic and hybrid.³⁷⁵

According to this research, a form of synthesis between mainstream reporting and citizen journalism seems to have been formed in the case of Andy Carvin. Namely, we see a professional journalist who somehow filters the “chaotic” flows of information generated in the social media through processes of authentication and contextualization in order to make that information useful for his followers.

Figure 4.3: Synthesis of Citizen Journalism and Mainstream Media

Carvin’s activities via social media, as a “member of professional news media,” included tweeting, giving links to images published online by demonstrators, generating discussions on social media and asking his followers on Twitter to help him interpret the information he has.³⁷⁶ While such a synthesis achieved by Carvin points to a “new paradigm of sourcing” in mainstream media, particularity of the case must also be taken into account.³⁷⁷

³⁷⁴ Hermida, Alfred, Seth C Lewis, and Rodrigo Zamith, “Sourcing the Arab Spring: A Case Study of Andy Carvin’s Sources During the Tunisian and Egyptian Revolutions,” 2012 [p. 11]

³⁷⁵ Ibid, p. 11.

³⁷⁶ Ibid, p. 4.

³⁷⁷ Ibid, p. 11.

Likewise, Newman, Dutton, and Blank underline the formation of an “ecology of media” (or “ecology of news production and consumption”) which incorporates elements from both mainstream media and social media instead of seeing them as two competing elements.³⁷⁸

On the other hand, others conceptualize citizen journalism as a “movement” that has “intrinsically oppositional characteristics” in their relationship towards mainstream media in the sense that citizen journalism aims at being an alternative to corporate media by being independent from it. Accordingly, the chances that citizen journalism and mainstream corporate media to form an alliance is often seen to be slim.³⁷⁹ However, Goode argues that citizen journalism is not completely independent from commerce and advertising activities and even when such independence is achieved, rules of mainstream media may continue to affect citizen journalism practices; thus, “the incorporation of citizen journalism practices by traditional news organizations” is worth investigating both as a challenge and an opportunity.³⁸⁰

According to Volkmer and Firdaus, mainstream media track content generated via social media with a cautious approach. They argue that professional journalists decide to use social media content when they are unable to collect data through traditional channels.³⁸¹ They give the example of countries such as Iran in which professional journalists from other countries may be banned in cases of civil unrest. Likewise, the planning editor of *Al Jazeera English* reports that since they did not have permission to gather information in Iran during the Green Revolution political protests in 2009, they had to rely on information disseminated via social media.³⁸² Volkmer and Firdaus add that journalists working at small bureaus, rather than those who work at newsrooms with enough resources, tend to choose content generated in social media in order to fill the gap caused by the inadequate number of journalists at hand.³⁸³

Volkmer and Firdaus also argue that “journalistic adoption of user-driven new media is not so much ‘innovation’ as it is ‘incorporation’ into existing journalistic practices.”³⁸⁴ Confirming this argument, a producer for *Al Jazeera English* explains that they use user-generated content (UGC), like pictures posted by Twitter users, to support the content of the shows; hence, social media content is treated as “supplement or complement to journalistic news reporting.”³⁸⁵

If UGC providers produce content that does not meet these conditions, or if their practices are incompatible with newswork, they are less likely to participate in the news process. Power then lies with those who can shape these customs and define appropriate practices; by and large these people remain journalists. Nonetheless, models of collaboration do give UGC providers mutual knowledge of the conditions their content should meet to make it into the evening news. As some journalists acknowledge, these models also open a window of

³⁷⁸ Newman, Nic, William H. Dutton, and Grant Blank, “Social Media in the Changing Ecology of News: The Fourth and Fifth Estates in Britain,” *International Journal of Internet Science*, Vol. 7, No. 1, 2012, pp. 6–22, [p. 18].

³⁷⁹ Goode, Luke, “Social News, Citizen Journalism and Democracy,” *New Media & Society*, Vol. 11, No. 8, November 24, 2009, pp. 1287–1305, [p. 1289]

³⁸⁰ *Ibid*, p. 1289.

³⁸¹ Volkmer, Ingrid, and Amira Firdaus, “Between Networks and ‘Hierarchies of Credibility’: Navigating Journalistic Practice in a Sea of User-Generated Content,” in Chris Peters and Marcel Broersma (eds.), *Rethinking Journalism: Trust and Participation in a Transformed News Landscape*, Routledge, Abingdon, 2013, pp. 101–113 [p. 105]

³⁸² *Ibid*, p. 106.

³⁸³ *Ibid*, p. 106.

³⁸⁴ *Ibid*, p. 106.

³⁸⁵ *Ibid*, p. 107.

opportunity: If UGC providers skilfully include their message in compatible package, they may be able to shape the news agenda.³⁸⁶

This discussion underlines a key problem with respect to the blurring relationship between mainstream media and citizen journalism: it is characterized by an asymmetrical power relationship between “top-down logic of cross-platform content dissemination and multi-platform newsgathering” and “the bottom-up use of various platforms and technologies to influence the flow of information and gain voice.”³⁸⁷ In other words, the existence of user-generated content in conventional channels seems possible only when the content fits the needs of the mainstream media.

A related dimension of the challenges brought about by the blurred lines between mainstream media and citizen journalism is about the working conditions in the media industry:

On the one hand, readers have the wherewithal to become producers of news, ideas, and original reflexivity, and so they potentially have become competitors for both editors and journalists (within the limits of their individual competence); but on the other they potentially have become unpaid, external content producers.³⁸⁸

According to Fortunati et al., replacement of professional journalists with citizen journalists devoid of professional rights and job security is important in terms of the future of employment conditions in the media industry.³⁸⁹ More importantly, as Waldman points out, this change in the employment conditions also implicate the process of news production in ways that directly contradict with the *raison d'être* of citizen journalism:

“Newspapers, local TV stations, and local radio stations employ fewer reporters now than they used to, and many of those that have survived have become more like 1930s wire service reporters —filing rapidly and frequently, doing fewer interviews, and spending less time pressing for information. This has resulted in a shift in the balance of power—away from citizens, toward powerful institutions. The watchdog reporter hates a press release; the busy reporter often loves it.”³⁹⁰

When there are less reporters, the reporters have less time to elaborate on the material they have; hence, they increasingly depend on official press releases. The fewer number of reporters is also combined with the pressure to publish faster which results in reliance on official account of the events.³⁹¹

To sum up, the emergence of a new ecology of media in which both professional journalists and citizen journalists have certain functions pose challenges for the future of mainstream media and new media alike. On one hand, there is the issue of incorporation of user-generated content into mainstream media which blurs the line between professional journalism and citizen journalism; and on the other, there is the issue of replacement of professional

³⁸⁶ Hänska-Ahy, Maximillian T., and Roxanna Shapour, “Who’s Reporting the Protests?,” *Journalism Studies*, February 9, 2012, pp. 1–17, [p. 14]

³⁸⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 4.

³⁸⁸ Fortunati, Leopoldina, Mauro Sarrica, John O’Sullivan, Aukse Balcytiene, Halliki Harro-Loit, Phil Macgregor, Nayia Roussou, Ramón Salaverría, and Federico de Luca, “The Influence of the Internet on European Journalism,” *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, Vol. 14, No. 4, July 2009, pp. 928–963, [p. 935].

³⁸⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 935.

³⁹⁰ Waldman, Steven, “The Media Food Chain and the Functions of Journalism,” *The Information Needs of Communities: The Changing Media Landscape in a Broadband Age*, Carolina Academic Press, Durham, NC, 2011, pp. 242–247 [p. 244]

³⁹¹ *Ibid.*, p. 244.

journalists with an unpaid labour force devoid of any kind of job security, which may result in a further decline in investigative reporting.

4.3.2.3 Journalism ethics and citizen journalism

While professional journalists are bound by certain ethical and legal rules, ordinary citizens who do not carry the responsibilities of a professional journalist but who are involved in journalistic activities raise a number of ethical questions.

First, as Riaz and Pasha argue, most citizen journalists are not aware of ethical codes followed by traditional media, they are not professionally trained in reporting, and their reports may not be credible and reliable enough in some instances.³⁹² Likewise, according to Jewitt, an important problem in citizen journalism pertains to the reliability of information:

In regimes where or during times when media are controlled, inaccessible, or not trusted, platforms like Twitter permit individuals to bypass traditional gatekeepers and contribute directly to the news process. However, these instances also expose temporal incompatibilities between Twitter as a news platform and the conventions of journalism. For instance, during the 2008 terrorist attacks in Mumbai, Twitter was useful in communicating breaking news, but also exposed the risks associated with reporting rumor as fact (Jewitt, 2009).³⁹³

In the context of social media use in emergencies, the problem posed by reliability of information is enhanced due to the limited time the respondents have to make decisions and use resources accordingly.³⁹⁴ As stated by Perng et al., “critical challenge for responders is the uncertainty dilemma – the need to balance urgent deployment of resources with the need for thorough evaluation of a situation.”³⁹⁵

According to Liebes and Kampf, immediacy is the most important aspect of newsgathering and news sharing in news Web logs; hence, reliability of information may not always be ensured.³⁹⁶ Liebes and Kampf give the example of rumours that spread after the “Defense Shield” operation in the West Bank in which 13 Israeli soldiers were killed and mainstream media could not report on the issue until families of the soldiers were informed.³⁹⁷

One solution proposed to overcome the problem of information reliability in citizen journalism, and particularly within the context of reporting during emergencies, is the extension of collaboration between citizen journalists and traditional media. Accordingly, citizen journalism should benefit from the institutional aspects of mainstream media through a close collaboration.³⁹⁸

³⁹² Riaz, Saqib, and Saadia Anwar Pasha, “Role of Citizen Journalism in Strengthening Societies,” *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, Vol. 5, No. 1, 2011, pp. 88–103 [p. 101]

³⁹³ Papacharissi, Zizi, and Maria de Fatima Oliveira, “Affective News and Networked Publics: The Rhythms of News Storytelling on #Egypt,” *Journal of Communication*, Vol. 62, No. 2, April 23, 2012, pp. 266–282, [p. 269].

³⁹⁴ Perng, Sung-yueh, Monika Büscher, Lisa Wood, Ragnhild Halvorsrud, Michael Stiso, Leonardo Ramirez, and Amro Al-Akkad, “Peripheral Response: Microblogging During the 22/7/2011 Norway Attacks,” *Proceedings of the 9th International ISCRAM Conference*, No. April, 2012, pp. 1–11. <http://eprints.lancs.ac.uk/id/eprint/61934> [p. 9]

³⁹⁵ *Ibid*, p. 9.

³⁹⁶ Liebes, Tamar, and Zohar Kampf, “Homullus Medius edTransforming the Logic of Reporting at Crisis,” *Dynamics of Asymmetric Conflict*, Vol. 3, No. 2, July 2010, pp. 86–98, [p. 89].

³⁹⁷ *Ibid*, p. 89.

³⁹⁸ Riaz, Saqib, and Saadia Anwar Pasha, “Role of Citizen Journalism in Strengthening Societies,” *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, Vol. 5, No. 1, 2011, pp. 88–103 [p. 101-2]

There is an approach, which is used by citizen journalism websites like OhMyNews.com and NowPublic.com, called “tier 1.5 approach” which refers to cooperation between professional and citizen journalists in the fact-checking and editing processes.³⁹⁹ A potential problem with this approach is that it may reduce the claim of citizen journalism to be bottom-up, democratic and non-commercial; yet, this approach has the potential to “allow citizen journalism to become more acceptable to a mainstream audience and co-exist comfortably with traditional journalism.”⁴⁰⁰

White and Fu argue that people in crisis situations are more likely to believe in consistent content across different media.⁴⁰¹ Therefore, actors (for example, readers of online sources) in crises are themselves looking for reliable information and they check multiple news sources with this aim. For such strategy to be successful, variety in terms of new sources is needed and citizen journalism and mainstream media can provide such variety, even in the absence of the aforementioned forms of collaboration between citizen and professional journalists.

Moreover, especially in certain online platforms such as blogs, citizen journalists inevitably produce practices and rules that act as ethical guidelines:

...in the blogging culture, there is something resembling the ethics of journalism: “Blogging has the following virtues: candour, a sense of humour, intellectual honesty (in the sense of confessing immediately and openly to mistakes), and an open-mindedness to different points of view” (Mooney, 2003). Thirty-five percent of US bloggers often include links to the original sources for their stories and state that they spend extra time checking the facts they want to include in a post (Lenhart and Fox, 2006).⁴⁰²

The conversational nature of the publication platforms that citizen journalists use provide additional incentives for fact checking: citizen journalists face the risk of being confronted by their followers when there is a suspicion of false reporting. As stated by Bowman and Willis, the logic of operation in citizen journalism is “publish, then filter” in contrast to “filter, then publish” which is found in the mainstream media.⁴⁰³

The culture of citizenry modelled online, therefore, is one where news is not passively received, but is challenged, corrected, embroidered and, through individual agency, rippled outwards into the society.⁴⁰⁴

Given these considerations regarding the definition of citizen journalism and how it may be different from or similar to practices of journalists working in the mainstream media, the next two sections of this chapter will focus on the results of a content analysis and in-depth interviews focusing on the implications of these considerations on citizen journalistic coverage of emergencies.

³⁹⁹ Jack, Martha, “The Social Evolution of Citizen Journalism,” *Canadian Journal of Media Studies*, Vol. 6, No. 1, 2010, pp. 95–158 [p. 107]

⁴⁰⁰ Ibid, p. 107.

⁴⁰¹ White, James D., and King-Wa Fu, “Who Do You Trust? Comparing People-Centered Communications in Disaster Situations in the United States and China,” *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice*, No. June 2013, 2012, pp. 37–41, [p. 138].

⁴⁰² Cited in, Domingo, D, and A Heinonen, “Weblogs and Journalism,” *Nordicom Review*, Vol. 29, 2008, pp. 3–15, [p. 8].

⁴⁰³ Cited in Bowman, Shayne, and Chris Willis, “We Media: How Audiences Are Shaping the Future of News and Information,” *The Media Center at the American Press Institute*, 2003.
http://www.hypergene.net/wemedia/download/we_media.pdf [p. 12]

⁴⁰⁴ Beers, David, “The Public Sphere and Online, Independent Journalism,” *Canadian Journal of Education/Revue Canadienne de L'éducation*, Vol. 29, No. 1, 2006, pp. 109–130, [p. 119].

4.4 CONTENT ANALYSIS

In this section, we will summarize findings from a content analysis of citizen journalist articles published about the following four emergencies that were discussed in detail in Deliverable 2.2 of the COSMIC project:⁴⁰⁵ Gezi Protests in Turkey, Boston Bombings, Xynthia Storm (Europe), Haiti Earthquake. Based on issues discussed earlier in this chapter about the definition of citizen journalism and opportunities and challenges that citizen journalists face when reporting an emergency, the section will focus on the balance between news and commentary in citizen journalism content about emergencies, sources of information and the types of frames citizen journalists utilize when covering emergencies.

4.4.1 Content analysis procedures

The content analysis was performed on citizen journalist articles that were retrieved online from blogs of individuals and/or citizen journalist portals like *allvoices.com* or *digitaljournal.com*. For each emergency event, first a list of potential citizen journalist sites or blogs was created. From this list, four citizen journalists were randomly selected for each event and for each citizen journalist, depending on availability of articles (henceforth called entries), four or five entries were randomly selected. This resulted in 88 entries to be content analyzed in total.

Rather than analyzing each entry as a single unit of analysis, which would have resulted in less detail, we decided to use “paragraphs” as a unit of analysis. This resulted in 878 units (paragraphs) to be coded by three independent coders who were trained for this purpose. The distribution of the paragraphs by events is summarized in Figure 4.4. In cases when the entry contained a block quotation or an image, they were coded as part of the paragraph they followed.

Figure 4.4: Proportion of Units Analysed by Event

⁴⁰⁵ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., “Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *COSMIC*, 2013

Appendix 1 contains a copy of the Content Analysis Coding Instructions document. As can be seen from this document, the analysis focused on the following variables:

- The balance between information vs. commentary
- Types of news sources utilized (e.g., mainstream media, wire services, identified news sources).
- Use of supporting audio-visuals
- Quotations and citations of key news sources
- Targets and sources of criticism (i.e., who voices criticism about whom)
- Reporting of emotions
- Utilization of episodic vs. thematic frames

4.4.2 Main findings

4.4.2.1 Balance: straight news vs. commentary

One salient issue that the previous sections of this chapter have discussed about what constitutes citizen journalism pertains to the extent to which citizen journalists balance providing news or updates (information) and commentary or opinions.

Figure 4.5 summarizes the balance between commentary and straight news. The results suggest that in general, while citizen journalists frequently provide commentaries/opinions (34%), they nevertheless primarily engage in provision of straight news (66%).

Figure 4.5: Straight News vs. Commentary

Note: $\chi^2(3, N = 877) = 196.112, p < .001$

The only event within which commentaries (63%) were more prominent than straight news (37%) was the Gezi Protests in Turkey. As discussed in Deliverable 2.2 of the COSMIC project,⁴⁰⁶ this may partly be due to the politically polarizing nature of the protests and media

⁴⁰⁶ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., "Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations", *COSMIC*, 2013

users' disillusionment with the perceived bias in the sense making function of the mainstream mass media.

4.4.2.2 News sources and citizen journalism witnessing

As discussed in the previous sections, according to many commentators, an important potential benefit of citizen journalism is its ability to democratize access by providing voice to alternative sources of information (including the citizen journalist as a witness). As such, this part of the discussion will provide some key findings regarding the types of information sources that were utilized by the citizen journalists.

Figure 4.6, summarizes the extent to which various sources of information were utilized. Accordingly, citizen journalists often (30%) provided firsthand updates about events that were transpiring. This is indicative of the prevalence of “witnessing” as an element of citizen journalism during emergencies.

Also important to note is that, we see that mainstream media sources like television or news sites (8%) and wire services (8%), while not dominant, are still frequently utilized by citizen journalists.

Figure 4.6: Information Sources

Finally, the most frequently utilized sources were identified news sources (38%). These may include citizens, experts, organizations (government agencies, companies, NGOs) that are quoted or cited as information sources. Next, we will discuss the breakdown of the types of news sources that are included in this category of “news source - identified”.

As can be seen from Figure 4.7, much like in mainstream media,⁴⁰⁷ in citizen journalist articles, government representatives tend to get higher voice than other potential news sources, with 24% of the units citing government sources and a further 19% quoting them. Following government representatives, NGOs are also given a high standing with 16% of the units containing an information source citing NGOs and a further 12% quoting them.

However, an indication of what may be considered as a “democratization” of access is the extent to which citizens are cited or quoted as information sources. Namely, our data suggests that citizen journalists tend to give voice to private citizens as “witnesses” (10% cites, 7%

⁴⁰⁷ Manning, Paul, *News and News Sources: A Critical Introduction*, London: Sage Publications, 2001.

quotes), as “protestors” (9% cites, 6% quotes), and as “victims” of emergencies (8% cites, 7% quotes). Combined together, these numbers mean that about 27% of paragraphs containing an identified information source cited citizens and another 20% quoted citizens. This suggests that in citizen journalism coverage, citizens get higher standing (being quoted and being cited) than any other information source.

Figure 4.7: Distribution of Sources for “News Sources – Identified” Category

As discussed in the previous sections, a distinguishing characteristic of citizen journalism coverage may be the “witnessing” element (i.e., the citizen journalist providing firsthand account of an event). And in Figure 4.6, we observed that witnessing constituted 30% of the potential sources of information for citizen journalists. In Figure 4.8, we compare the occurrence of “witnessing” across different emergencies.

Figure 4.8: Comparison of Citizen Journalist “Witnessing” by Event

Note: $\chi^2(3, N = 877) = 206.174, p < .001$

As it can be seen from Figure 4.8, Gezi Protests stand out as the crisis the coverage of which was predominantly driven by “witnessing”. This should not be surprising since, as discussed in Deliverable 1.1.,⁴⁰⁸ unlike natural disasters and man-made crises like terrorism, which usually are much less predictable in terms of where/when an event is going to transpire, protests are typically characterized by gathering and clashes in a limited number of, typically symbolically significant, spaces. Also, protests are typically going to have more sustained continuity than other emergencies (such as a bombing). Both of these factors make it more likely for witnessing to be more intentional (and considerably easier in terms of determining when to be where) than other emergencies, which may explain the higher proportion of “witnessing” during Gezi Protests.

Also related to witnessing is the extent to which a citizen journalist utilizes audio-visuals to substantiate a claim. The sources of such audio-visuals may include other citizens, mainstream media, or, as discussed in the preceding sections, increasingly, audio-visuals recorded by the citizen journalists. As can be seen from Figure 4.9, in a way that is very similar to the data about “witnessing” as a source of information, use of audio-visuals were much more prominent for coverage of Gezi Protests. Although we have not engaged in a systematic analysis of these images, we observed that many of these audio-visuals (including photographs) were related to the sousveillance function mentioned above and contained content that citizen journalists may have used to substantiate claims about police violence during the protests (e.g., injured citizens, police aiming gas canisters directly at protestors).

Figure 4.9: Use of Audio Visual Proofs in “Witnessing” by Event

Note: $\chi^2(6, N = 259) = 53.906, p < .001$

4.4.2.3 Sense Making and Framing in Emergency Reporting by Citizen Journalists

As mentioned in the introduction section of this chapter, one important consequence of the interactive nature of new media technologies is their ability to allow individuals to be heard when they voice their opinions. Accordingly, citizen journalism may be a key outlet for the dissemination of opinions, or more appropriately, alternative ways of making sense of

⁴⁰⁸ Watson, Hayley et al., “Deliverable 1.1: Report on security crises with high societal impact”, *COSMIC*, 1 April 2013.

events.⁴⁰⁹ In this section we will report some of the key findings regarding the potential components of such sense-making in citizen journalism: criticism, reporting of emotions and choices of framing.

4.4.2.3.1 Criticism

Figure 4.10 summarizes the targets of criticism in citizen journalist entries. Accordingly, government organizations are most frequently criticized (27%), followed by media institutions (7%) and NGOs (5%).

Figure 4.10: Targets of Criticism

As shown in Figure 4.11, when we compare the four events in terms of the criticism directed towards media and government institutions, we see that almost half of the coded paragraphs coded for Gezi Protests contained criticism of government institutions and than a further one fifth of the paragraphs contained criticism of media institutions. This was followed by Xynthia Storm, within which one-third of the coded paragraphs contained criticisms directed at government institutions.

Figure 4.11: Criticism of Media and Government by Event

Note: $\chi^2(6, N = 876) = 88.970, p < .001$

⁴⁰⁹ Goode, Luke, “Social news, citizen journalism and democracy,” *New Media & Society*, Vol. 11, No. 8, pp. 1287-1305.

We further see, as summarized in Figure 4.12, that citizen journalists' own statements are the most frequently occurring type of criticism voiced (21%), followed by criticisms raised by politicians (19%). However, unlike the results we observed with respect to information sources, whereby citizens had considerable voice, citizen journalists seem to have given little space to criticisms raised by private citizens (5%).

Figure 4.12: Sources of Criticism

4.4.2.3.2 Expression of Emotions

While mainstream journalism is typically characterized by the need to provide detached (neutral) coverage of events, the editorial freedom of citizen journalists may be more conducive to communication of emotions as a form of sense-making. With this expectation, using a seven-point scale ranging from 0 (not at all) to 6 (very much), we coded each paragraph with respect to the extent to which it expressed negative emotions such as sadness, anger, frustration.

Contrary to our expectations, we found that articles written by citizen journalists did not contain much expression of negative emotions ($M = 1.31$; $SD = 1.67$). Yet, like our findings with respect to criticism, we found that citizen journalists were more likely to express negative emotions while reporting Gezi Protests ($M = 2.12$; $SD = 1.4$) and the aftermath of Storm Xynthia ($M = 1.25$; $SD = 1.5$) $F(3,864) = 43.817$; $p < .000$.

Another key finding with regards to reporting of negative emotions concerns the attributions made by the citizen journalists as the source of the negative emotions (Figure 4.13). Interestingly, expression of negative emotions is most frequently done in a way that attributes these emotions to the generalized public (23%). Or more precisely, negative emotions are often expressed as the collective emotion of the public, thus making, albeit implicitly, a claim regarding citizen journalists' ability as a gauge of public's sentiments and their sense-making capacities.

Attributions made to the collective sentiments of the public are followed by attributions of negative emotions to individuals or organizations that are identified by the citizen journalists (14%). Finally, the data suggests that although citizen journalists engage in considerable

amount of criticism of institutions, they still try to adopt a detached writing style that refrains from reporting their own emotions

Figure 4.13: Source of Emotions

4.4.2.3.3 Episodic vs. Thematic Framing

Literature on journalism underlines the role that news frames play as organizing structures of news and how they influence the ways in which readers think about an issue.⁴¹⁰ To date, media studies have frequently focused on the extent and potential effects of utilization of “thematic” vs. “episodic” frames in news media.⁴¹¹

Iyengar defines episodic frames as those focusing on a concrete, isolated event and thematic frames as those which discuss issues in a way that describes the context and not just the incident. According to Iyengar, the choice of episodic frames can have an impact on readers' interpretations about causal and treatment responsibility. Namely, by focusing on the bigger picture, thematic frames can help readers make sense of the factors that may have contributed to the incident (e.g., not just that an earthquake happened in Haiti but also why it claimed so many lives and created so much damage). Research also indicates that with respect to issues such as race relations, poverty, terrorism, mainstream news media has often utilized episodic frames.⁴¹² In many respects, use of episodic frames can be considered to be more in line with the commercially driven, detached “just the facts” approach of mainstream news institutions.⁴¹³

To the extent that citizen journalists are less likely to be driven by commercial imperatives or face editorial pressure about writing conventions (e.g., neutrality, inverted pyramid), both of which may limit the choice of frames, a question that needs to be addressed concerns whether this freedom translates into utilization of thematic frames that can be crucial in sense-making. To address this question we coded each paragraph as being either predominantly “episodic” or as “thematic”. The results are shown in Figure 4.14. Accordingly, we observe that while 31% of the paragraphs that were coded utilized a thematic frame, this was largely attributable to the coverage of Gezi Park protests (72%). On the other hand, coverage of Haiti

⁴¹⁰ Entman, Robert. M. “Framing: toward clarification of a fractured paradigm,” *Journal of Communication*, Vol. 43, 1993, pp.51-58.

⁴¹¹ Iyengar, Shanto. *Is Anyone Responsible? How Television Frames Political Issues*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1991.

⁴¹² *Ibid*, p. 3.

⁴¹³ Tiegreen, Sara, and Elana Newman, “How News is ‘Framed’,” *Dart Center for Journalism & Trauma*, 2008. <http://dartcenter.org/content/how-news-is-framed>

Earthquakes and the Boston Bombings were predominantly driven by episodic frames (96% and 91% respectively), apparently leaving out any potential discussion about responsibility for the events or their impact.

Figure 4.14: Episodic vs. Thematic Frames by Event

Note: $\chi^2(3, N = 878) = 340.965, p < .001$

4.5 FROM THEIR PERSPECTIVE: ONLINE INTERVIEWS WITH CITIZEN JOURNALISTS

In this section, we will summarize findings from data collected via online interviews with a sample of bloggers who engaged in reporting/commentary functions during emergencies/crises. The section will focus on findings regarding the motivational aspects of citizen journalism (i.e., why interviewees engage in citizen reporting/commentary); citizen journalists' perceptions regarding what constitutes citizen journalism; and perceived differences between citizen journalism and professional journalism, particularly in terms of opportunities and challenges associated with reporting during an emergency.

4.5.1 Procedures and participants

For the online interviews, 48 citizen journalists, whose blog entries regarding Haiti Earthquake, Xynthia Storm, Gezi Park Protests, or Boston Bombings were content analyzed (summarized in the previous section), were contacted. Out of these 48 citizen journalists 20 responded back and out of the 20 citizen journalists who responded back seven completed an online interview. These seven respondents had previously reported about Gezi Park Protests or Haiti Earthquake. None of the citizen journalists who had covered the Xynthia Storm or Boston Bombings completed the interview.

The discussion guide for the online interviews is available in Appendix 2. Particularly given the sensitive issues that they cover (e.g., protests), in order to protect the anonymity of the respondents no personal identification information other than information about the gender of the respondent was recorded and consequently none will be reported. This also means that we will not engage in a first-order linkage analysis of the content produced by the journalists and their responses to the interview questions.

Data analysis process included a grounded theory coding of the collected data in terms of the identified concepts, themes and events and analysis of the coded data in terms of the theoretical background provided in the literature review.

4.5.2 Main findings

4.5.2.1 The identity of "citizen journalist"

As discussed in Section 2.2. of this chapter, the question of what constitutes citizen journalism continues to be a frequently debated one. For example, there is considerable disagreement regarding whether "commentary" that provides an opportunity for sense making for other citizens should be considered as citizen journalism. Likewise, the extent to which citizen journalists should be able to enjoy the same privileges as "professional journalists" has been widely debated.⁴¹⁴

Among our interviewees, some respondents used broad definitions of citizen journalism. For example, according to interviewee #1, who defines himself as a citizen journalist, "being a citizen journalist means keeping people informed on issues one finds to be important through communications channels which are either digital or not." Interviewee #2 also defines anyone

⁴¹⁴ Boehm, Eric, "Feinstein wants to limit who can be a journalist," *Watchdog.org*, August 12 2013, <http://watchdog.org/100682/feinstein-wants-to-limit-who-can-be-a-journalist/>

who writes on events “with a certain level of elaboration/carefulness” as a citizen journalist. Experiences of both interviewees during Gezi Park protests corroborate their understanding of citizen journalism – informing others by writing on events or by sharing photographs during a crisis in which mainstream media channels are perceived to be weak in coverage. This is not a case only applicable to political crises such as Gezi Park protests. Interviewee #6, who reported on Haiti earthquake which, according to him, got inadequate coverage in the mainstream media, states that “citizen journalism is about calling politicians and elites to account, to get the public to focus on what is happening around them, to participate in democracy” and describes a citizen journalist as a person who is independent and who wants to inform public on important issues to get them think about it.

On the other hand, other interviewees used a very strict definition of citizen journalist and indeed indicated that they would not categorize themselves as citizen journalists. For example, interviewee #3, who does not define herself as a citizen journalist, grounds her claim on the fact that she did not engage in reporting on-site. Interviewee #5 also does not define himself as a citizen journalist, even though he mentions that he reported on Gezi Park protests to provide an “inside perspective” due to his incidental presence during the events. He grounds his claim not to be a citizen journalist by mentioning that he is “just someone who likes to write about journalism.” Throughout the interview, he also mentions that he is not writing journalistic content but writing on the concept of “journalism” itself.

These interviews indicate that at least some bloggers construct a hierarchy in their conceptualization of citizen journalism. Namely, for some, on-site reporting is a prerequisite of being considered as a citizen journalist. Yet, for others, being able to contribute to the information environment by engaging in functions related to filtering, agenda-setting and sense making should be sufficient to categorize a person as a citizen journalist. These respondents also underline the need to adhere to ethical boundaries set about information and reporting accuracy.

4.5.2.2 What motivates a citizen journalist

Our analysis of interviewees' remarks indicates that one of the primary, but not only, reasons that drove them to engage in online reporting or commentary is the perceived lack of coverage in mainstream media. In other words, citizens may choose to engage in journalistic activity themselves when they feel that the gatekeeping function of mainstream media work in a way that does not reflect their daily lives accurately. For example Interviewee #7 states that:

The first time that I used the online tool back to 2008 when I thought we need to show the other face of Iraq, not face that contain bombing, etc., the other face of daily life in Iraq, when they celebrate and see the good life of Iraq, because when you want to use the Search engine, you will find just car bombed, etc. (Interviewee #7)

Likewise, interviewee #1 stresses the fact that “all the news in the Internet were same in terms of both style and content” which led to his choice of engaging more in news gathering and dissemination processes.

It should also be noted that interviewees were also motivated by the desire to share their political opinions in ways that, they wish, are going to help influence public opinion and attitudes. For example, Interviewee #1's comments indicate that he was motivated also by the desire to write about his political opinions. Similarly, interviewee #4 mentions that his online authorship began with writing comments, critiques and research on online music and cinema forums and evolved into commenting on the current events. In many ways, this shows the

multifaceted nature of citizen journalism in which citizen journalists are able to contribute to various phases including opinions authorship, news gathering, news reporting and dissemination, etc.

While general themes on motivation are in agreement with the motivation to publish opinions with the aim of changing attitudes and sharing information, there were a few instances where interviewees indicated that they were also motivated by the potential income they could earn from journalistic activities. For example, Interviewee #6 states:

Partly I wrote for the enjoyment and being curious to learn more, partly to see if I could earn a supplementary income. There was no specific incident that caused me to start writing but I did find myself gravitating to environmental, humanitarian and astronomical topics, all areas where I had an interest. On the environmental and humanitarian aspects, I hope that in some small way, what I write about will cause people to stop and think and maybe make the world a better place.

While the definition of citizen journalism as it is discussed in the literature review stresses the aspect of not being professionally trained to become a journalist,⁴¹⁵ the motivation to earn income through writing on the Internet may be problematic in terms of the “independence” of citizen journalism.

Unsurprisingly, we see that the underlying motivations of interviewees to report about the emergencies were similar to their reported reasons for engaging in citizen journalism in general. With respect to the Gezi Protests, interviewee #1 states that his aim was to “...reveal the police violence and to provide informational flow in order to prevent disinformation.” Interviewee #7 refers to the concept of “awareness”, which is in line with the motivation to publish opinions and change attitudes.

Likewise, with regard to citizen reporting of the aftermath of the Haiti earthquake, interviewee #6 mentions that:

This was a topic which I felt had slipped off the radar of public consciousness. I'd seen a TV documentary some time after the earthquake which told of the suffering of Haitians, still living in 'temporary' camps long after the earthquake struck. I think the documentary stuck in my mind and at a later date, I spotted a press release on Haiti via the UN News service which I had started to use semi-regularly as a source for articles on matters of humanitarian interest. The fact that almost 3 years on from the quake, nothing much seemed to have happened, prompted me, I think, to try and raise the profile of the Haitian people who have suffered so much. (Interviewee #6)

Moreover, Interviewee #2 states that his engagement in citizen journalism began in the first day of Gezi Park protests due to the “ambience” of the day and the lack of mainstream media coverage. In terms of his motivations, Interviewee #2 also mentions that it was hard to reach quality content also on the Internet; therefore, filtering digital content in terms of quality emerges as another important function of citizen journalists.

These remarks show the importance of lack of coverage or lack of adequate coverage in the mainstream media as a source of motivations for individuals to engage in the production and dissemination of journalistic content. Interviewee #6 also mentions that “Citizen journalists have an opportunity to re-visit such events when the media caravan has moved on and deal with matters in more depth – hopefully to the advantage of those affected by a disaster.” To a

⁴¹⁵ Cited in Dugan, Molly A, Dan Smith, and Leonard Witt, “Journalism Ethics and the Independent Journalist,” No. September 2004, 2007, pp. 801–811 [p. 804]

great extent, particularly in instances when events are no longer deemed newsworthy for mainstream media (and this is certainly the case for emergencies with long term impacts such as the Haitian Earthquake) the concept of “re-visiting” the events underlines an important role that citizen journalists may play in terms of the aforementioned sense making related agenda setting function of citizen journalism.

As it is seen especially in Interviewee #2 and #6, emergencies and political crises are events which have the potential to encourage people to engage in processes of production and dissemination of information and opinions through convenient channels especially when mainstream media are perceived to be weak in coverage. In addition, abundance of information and opinions in the Internet creates a need to filter online content.

To sum up, our analyses underline four main factors that contribute to individuals' motivations to engage in citizen reporting and commentary: 1) a motivation to share one's opinions on issues relevant to personal interests and contribute to attitude change in the society through online media – in other words, raising awareness, 2) lack of coverage of certain events by the mainstream media, 3) uniformity in the mainstream media in terms of both style and content – lack of alternative voices, 4) need to filter online content.

4.5.2.3 What sets citizen journalism apart? Opportunities and challenges

When inquired about how citizen journalism activities differ from “professional” journalism activities in established mainstream media institutions, one reference that was commonly made by the interviewees was the extent of control they had over content and perspective. For example, Interviewee #2 emphasizes “working without censorship” as a main difference of citizen journalists from professional journalists. Similarly, Interviewee #4 states that “I feel freer with regard to selection of words and sentences” and “I determine the topics, *I do not try to make anyone happy*” (emphasis added). According to interviewee #5, citizen journalists are “untrained and unconstrained.”

There is no political agenda except one's own, if a citizen journalist so chooses. Mostly, I'll write the facts without adding my own political slant. If I do add comment, then I can do so from the heart, reflecting what I believe, rather than reflect the policy of a newspaper proprietor. There is very fundamental editorial independence.

These remarks point out that editorial independence, or the lack of editorial supervision and pressure, as well as being free from (potentially commercial) concerns about satisfying reader wishes, are among the main differences of citizen journalism from professional journalism.

With respect to emerging news writing styles in citizen journalism, interviewee #1 indicates that:

I do not care for the inverted pyramid rule which is adhered by classical journalism, I do not use it in most cases. I often use chronological news narratives. I differ from the production in the media sector through content building tools such as Storify. (Interviewee #1)

In addition, interviewee #2 believes that “it is inevitable that a new generation of journalists will emerge through applications such as ‘stringwire’ on the Internet.” Hence, emerging news writing styles, especially online services which allow the building of chronological news narratives based on user-generated content, is seen as an important aspect of citizen journalism as far as the interviewees are concerned.

Respondents mention that citizen journalists are able to act more quickly than professional journalists with regard to publishing news. Interviewee #1 says that he is able to publish information without engaging in a long process of fact-checking and that he checks user profiles, publishing time and location if provided and gives links to the user profiles by whom the content is created.

The practice of providing links to user profiles is in the logic of operation that is called as “publish, then filter” in citizen journalism as opposed to the “filter, then publish” logic of professional journalism.⁴¹⁶ Interviewee #6 mentions that he uses “multiple sources” to check the authenticity of information, he uses online news channels with good reputation, and he checks publication time and location when provided.

Interviewee #2, who reported during Gezi Park protests, mentions that he tried to gather more information by consulting protestors who are identifiable in photographs; however, this was not possible all the time due to time pressure. In terms of fact-checking, on the other hand, he argues that his writings were composed of emotions rather than facts and the photos he shared were self-exploratory and there was little need for fact-checking.

On the other hand, there are those citizen journalists, such as interviewees #3 and #4, who argue that they do not experience any pressure to publish immediately and they do not face any dilemmas in terms of fact-checking. Interviewee #3 simply states that she does not experience any pressure of immediacy. Interviewee #4 also says that he does not experience any pressure since he is engaged in critique and analysis rather than news gathering and dissemination. As was the case in the previous section regarding definitions of citizen journalism, with respect to the balance between fact-checking and immediacy of coverage, these remarks underline the need to differentiate between citizen journalism as opinion authorship and news reporting.

In addition, another important difference and aspect of citizen journalism, reliance on official press releases and reports, is experienced by one of the respondents specifically in international reporting. Interviewee #6 states that “Inevitably, since I am not 'on site' for many international reports, I have to rely on press releases, news services, and other news outlets - nor do I have the resources of a Reuters, AFP or BBC at my disposal.” Since they do not have the resources which can be accessed by professional journalists, citizen journalists may be compelled to rely on official press releases. In Waldman, we saw that reliance on official account of events was caused by the pressure of immediacy.⁴¹⁷ In the case of interviewee #6, we see that the reliance on official press releases can be caused by lack financial resources and lack of sufficient human resources in the context of international reporting by citizen journalists.

Another difference, and also a challenge, of citizen journalism from professional journalism concerns the level of protection received when they report on-site. Interviewee #4 talks about his on-site experiences during Gezi Protests: “Since I am also a photographer, it was hard to take photos freely without the press card. The fact that security forces asked press card all the time prevented us recording some of the witnessing on-site.” Hence, the lack of press card means lack of protection in terms of collection of data on-site.

⁴¹⁶ Cited in Bowman, Shayne, and Chris Willis, “We Media: How Audiences Are Shaping the Future of News and Information,” *The Media Center at the American Press Institute*, 2003.
http://www.hypergene.net/wemedia/download/we_media.pdf [p. 12]

⁴¹⁷ Waldman, Steven, “The Media Food Chain and the Functions of Journalism,” *The Information Needs of Communities: The Changing Media Landscape in a Broadband Age*, Carolina Academic Press, Durham, NC, 2011, pp. 242–247 [p. 244]

None of the respondents in the study reported any experience in terms of dealing with the privacy and trust issues in terms of information sources. This point seems relevant in both reliance on official press releases and fact-checking. As shown in the remarks of respondents, some citizen journalists use online witnessing through social network sites and check the facts via user, time, and location information and let others check the facts by providing links to the original postings and user profiles; there are also citizen journalists who use official press releases of governments, international institutions, mainstream media channels and non-governmental organizations to be able to write on worldwide events.

In sum, with respect to the main differences between citizen and “professional” journalism, the interviews underline five key points:

- 1) Citizen journalists typically perceive that they enjoy higher editorial independence in terms of topic, wording, opinion, etc.,
- 2) Changes in news writing style via online services and applications such as *Storify* and *Stringwire* which enable users to create chronological news stories based on user-generated content allows citizens to challenge conventions such as the inverted pyramid
- 3) For citizen journalists, “publish and then filter” approach to reporting creates a different, and apparently delicate, balance between immediacy and fact-checking.
- 4) For some citizen journalists, lack of access to on-site reporting capabilities, particularly while covering international events, leads to reliance on official press releases. This may potentially diminish citizen journalists' ability to offer original information. Yet, a subset of citizen journalists do not consider this as a constituting a problem because they believe that their contribution will be in terms of offering new frames/interpretations of existing information.
- 5) Another important challenge for citizen journalists is the lack of protection which is enjoyed by professional journalists.

4.6 CONCLUSION

With the emergence of new media technologies that enable individuals to be producers (and reproducers), as well as being consumers, of content, important changes in the landscape of news reporting have taken place. Online networks have the potential to give voice to citizens, allowing them to challenge the monopoly that mainstream media institutions have had over production and dissemination of information. A concept that underlines this “democratization” of news/information production and dissemination is “citizen journalism.”

Citizen journalism have been claimed to be different from conventional forms of journalism in many respects, including, but not limited to, how authentication of information works and the nature of witnessing, agenda-setting, and sense-making. In the light of these potential changes that are brought about by citizen journalism, the aim of this chapter was to investigate the role that citizen journalists may assume in news production and information dissemination during emergencies and crises.

The chapter had four major sections.

The aim of the first section was to summarize the debates about the factors that have contributed to the rise of citizen journalism and what citizen journalism entails. Here several important points need to be underlined:

- Emergence of citizen journalism is as much the result of what has been named as a “democratic deficit” in mainstream media, as it is the result of technological developments that make production of content easier.
- Despite the frequent use of the concept “citizen journalism”, there is no agreed upon definition.
 - Conservative definitions of citizen journalism typically emphasize the prerequisite that citizen journalists engage in newsgathering.
 - However, related to the first point mentioned about the “democratic deficit” in mainstream media, most conceptualizations of citizen journalism emphasize the transformation of media users into active contributors to production and dissemination of information. Such definitions typically, but not always, include a number of activities like current affairs blogging, eyewitness reporting, and commentary as part of citizen journalism.

The second section provided an overview of key opportunities offered by and challenges for citizen journalism within the context of emergency communications. In terms of opportunities, the section focused on decentralization of news making processes, recent rise of witness accounts in citizen journalism, and citizen journalism’s potential as a fifth estate that can provide checks and balances against powerful institutions within the society (including mainstream media). However, there are also key problems that are faced by citizen journalists:

- Continuing digital divide means that certain segments of the population still are excluded from the democratization of access provided by online networks.

- Reliability of information, particularly during emergencies when there is a push for being the first to beat, may suffer, leading many citizen journalists to, unwittingly, contribute to the spread of false information. This problem requires the development of approaches like the “tier 1.5 approach”, which creates cooperation between professional and citizen journalists in fact-checking and editing processes. One potential pitfall of such approaches, however, may be the cooptation of citizen journalism by mainstream media.

The third section engaged in a content analysis of citizen journalists' coverage of four recent emergencies: Xynthia Storm (Europe), Boston Bombings, Gezi Protests (Turkey), and Haiti Earthquake.

The findings from this content analysis reveal several important points that are in line with the discussions from the previous sections:

- While reporting of straight news is the dominant form of journalistic activity for citizen journalists reporting about these crises, a considerable proportion of content can be categorized as opinions and commentary (34%).
- In line with the notion that citizen journalism provides an opportunity for democratization of information production and dissemination, citizen journalists reporting about these events were more likely to report what they witnessed during these crises (30%) than they were to recycle content from mainstream media sources (8%) and wire services (8%).
- Likewise, we observed that citizen journalists frequently utilize other citizens as their sources of information. About 30% of the information sources cited by citizen journalists were citizens (as victims, witnesses or protestors). Although we do not have comparative data from mass media, these numbers are indicative of the increased voice that regular citizens may have as a result of citizen journalism activities.
- On the other hand, in terms of whose criticisms get heard via citizen journalism, we observed that citizens (5%) are not among the top choices that citizen journalists utilize. Rather, citizen journalists tend to either criticize an institution themselves (21%) or give voice to criticisms raised by politicians (19%).
- There were mixed results with respect to the “witnessing” element of citizen journalism. That is, only in the reporting of Gezi Protests did we see that witnessing was the dominant form of reporting. This may be due to the differences in the nature of the emergencies. Namely, protests typically last longer and are more predictable in terms of where/when newsworthy material will be available than sudden emergencies like an earthquake or a bombing. In fact, we observe that use of audio-visuals as parts of witnessing of events were higher in two relatively longer lasting and predictable emergencies/crises: Gezi Protests and Xynthia Storm.
- When emotions are reported, citizen journalists tend to make generalized references to the collective emotions of the public. This is indicative that as part of the public, citizen journalists implicitly assume/claim an ability to speak for public sentiments.
- Despite the editorial independence, while writing about emergencies, citizen journalists tend to adhere to news writing conventions that are often associated with mainstream media. This is evident in the dominance of “episodic” frames, which are

characterized by writing about an isolated event rather than providing information that can help readers understand the context of the event.

The final section of the chapter summarized findings from online interviews conducted with a subsample of the citizen journalists who reported about Xynthia Storm (Europe), Boston Bombings, Gezi Protests (Turkey), and Haiti Earthquake. This data indicates that:

- Citizen journalists were typically motivated by their disillusionment with the coverage of current events (and emergencies) in mainstream media. Here, citizen journalists underlined two dimensions of their own functions: 1) challenging the monopoly that mainstream media institutions have over agenda setting; 2) offering perspectives (sense making) that often get filtered out in mainstream media.
- The respondents had different conceptualizations of what constitutes “citizen journalism”. Some respondents utilized a very conservative definition of citizen journalism by indicating that unless a person does on-site reporting, he or she should not be considered as a citizen journalist. Others, on the other hand, indicated that any contribution to the sense-making ability of the public should count as citizen journalism.
- Based on these discussions regarding what constitutes “citizen journalism”, we see three categories of approaches to citizen journalism:
 - Reporting based on user-generated content – it is on-site reporting when the generated content belongs to the citizen journalist herself,
 - Reporting/commenting based on information from official and/or mainstream sources
 - Opinion authorship.
- Citizen journalists often underlined their conscious decision not to adhere to the writing styles and conventions (inverted pyramid) associated with mainstream journalism. However, the readers of the report should also bear in mind that our content analysis indicates that use of episodic frames in emergency reporting by citizen journalists may potentially contradict with this claim.
- Citizen journalists believe that during emergencies, they have an advantage over mainstream media journalists because they can sidestep long fact-checking processes through what they call the “publish and then filter” approach. Other citizen journalists indicate that fact-checking is less of a concern for them because they report perspectives and emotions. The implications of this approach for reliability of information needs to be further studied; however, we believe that such comments are indicative that “reliability of information” will continue to be a key problem in citizen journalism, particularly during emergencies when the need to be quick in reporting events may be more pressing.

4.7 APPENDIX 1 – CONTENT ANALYSIS CODING INSTRUCTIONS

Procedures and Definitions

The aim of this section is to define and describe main elements of the coding procedure.

Number of Articles to Be Analysed

For each emergency/crisis (e.g., Gezi, Boston Bombings), 5 randomly selected articles (about crises or emergencies as defined in WP1) from each selected citizen journalism source should be analysed. If there are less than 5 entries, all available entries should be analysed.

Analysis File

Using the Content Analysis Coding Protocol provided below,

The analysis of citizen journalist articles will be performed on the following excel sheets depending on the partner:

TASKS/TASK_4_1_3/KU/CitizenJournalist_ContentAnalysis/Analysis/CA_DATA_KU.xls

TASKS/TASK_4_1_3/HRT/CitizenJournalist_ContentAnalysis/Analysis/ CA_DATA_HRT.xls

Entry

An **entry** refers to each article with a separate title and a date.

Unit of Analysis

Each **paragraph** of an article **entry** should be analysed as a separate **unit**. Hence, each paragraph of the entry will be coded in a separate line in the excel file.

Coding of Block Quotations

A block quotation is a form quotation that is set off from the main text as a paragraph and is distinguished visually from the main text using indentation and a different typeface or smaller size font. When coding a block quotation, the quotation should be coded as a part of the paragraph that it follows. Block quotations should not be coded as a separate unit.

Coding Protocol

For each paragraph within each article, complete the following information in the excel file created for each partner.

TASKS/TASK_4_1_3/KU/CitizenJournalist_ContentAnalysis/Analysis/CA_DATA_KU.xls

TASKS/TASK_4_1_3/HRT/CitizenJournalist_ContentAnalysis/Analysis/CA_DATA_HRT.xls

Section 1. Document Record Information

(please repeat this procedure for each paragraph you are coding)

- 1.1. Coder ID
- 1.2. Write the address of the webpage from which the article is coming from
- 1.3. Write the name of the DOC file containing the entry
- 1.4. Title of the article
- 1.5. If available, name of the citizen journalist (author of the article)
- 1.6. If country information (of the journalist or the site) is available, please enter country name. If not available, please write N/A
- 1.7. Publication Date yyyy/mm/dd
- 1.8. Copy the unit (paragraph) to excel sheet

Section 2. Entry Characteristics

2.1 Category that best describes the type of emergency/disaster/crisis unit is discussing

- 1 Flood
- 2 Extreme Temperature
- 3 Storm
- 4 Wildfire
- 5 Earthquake
- 6 Man-Made Disaster (intentional act of terrorism-violence or threat of violence)
- 7 Man-Made Disaster (Other)
- 8 Social/Political Protest
- 9 Other

2.2 Info-Commentary prominence in unit.

- 1 Straight news/information (coverage/updates about the with little or no personal/subjective statements or opinions)
- 2 Commentary/opinion is prominent

2.3. Does the unit contain information sourced from the following?

		Yes	No
2.3.1	Mainstream news source: Newspaper, Television (or its website, social media site)	1	0
2.3.2	Mainstream news source: Wire service (or its website)	1	0
2.3.3	Other Citizen Journalists: Tweets or social media entries of journalists not affiliated with a mainstream source	1	0
2.3.4	News Source – Identified (an individual, an expert, an organization that is quoted or cited; the identity of the source can be indicated in the current unit or somewhere else in the entry).	1	0
2.3.5	News Source - Unidentified	1	0
2.3.6	Primary information (by personal observation, reporting from point of crisis)	1	0

2.4. (If 2.3.3 = 1 Other Citizen Journalist = Yes) Please record the URL of the sourced citizen journalist.

2.5. (If 2.3.6. = 1 Primary information = Yes) Does the unit contain visuals, videos, sound clips that can be used to verify the primary information that the citizen journalist has collected?

- 1 Yes, Photo
- 2 Yes, Video and Audio Recording
- 3 Yes, Only Audio Recording
- 0 No

2.6. (If 2.3.4 = 1 News Source – Identified) Which of the following sources were quoted (using a quotation mark or a block quotation)?

		Yes	No
2.6.1	Industry, Business Organizations	1	0
2.6.2	Government agency representatives or political authorities	1	0
2.6.3	Representatives of NGOs, Emergency Response Organizations	1	0
2.6.4	Representatives of a group claimed to be responsible for terrorism	1	0
2.6.5	Private citizens identified as aid workers, rescue volunteers, doctors	1	0
2.6.6	Private citizens identified as protestors, organizers of protests	1	0
2.6.7	Private citizens identified as victims	1	0
2.6.8	Private citizens identified as observers/witnesses	1	0
2.6.9	A person who is identified as an expert regarding the issue	1	0

2.7. (If 2.3.4 = 1 News Source – Identified) Which of the following sources were cited?

		Yes	No
2.7.1	Industry, Business Organizations	1	0
2.7.2	International or national government agency representatives or political authorities	1	0
2.7.3	Representatives of NGOs, Emergency Response Organizations	1	0
2.7.4	Representatives of a group claimed to be responsible for terrorism	1	0
2.7.5	Private citizens identified as aid workers, rescue volunteers, doctors	1	0
2.7.6	Private citizens identified as protestors, organizers of protests	1	0
2.7.7	Private citizens identified as victims	1	0
2.7.8.	Private citizens as observers/witnesses	1	0
2.7.9.	A person who is identified as an expert regarding the issue	1	0

2.8. Does the unit contain a criticism targeting the following?

		Yes	No
2.8.1	Industry, Business Organizations – Non-media business	1	0
2.8.2	Media Companies	1	0
2.8.3	International or national government agency representatives or political authorities	1	0
2.8.4	NGOs, Emergency Response Organizations	1	0
2.8.5	Private citizens (e.g., for not being calm, not being informed, for acting violently in a protest etc.)	1	0

2.9. Does the unit contain a criticism voiced...

		Yes	No
2.9.1	Directly by the author of the article without citing a source	1	0
2.9.2	By an expert that the author cites/quotes	1	0
2.9.3	By a representative of a government/political authority that the author cites/quotes	1	0
2.9.4	By an NGO, Emergency Response organization that the author cites/quotes	1	0
2.9.5	By private citizens or by the general public	1	0

2.10. Does the unit make a reference to/discuss undue pressure (such as censorship, financial pressure, surveillance) that may impede on civil liberties (freedom of speech, privacy, freedom of association)?

- 1 Yes
- 1 No

2.11. To what extent does the unit express negative emotions such as sadness, anger, frustration, disappointment?

Not at all		Somewhat				Very much	
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	

2.12. (Code If 2.11 > 0) Which of the following best describes the expression of negative emotion?

- 1 Reporting emotion through quotes (attributing emotions to specific others)
- 2 Indirect description of emotion (references to collective emotions)
- 3 Authorial emotions (entry author expressing his/her emotions)

2.13. To what extent does the unit express or implicitly reveal non-negative emotions such as happiness, hope, or excitement?

Not at all		Somewhat				Very much	
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	

2.14. (Code If 2.13 > 0) Which of the following best describes the expression of positive emotion?

- 1 Reporting emotion through quotes (attributing emotions to specific others)
- 2 Indirect description of emotion (references to collective emotions)
- 3 Authorial emotions (entry author expressing his/her emotions)

2.15. Does the unit apply a thematic frame that focuses on broader social trends related to and implications of the incident or an episodic frame that focuses on the isolated incident?

- 1 Thematic Frame (incident and social causes/implications/trends)
- 2 Episodic Frame (isolated incident)

4.8 APPENDIX 2 – INTERVIEW DISCUSSION GUIDE

1. Can you tell us about the first time when you decide to use online tools to report or comment about current events and issues? Can you tell us about whether there was specific incident that lead to your decision? [PROBE IF NOT YET MENTIONED] What were the reasons that prompted this decision?
2. Specifically, what motivated you cover the [HAITI EARTHQUAKE/GEZI PROTESTS/BOSTON BOMBING/XYNTHIA STORM]?
3. Based on your personal experience in gathering information, writing and sharing your reports, connecting with your readers etc., how would you say your own reporting activities differ from journalists who report for mainstream media?
4. How do you think these differences that you mentioned previously influenced your coverage of [HAITI/GEZI/BOSTON/XYNTHIA]?
5. Again, comparing yourself to journalists reporting for mainstream media, who may often have a number of privileges like access to information sources, protection of confidential sources etc., what would you say are the main challenges you face as a citizen journalist? How do you cope with these challenges? [PROBE IF NOT YET MENTIONED] While answering this question, please also think about the experience you had while report [HAITI/GEZI/BOSTON/XYNTHIA].
6. Conversely, particularly in reporting of natural disasters or incidents like protests, bombings, what are the advantages you think you have over journalists working for mainstream media?
7. Information sources may have a hard time trusting a citizen journalist over issues like anonymity and confidentiality. How do you build rapport with your information sources? What are the measures you take to protect your sources of information?
8. If you had any such issues during [HAITI/GEZI/BOSTON/XYNTHIA], can you briefly summarize how you handled your source and the information he/she provide?
9. As a citizen journalist, what methods do you use to check the accuracy of the information you publish? [PROBE] During coverage of emergencies, how do you cope with the pressure to publish increasingly more quickly while maintaining accuracy?
10. How do you think emergency and crisis reporting will change in the future in the context of citizen journalism and mass media?
11. According to you, what does it mean to be a citizen journalist? Would you classify yourself as one? Why, or why not?

Chapter 5: Conclusion

5 CONCLUSION

The increased penetration of communication technologies and social media applications may present important opportunities for emergency preparedness and response. One such opportunity concerns the incorporation of citizens into emergency communications, emergency preparedness and response. Also, the rise of self-publishing applications and mobile recording devices can potentially transform individuals from being passive consumers to being producers and distributors of information, thereby contributing to the information environment during an emergency. The networking capabilities offered by new communication technologies also mean that citizens—as social activists or emergency response volunteers—can organize and coordinate their actions more efficiently.

Given these potential benefits brought about by communication technologies in enhancing citizens' involvement in emergency communications in general, and emergency preparedness, mobilization and response in particular, the aim of this report was to examine the role that media technologies may play citizens' involvement in emergency communications. Specifically, the report focused on three roles that citizens may assume in emergency and crisis communications:

- 1) Citizens as first responders/volunteers
- 2) Citizens as social activists
- 3) Citizens as journalists/reporters

5.1 CITIZENS AS FIRST RESPONDERS

- Citizens' involvement in emergency response via social media can potentially supplement existing data about emergencies with crowd-sourced information. Also, citizens can contribute to filtering and making sense of existing information for emergency response functions such as crisis mapping.
- Emergency response training can be made easier, more accessible and engaging for the public through the use of utilities like simulation games, interactive applications, or virtual reality.
- While conventional methods of emergency preparedness training, such as workshops, training videos or pamphlets are still dominant in the countries we analyzed (Turkey, Greece, Italy, UK), we see increasing utilization of creative methods for training citizens. For example,
 - In Turkey, AKUT, a volunteer organization that provides emergency recovery and rescue services, uses G-Force simulators (which travel through Turkey) to raise awareness about the impact of earthquakes.
 - In Greece, in the Seismopolis project that the OASP participated in, training via virtual reality was among the techniques that were utilized to enhance pupils' knowledge about earthquakes.

- Two related approaches for involving citizens in emergency preparedness are seen across different countries we analyzed.
 - First, in all countries, volunteer organizations and government agencies use various communication methods actively to recruit and train rescue volunteers.
 - Second, as examples from UK and Turkey suggest, a potentially useful strategy is to develop community leader programs (in the U.K., with respect to Floods, these community leaders are called Flood Plan Leaders), who can act as a bridge between the community and agencies before, during and after an emergency.
- As our analysis of Italy suggests, absence of common approaches at the national level, regional imbalances and inconsistencies, budget limitations that mar the development of technological means of reaching out to the public, and low levels of cooperation among local officers of emergency organizations are the key obstacles that may impede on the effective utilization of different communication methods to create, maintain and utilize a network of volunteers that can support authorities.
- While community involvement is considered as an important goal across all countries we analyzed, the type of involvement is typically an asymmetric one in that response organizations and government agencies see citizens as stakeholders that need to be trained but do not pay sufficient attention to soliciting intelligence from the public to improve emergency response. One notable exception that we observed was AFAD from Turkey, which has, in different occasions, created calls for projects for design and implementation ideas for earthquake preparedness from regular citizens (and not solely experts, academicians and researchers).
- Across all different countries, one important problem that we observed was the inconsistent accessibility or availability of training materials online, and particularly in social media platforms. This may reduce the likelihood that a large portion of the population, mostly of younger age, will have the opportunity to stay informed on important safety topics.

5.2 CITIZENS AS SOCIAL ACTIVISTS

- Contemporary social activist formations, which benefit from online networks for organization, coordination and governance, have three important characteristics:
 - **Glocal action and coordination:** While issues that motivate activists may often be local in nature, they nevertheless build networks at global levels to share their ideas and build solidarity.
 - **Horizontal organization structures:** The networking logic has important implications for how contemporary activist formations organize. They typically have horizontal organizations with little hierarchy; they emphasize direct participation in decision making processes. This structure contrasts starkly with traditional forms of political organizing which are based on rigid leadership structures that limit the engagement of the individual.
 - **Autonomous flexibility:** Online communications and networking logic also enable social activist formations to be highly dynamic in the sense that individuals and groups can quickly enter or exit formations, form affinity groups that can easily dissolve once a goal is attained. As we have seen with respect to Occupy

Sandy, which was organized by activists from the Occupy Wallstreet movement, this autonomous flexibility creates opportunities not only for social activism but also for efficient response to natural disasters.

- With the increased penetration of new media technologies and social media applications, every individual can potentially induce the formation of networks or become the locus of a network.
- An increasingly common form of social activism, which can be named as “Occupation” illustrates the highly symbiotic nature of the relationship between “offline” action, online organization, and utilization of conventional media. As such, we see that “occupations” have several important functions:
 - They create spaces where forms of autonomy are experimented.
 - They facilitate the development, extension and strengthening of networks, which can then be maintained loosely via social networks
 - They help increase public visibility, which is also needed for media attention, which in turn may help increase public visibility further.
 - They help intensify the experience of solidarity.
- New communication and information technologies, including mobile phones, recording devices, blogs, and microblogs are crucial for social activist formations' ability to build networks, mobilize, make decisions, engage in sousveillance, and build global awareness about their cause.
- However, for social activists, the media mix still needs to be diverse in the sense that relying solely on social media platforms will not be sufficient to reach out to the public with ideas.

5.3 CITIZENS AS JOURNALISTS

- Emergence of citizen journalism is as much the result of what has been named as a “democratic deficit” in mainstream media, as it is the result of technological developments that make production of content easier.
- Citizen journalism is argued to be different from conventional forms of journalism in terms of processes related to authentication of information, the nature of witnessing, agenda-setting, sense-making, and the extent to which voices of the public can be heard.
- Interviews with citizen journalists who covered recent emergencies/crises like the Gezi Park Protests (Turkey) and Haiti Earthquakes indicates that citizen journalists were typically motivated by their disillusionment with the coverage of current events (and emergencies) in mainstream media. Accordingly, citizen journalists mentioned two main reasons for their engagement in citizen journalism:
 - challenging the monopoly that mainstream media institutions have over agenda setting;
 - offering perspectives (sense making) that often get filtered out in mainstream media.

- Data from content analysis of citizen journalists' coverage of recent emergencies/crisis partly confirm that citizen journalism may potentially bridge the democratic deficit by giving voice to those who would not have received it from mainstream media.
 - Citizen journalists reporting about emergencies were more likely to report what they witnessed rather than recycling content from mainstream media,
 - Citizen journalists frequently utilize other citizens as their sources of information,
 - On the other hand, we also observe that citizens' criticism of institutions during or in the aftermath of emergencies get little coverage from citizen journalists.
- The nature of an emergency/crisis may have a notable impact on the extent to which citizen journalism provides witnessing functions. For example, in citizen coverage of protests, which typically last long and are considerably predictable in terms of where/when events will occur, witnessing is more prevalent and systematic (intentional) than in sudden emergencies like earthquakes or bombing.
- Freedom from commercial concerns and editorial constraints can potentially enable citizen journalists to adopt writing styles that are less likely to be present in mainstream news outlets. In our interviews, we observed that citizen journalists often underlined their conscious decision not to adhere to the writing styles and conventions (inverted pyramid) associated with mainstream journalism. However, our content analysis data suggests that despite this editorial freedom, citizen journalists frequently adopt news reporting conventions, such as neutral reporting of events that are seen in conventional forms of journalism. For example, we observe that in citizen journalism accounts of the emergencies we focused on, "episodic" frames, which are characterized by writing about an isolated event rather than providing information that can help readers understand the context of the event, were dominant.
- An important factor that contributes to information reliability problems in citizen journalism is the "publish and then filter" approach that some citizen journalists adopt. This approach means that verification of information will occur *after* publication, at which time it is possible that potentially false information may have already been replicated, shared and circulated elsewhere.
- The problem of information reliability in citizen journalism may also be due to the fact that citizen journalists, who are not typically trained in reporting, are unaware of ethical codes within journalism. In fact, our interviews with citizen journalists have shown that some citizen journalists might even consider that not having to "fact-check" information gives them an edge over conventional sources of news in terms of the pace of reporting.
- Given the continuing issues regarding reliability of information during citizen coverage of emergencies, collaboration between mainstream media and citizen journalist may prove important in terms of transferring know-how and ethical awareness.